

DESIGN AND PERFORMANCE INVESTIGATION OF OWC SYSTEMS IN INDOOR AND OUTDOOR SCENARIOS

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Certificate

This is to certify that the thesis entitled "**Design and Performance Investigation of OWC Systems in Indoor and Outdoor Scenarios**" being submitted by **Mr. Pranav Sharda** to the Department of Electrical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, for the award of the degree of **Doctor of Philosophy** is the record of the bonafide research work carried out by him under my supervision. In my opinion, the thesis has reached the standards fulfilling the requirements of the regulations relating to the degree.

The results contained in this thesis have not been submitted either in part or in full to any other university or institute for the award of any degree or diploma.

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Abstract

Over the recent few years, optical wireless communication (OWC) has attracted significant attention in both academia and the research community. Contrary to radio frequency (RF) systems, the spatial confinement of the optical beams makes the OWC system a potential system offering higher data rates and secured communication. OWC systems find applications in several areas, such as terrestrial outdoor (free-space optical (FSO) communication), indoor and outdoor visible light communication (VLC), etc. For the terrestrial outdoor FSO systems, spatial diversity techniques are employed over FSO links to enhance the diversity and overall performance. To this end, the spatial diversity techniques corresponding to the state-of-the-art are repetition coding (RC), transmit laser selection (TLS), and orthogonal space-time block codes. Note that, TLS is the optimal transmission scheme in the FSO systems. In this dissertation, we name the conventional TLS scheme as a single TLS (STLS) scheme. However, the performance of the conventional STLS scheme is highly dependent on the feedback errors. On the other side, the outdoor VLC finds applications in vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) communications, infrastructure-to-vehicle (I2V) communications, etc. Emphasizing the state-of-the-art corresponding to the outdoor V2V-VLC systems, there is a lack of comprehensive modeling and performance investigation under the adverse challenges of the outdoor VLC environment. Moreover, to address the challenges of the next-generation-based outdoor intelligent transportation systems (ITSs), an indoor testbed design for an outdoor I2V-VLC system is still missing.

In order to enhance the diversity and overall performance of the terrestrial outdoor FSO systems, the study begins by proposing two novel TLS schemes. We call the proposed schemes as two TLS (TTLS) and modified error-tolerant weighting scheme

(METWS). Note that, the conventional STLS scheme gives optimal performance under a perfect feedback scenario. However, its performance degrades significantly under an imperfect feedback scenario. To this end, the two proposed schemes overcome the practical limitations of the conventional STLS scheme. Moreover, we analyze the performance of the two proposed schemes for both perfect and imperfect channel state information (CSI)-based communication scenarios. Further, different performance metrics, such as bit error rate (BER), diversity gain, etc., are thoroughly analyzed. Furthermore, to gain more insights, the performance of the two proposed schemes is also compared with the conventional STLS and RC schemes.

We then investigate the diversity-multiplexing tradeoff (DMT) for the OWC systems. To this end, we mainly focus on the indoor VLC and outdoor FSO systems. For the DMT investigation of the indoor VLC system, we consider the random radial movement of the end-user in the proposed system model. The optimal DMT for both the single-input single-output (SISO) and multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) VLC systems are analyzed. Novel analytical expressions for the probability distribution function (PDF), outage probability, and outage diversity order for the SISO-VLC and MIMO-VLC systems are derived. Moreover, we extend our study to the outdoor FSO system. For the first time in literature, a limited feedback-based DMT is investigated for the FSO system under different transmission scenarios. To this end, we consider a MIMO-FSO setup and investigate the DMT for single-rate and adaptive-rate transmission scenarios.

Further, we venture into the area of vehicular VLC and comprehensively explore the area of vehicular VLC. To this end, contrary to the state-of-the-art, we emphasize comprehensive modeling of the V2V-VLC system under the practical challenges of an outdoor VLC environment. For the first time, we model the vehicle's mobility as random with a specific PDF. Therefore, we emphasize a more realistic approach to model the vehicle's mobility. Moreover, a novel channel model that incorporates the joint impact of the outdoor V2V-VLC random path loss and atmospheric turbulence (AT) is emphasized. Further, different performance metrics are analytically examined, such as path loss, outage probability, average BER (ABER), diversity order, discrete-

input continuous-output memoryless channel (DCMC) capacity, etc., under different weather conditions.

We also extend our work on vehicular VLC by proposing a shadowing/blocking-based V2V-VLC model. In a line-of-sight (LOS) VLC system, the communication link is exposed to temporary shadowing due to physical obstructions by vehicles in the same lane or nearby parked vehicles. Since VLC is highly dependent on the LOS, proposing and analyzing a V2V-VLC model under a shadowing-based transmission scenario is of extreme importance. The performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model is analyzed with the DMT metric. Moreover, to minimize the path loss at the receiver (Rx), a novel hemispherical optical concentrator-based Rx structure (offering an omnidirectional gain) is also proposed. Some striking insights are envisioned for the proposed work.

Finally, as a part of the next-generation-based ITSs, we also develop an indoor testbed for an outdoor I2V-VLC system. For the first time in literature, we experimentally demonstrate the communication between the traffic light acting as the transmitter (Tx) and the camera (i.e., the Rx) under different realistic I2V-VLC scenarios in a controlled indoor environment. Moreover, all the experimental findings are demonstrated for different exposure times of the camera for the first time, which is a very critical parameter when using a camera-based Rx. Further, different performance metrics are experimentally examined, such as BER, peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), and capacity. Furthermore, LOS blockage-based communication scenarios are also experimentally analyzed.

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Abbreviations

ABER	Average Bit Error Rate
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
AT	Atmospheric Turbulence
BER	Bit Error Rate
CSI	Channel State Information
CSIT	Channel State Information at the Transmitter
DB	Dashboard
DMT	Diversity-Multiplexing Tradeoff
DCMC	Discrete-Input Continuous-Output Memoryless Channel
FSO	Free Space Optical
FOV	Field-of-View
I2V	Infrastructure-to-Vehicle
ITSs	Intelligent Transportation Systems
i.i.d.	independent and identically distributed
IM/DD	Intensity-Modulation/Direct-Detection
LOS	Line-of-Sight
LED	Light Emitting Diode
MISO	Multiple-Input Single-Output
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
NLOS	Non-Line-of-Sight
OWC	Optical Wireless Communication
OSTBCs	Orthogonal Space Time Block Codes
OOK	On/Off Keying

PD	Photodetector
PDF	Probability Distribution Function
RF	Radio Frequency
RV	Random Variable
RC	Repetition Coding
Rx	Receiver
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
STLS	Single Transmit Laser Selection
SISO	Single-Input Single-Output
Tx	Transmitter
TLS	Transmit Laser Selection
VLC	Visible Light Communication
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure

Notation

\approx	Approximately equal to
$<$	Less than
\leq	Less than equal
$>$	Greater than
\geq	Greater than equal
$\sqrt{\cdot}$	Square root
\doteq	Exponential equality
$\exp(\cdot)$	Exponential function (i.e., $e^{(\cdot)}$)
\mathbf{w}_i	i^{th} column of the identity matrix
\mathbf{w}	Vector
\mathbf{W}	Matrix
$[\cdot]_{M \times N}$	A matrix with M rows and N columns
$\text{Tr}(\cdot)$	Trace of matrix
\mathbf{I}_{L_t}	Identity matrix of order $L_t \times L_t$
$\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$	Expectation operator
$[\cdot]^T$	Transpose operator
$ \cdot $	Absolute value
$f(\cdot)$	PDF
$f(\cdot \cdot)$	Conditional PDF
$\text{Pr}[\cdot]$	Probability of event
P_e	Probability of error
P_c	Probability of correct detection
$Q(\cdot)$	Gaussian q-function

$\Gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$	Upper incomplete gamma function
$\Gamma(\cdot)$	Complete gamma function
$\log_x(y)$	The log, base x, of y
$G_{p,q}^{m,n} \left(\cdot \middle \cdot \right)$	Meijer-G function
$\inf(\cdot)$	Infimum of a function

Chapter 1

Introduction

With the growing increase in the number of users, the bandwidth requirement in wireless communication is also increasing exponentially. To this end, optical wireless communication (OWC) technology has emerged as a promising technology. OWC corresponds to the transmission of the optical signal in an unguided propagation medium such as the atmosphere, water, and vacuum [1]. Moreover, OWC offers unique features such as *(i)* High bandwidth, *(ii)* Unlicensed spectrum, *(iii)* Ease of deployment, *(iv)* Small size ($\approx 1/10$ the diameter of RF antenna), *(v)* Easy installation, *(vi)* Improved security, etc. Due to the availability of huge bandwidth, OWC technology is capable of supporting data rates up to 10 Gbps offering voice and video communication through the atmosphere/free-space. Nowadays, OWC is one of the most promising fields of research with the potential for impactful results, which will eventually bring revolution in the wireless market.

Based on the transmission range (see Fig. 1.1), OWC can be categorized into five different types. In this thesis, we focus on two domains of OWC, i.e., medium-range OWC (with a comprehensive focus on visible light communication (VLC)) and partially on long-range OWC, i.e., free-space optical (FSO) communication. **We first investigate the terrestrial outdoor FSO system (with an emphasis on diversity-improving techniques) and then the VLC system for indoor and outdoor**

Figure 1.1: Classification of OWC systems based on the transmission range.

scenarios with a primary focus on outdoor VLC.

1.1 Free-Space Optical Communication System

OWC systems are referred to as FSO communication systems when the unguided medium is the atmosphere. FSO communication system is also recognized as an outdoor terrestrial OWC system. It is a line-of-sight (LOS) technology that allows high-speed information transfer through the free-space between two well-aligned fixed nodes using an intensity-modulated optical signal. The typical transmission range of an FSO system is 4-5 km.

1.1.1 Advantages

The point-wise advantages of FSO systems are outlined as below [1]:

1. Unlicensed spectrum,

2. Ease of link establishment,
3. Economical installation and operational costs,
4. Highly secured due to narrow beam divergence angle of optical beam,
5. Free from electromagnetic interference.

All these advantages of the FSO system lead to several applications which are discussed in a point-wise manner as follows:

1.1.2 Applications

Several applications of FSO systems are discussed with examples as follows [2]:

1. **Enterprise/campus connectivity:** Corporate and campus networks that support ultra-high speeds can implement FSO systems without the need for specialized fiber optic connections.
2. **Reliable link and disaster recovery:** Disasters, terrorist attacks, and other crises necessitate prompt, dependable responses. In such situations wherein local infrastructure could be damaged or unreliable, short-term FSO links can be installed within hours.
3. **Surveillance:** In the modern era, surveillance cameras are widely deployed in commercial, public safety, and military applications. However, conventional wireless systems are not efficient in terms of providing high throughput for video streaming. To this end, FSO technology provides an alternative solution to support high quality video transmission.
4. **Back-haul for cellular systems:** Wireless communication bandwidth needs are growing rapidly along with the exponential growth in mobile phone users. Therefore, the deployment of FSO technology will meet the above goal and offer much higher throughput.

5. **High-quality broadcasting:** FSO systems can be deployed for the transmission of high-quality video and sound of a live event to the broadcasting station.

1.1.3 Limitations

The major limitations of the FSO systems are outlined as below:

1. **Environmental conditions:** Environmental conditions are time-dependent and change accordingly. It includes rain, fog, snow, dust, smoke, etc. These environmental conditions have a deteriorating impact on the properties of the optical signal, which may result in the complete blocking of the transmission path due to absorption and scattering [1].
2. **Atmospheric turbulence:** Atmospheric turbulence (AT) is a random phenomenon that occurs due to the change in the refractive index of air with time along the signal propagation path. It results in amplitude and phase fluctuations of the propagating light beam, which consequently affects the link performance, i.e., reduced signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and increased bit error rate (BER) [1–6].
3. **Pointing Errors:** Since the transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) nodes are well-aligned in FSO systems, therefore, a slight misalignment between the Tx and the Rx leads to pointing errors (PE) [2].

1.2 Visible Light Communication System

VLC is a subset of OWC technology that uses visible light of the electromagnetic spectrum to transfer data. The indoor OWC system, also known as VLC, corresponds to the transmission of the optical signal in the visible spectrum (400 THz to 800 THz). VLC systems use light-emitting diode (LED)-based lights and therefore are energy-efficient and low-cost [7]. LEDs have quick switching characteristics allowing intensity modulation at higher data rates, giving them illumination and communication capabilities [8]. In light of this, VLC is currently regarded as one of the most important

Figure 1.2: Geometrical model of the indoor VLC system implementation.

green communication technologies [9]. Fig. 1.2 illustrates the geometrical model of indoor VLC system with N transmitting LEDs and M end-users in a room. To send information to the end-users, the room's ceiling is covered with N transmitting LEDs. For the illustration purpose, we show a single transmitting LED. A particular transmitting LED is denoted by l_j , $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and a particular end-user is denoted by u_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$. As shown in Fig. 1.2, the LED Tx is placed at a height D (in metres) from the u_i end-user with angle of irradiance ϕ_{u_i} , the angle of incidence ψ_{u_i} and radius r_{u_i} on the polar coordinate plane. The euclidean distance between the l_j^{th} LED and the u_i^{th} PD Rx is denoted by d_{u_i} . Moreover, R_e denotes the maximum radius of a LED cell footprint.

Further, the inherent advantages of the VLC over radio frequency (RF) communications are given in a point-wise manner as follows [10]:

1.2.1 Advantages

The advantages of VLC systems in a point-wise manner are outlined as follows:

1. Huge Bandwidth [10],

2. **Low power consumption** due to the use of the optical components such as LEDs and photodetectors (PDs) which consume low power compared to costly RF alternatives [10], [11],
3. **Low cost** due to the use of optical components such as LEDs and PDs which are inexpensive, compact, lightweight [10], [11],
4. **No health concerns:** Compared to RF systems, VLC does not generate radiation that leads to public health concerns,
5. **Highly secured** due to narrow beam divergence angle of optical beam [10], [11],
6. VLC supports both illumination and communication and has low power consumption. Therefore, VLC is a power-efficient system.

All these advantages make VLC a promising technology and lead to several applications.

1.2.2 Applications

Several applications of VLC systems are discussed with examples as follows:

1. **Li-Fi:** A high-speed, bi-directional, enhanced visible light wireless communication method is called light fidelity (Li-Fi) [13]. Li-Fi is comparable to wireless fidelity (Wi-Fi), which communicates by RF.
2. **Vehicular communication:** VLC can be employed for vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) communication [10], [11]. Note that vehicle headlights/backlights can be used as the VLC Tx. Moreover, a PD (as the Rx) can be employed at the back of the following vehicle. Moreover, VLC can be employed in vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) scenario wherein the vehicle headlights can be used as the Tx and traffic light (infrastructure) as the Rx. Also, an infrastructure-to-vehicle (I2V)-based scenario can be implemented, with a traffic light as the Tx and an optical camera/PD (mounted at a specific position on the vehicle) as the Rx.

3. **Hospitals:** Hospitals are likely to transition to VLC since it won't interfere with the radio waves of the other machines in electromagnetic wave-sensitive regions (like MRI scanners).
4. **Information displaying signboards:** Airports, bus stations, and other locations where the dissemination of information is required use signboards with an array of LEDs to display information. For example, passengers can be provided information about nearby accommodations, dining, and entertainment alternatives by installing LED kiosks at airport exit points.
5. **Industrial applications:** An effective and dependable communication link is needed in the oil and gas industry for down-hole applications like wells and boreholes. VLC, which provides significantly faster data rates at a reasonable price, could be used for this purpose.

1.2.3 Limitations

The limitations of VLC systems in a point-wise manner are outlined as follows:

1. VLC is highly dependent on LOS and therefore requires both Tx and Rx to be in LOS [10].
2. VLC-based communication systems have interference issues from other ambient light sources. For instance, background-induced noise [11].
3. VLC supports a short communication range [10], [11].
4. Challenging to integrate VLC with wireless-fidelity (Wi-Fi) system.
5. Other drawbacks of the VLC system are atmospheric absorption, shadowing, beam dispersion, etc.

Based on the application scenario, VLC can be categorized into **indoor and outdoor VLC (vehicular VLC)**. Nowadays, vehicular VLC has become a vital part of the next-generation-based intelligent transportation systems (ITSs) [11], [12]. To this

Figure 1.3: Illustration of the outdoor V2V-VLC scenario.

end, vehicular networks can be classified into three main types of communications, i.e., V2V, I2V, and V2I communications. In this thesis, we investigate both indoor and outdoor VLC-based scenarios. However, the main focus is outdoor VLC (V2V and I2V) systems.

1.2.4 V2V Communication

Vehicular VLC is a vital application area of an outdoor VLC. To this end, as a part of the next-generation-based ITSs, V2V communication is a vital and emerging area of research in the field of vehicular technology. To facilitate road safety, V2V communication allows two communicating vehicles to exchange the following information: (i) Collision warning, (ii) Braking and speed, (iii) Lane departure and direction of travel, etc. A two-lane road-based V2V communication scenario is shown in Fig. 1.3. Vehicle's headlights /backlights can be used as the Tx's, and a PD can be deployed at the bumper of the following vehicle as the Rx (see Fig. 1.3). Note that, θ_i and ϕ_i denote the angles of incidence and irradiance, respectively, with respect to (w.r.t.) i^{th} Tx, $i = 1, 2$. Moreover, L_i and d_{h_i} denote the LOS propagation distance and lateral shift

Figure 1.4: Illustration of the outdoor I2V-VLC scenario.

of the vehicle, respectively, w.r.t. i^{th} Tx. Further, W_L denotes the width of the single lane, W_v denotes the width of the vehicle, and d denotes the inter-vehicle separation.

1.2.5 I2V communication and V2I communication

I2V and V2I are the other application scenarios of outdoor VLC. I2V and V2I communication enable the driver inside the car to access the Internet to get directions, road maps, congestion, and awareness of accidents in real-time. A two-lane road-based I2V-VLC scenario is demonstrated in Fig. 1.4. The traffic light (infrastructure) can be used as the Tx, and an optical camera/photodetector (PD) as the Rx can be mounted on the dashboard/top of the vehicle. Note, streetlights can also be used as the Txs in I2V-VLC [14]. For V2I-VLC scenario, vehicle headlights and PDs placed in the traffic lights can be used as the Txs and Rxs, respectively [15]. Note that, α and β denote the angles of irradiance and incidence, respectively. L_w denotes the width of the lane,

Ψ_C is the field-of-view (FOV) of the camera, and D_T denotes the horizontal distance between the Tx and the camera. Moreover, $H_{T,DB}$ denotes the height of the Tx from the camera positioned on the dashboard (DB) of the vehicle and $H_{T,DB,LOS}$ denotes the LOS propagation distance between the traffic light and the DB mounted camera. Further, $H_{T,RS}$ denotes the height of the Tx from the road surface and $H_{DB,RS}$ denotes the height between the DB camera and the road surface.

1.3 Literature Review (Diversity Techniques in FSO Systems)

In this section, we emphasize a comprehensive state-of-the-art considering the spatial diversity techniques in FSO systems. Moreover, we briefly discuss the proposed diversity techniques.

1.3.1 State-of-the-Art

The FSO system can use spatial diversity techniques to lessen the effects of turbulence-induced fading [16], [17]. The most commonly used techniques to achieve spatial diversity are repetition coding (RC), transmit laser selection (TLS), and orthogonal space-time block codes (OSTBCs). These techniques offer full diversity in the FSO system. For RC, the same information symbol is transmitted from all the transmit apertures/lasers [4]. In contrast to RC, TLS activates the laser ensuring the maximum irradiance at the Rx; this requires a feedback link to have channel state information at the transmitter (CSIT) side. OSTBC uses both space and time for transmission. Moreover, OSTBC transmission is very useful because it does not require any CSIT for achieving transmit diversity. However, it has been shown in [6] that OSTBC performs poorer than RC in the FSO system employing intensity modulation and direct detection (IM/DD) with on/off keying (OOK). In [5], the TLS scheme is studied and analytically examined, demonstrating that the TLS scheme outperforms the RC scheme

under IM/DD. TLS is the best transmission scheme in the FSO system. Inspired by [5], the TLS scheme is examined in [18–23] considering different channel models. An extended version of the TLS scheme for a multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO)-FSO system employing limited feedback bits is presented in [24]. In this scheme, transmit apertures are divided into different sizes of partitions, and a single partition is selected based on feedback bits received from the receiver for transmitting signals. Hereafter, in this thesis, we name the conventional TLS scheme as a single TLS (STLS) scheme.

The study of STLS in [18–23] assumed perfect CSIT, which does not hold true for practical (imperfect/erroneous feedback link) communication systems. A practical communication system always introduces a possibility of the feedback bits getting erroneously decoded at the transmitter. Due to this, the conventional STLS scheme makes an incorrect selection of the transmit aperture. Furthermore, in the erroneous feedback scenario, the diversity of the conventional STLS scheme becomes equivalent to the diversity of a single-link-based FSO system [25]. To overcome this problem, an error-tolerant aperture selection-based scheme is proposed in [25] employing activation of all the transmit lasers to achieve the full diversity. Since the conventional STLS scheme exploits a single communication link, the channel degradations affect the system performance significantly. Moreover, for the selection of the best transmit aperture, the feedback link also introduces some delay. Considering the time-varying nature of the channel, the feedback information on the selected source index may become outdated when it reaches the transmitter [26]. It deteriorates the performance of the conventional STLS scheme significantly.

In [27], a quantized feedback-based differential signaling scheme is proposed. In this work, the effect of the feedback error on the performance of the proposed scheme is studied. Recently, some research efforts based on STLS/transmit antenna selection (TAS) have been reported in the literature [26], [28], [29]. In [26], the asymptotic performance of a generalized TLS under the Lognormal channel model is investigated. Note that the generalized TLS corresponds to the n^{th} best transmit laser, $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$, among the available N transmit lasers. In [28], the secrecy outage performance of the mixed RF-FSO system under imperfect CSIT for different TAS schemes is investigated. The

Figure 1.5: Block diagram of the proposed TTLS scheme for a MISO-FSO system.

performance analysis of a hybrid multiple-input single-output (MISO) RF-FSO system with a STLS scheme is analyzed in [29].

1.3.2 Motivation and Proposed Diversity Improving Techniques

The main drawback of the traditional STLS scheme is that it only performs at its best in the case of perfect feedback, as stated in [5]. Hence, the feedback link's dependability has a big impact on how well it performs. **Therefore, an imperfect feedback scenario has a substantial impact on the STLS scheme's diversity order.** Thus to overcome the limitations of the conventional STLS scheme, we propose two new clustering-based TLS schemes, which are briefly discussed as below:

- **Two TLS (TTLS) scheme:** In the proposed TTLS scheme, the L_t available transmit lasers/apertures are divided into two clusters named as Cluster 1 and Cluster 2. In each cluster, the number of transmit apertures are given by N_{C_1} and N_{C_2} , respectively. Based on the CSI (selection of the optical path with a

greater value of channel irradiance), two best transmit lasers are selected from each cluster for the transmission. The system block diagram of the proposed TTLS scheme for a MISO-FSO system is also illustrated in Fig. 1.5. The further detailed discussion of the proposed TTLS scheme will be provided in Chapter 2.

In general, N_{C_1} and N_{C_2} are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} N_{C_1} &= N_{C_2} = L_t/2, L_t \text{ is even.} \\ N_{C_1} &= (L_t - 1)/2, N_{C_2}=(L_t + 1)/2, L_t \text{ is odd.} \end{aligned} \quad (1.1)$$

Moreover, to retain the full diversity under an imperfect feedback scenario, we also propose and analyze another clustering-based diversity improving TLS scheme, namely **modified error-tolerant weighting scheme (METWS)**.

- **METWS:** In the proposed METWS, the larger fraction of the total transmit power is allocated to the best transmit laser from each cluster while the rest power is equally divided into other transmit apertures. The further detailed discussion of the proposed METWS will be provided in Chapter 2.

1.4 Literature Review (Indoor and Outdoor VLC)

To motivate our significant contributions, in this section, we will emphasize a comprehensive literature review on indoor and **outdoor (V2V-VLC and I2V-VLC)** scenarios. **The primary emphasis will be on outdoor VLC.**

1.4.1 State-of-the-Art (Indoor VLC)

Wireless communication systems employing MIMO technology has fascinated numerous researchers over the last decade. Considering the reliability of the communication system, MIMO systems offer superior performance compared to the conventional single-input single-output (SISO) systems in terms of the availability of independent propagation paths. These independent propagation paths are characterized by the

term ‘diversity gain’. Further, MIMO systems utilize parallel spatial modes characterized by the term ‘spatial multiplexing gain’ or simply ‘multiplexing gain’. The diversity-multiplexing tradeoff (DMT) is illustrated in [30], [31]. The research has included VLC-based studies over the past few years that have taken a variety of factors into account, such as channel characterization [32], different modulation schemes [33], different coding schemes [34], development of MIMO-VLC systems [35], performance investigation of non-orthogonal multiple access [36], transceiver design [37], and channel capacity [38]. **However, none of the works have investigated DMT of an indoor VLC.**

1.4.2 State-of-the-Art (Modeling of Outdoor V2V-VLC)

We give a detailed state-of-the-art w.r.t. existing literature to motivate our significant contributions in the context of thorough modelling of a V2V-VLC system under practical considerations.

ITSs, street-level access networks, the Internet of things, and other applications can all greatly benefit from the application of VLC in outdoor scenarios as part of fifth-generation (5G) wireless networks. The idea of vehicle lighting in ITSs was first presented in [39] by fusing VLC with visible light placement. In [40], where simulated channel models matching real conditions for the use of VLC in ITSs were offered, a VLC-based simulation model for automotive applications was proposed. An environment-adaptive Rx to boost communication effectiveness for automotive applications was suggested in [41]. For vehicular VLC channels, a new non-stationary regular-shaped geometry-based stochastic model (RS-GBSM) was put forward in [42]. A thorough channel simulation was done in [43] to determine the impact of rain and fog on a V2V-VLC link. The authors of [44] examined several precoding and equalization strategies for a 2×2 MIMO-based V2V-VLC system. It should be noted that precoding is a method that takes the use of transmission variability by weighting the information stream. A 3-D massive MIMO-based channel model for V2V communications was suggested in [45]. The authors made a spherical wavefront assumption rather than the

plane wavefront assumption that is typical of the traditional MIMO channel model [45]. In [46], a V2V-VLC simulation-based channel modeling was recently presented. Also, novel path loss expressions were suggested, and their comparison study was looked at [45]. The channel impulse response of the under-consideration V2V-VLC system was obtained using a non-sequential ray-tracing simulation-based approach [46].

By lowering the camera's spatial bandwidth in the out-of-focus areas, a unique technique was presented in [47] to expand the transmission linkspan of a rolling shutter-based optical camera communications (OCC) system to 400 m. In [48], a V2V communications system utilising OCC was examined. According to [48], the camera frame rate and symbol duration have a complete impact on the system data rates. A multi-hop relay-based routing algorithm and a prediction-based channel gain model for V2V-VLC networks were proposed in [49]. For a multi-hop, V2V-VLC link, a low complexity least-squares-based post-distortion algorithm was suggested in [50]. The proposed approach employs a low dimensional approximation of the random Fourier characteristics to alleviate the V2V-VLC channel impairments. A geometry-based stochastic channel model for V2V communications was recently proposed in [51]. The model was parametrized based on measurements after the authors took into account an urban setting [51]. The authors of [52] examined the effectiveness of a cooperative (relaying-based) full-duplex V2V-VLC system. A report on an experimental investigation of the V2V-VLC system can be found in references [53], [54], [55], and [56]. Moreover, in a LOS VLC system, the communication channel may encounter momentary shadowing as a result of actual physical impediments from other lanes of traffic or nearby parked cars [57]. Shadowing can result in an increase in route loss, a variation in the received signal's power, and finally a link breakdown [1]. Moreover, the DMT has primarily been examined for RF systems rather than V2V-VLC systems. DMT was examined for generic fading channels in [58]. In [59], a partial CSIT-based DMT was examined. DMT for Rician MIMO channels was determined in [60]. A locating beacon system utilising a digital camera was studied in [61]. Any LED traffic light or signalling equipment on the road can be converted using this concept into a component of a location beacon system. According to [62], a study on traffic information systems using LED traffic lights was

conducted. The analytical LOS path loss model is put forward for ITSs in [63].

1.4.3 State-of-the-Art (Recent Research on Outdoor V2V-VLC)

Now, we emphasize some recent investigations in V2V-VLC to motivate our significant contributions. Considering the indoor VLC, there are numerous research works in the literature. We put light on some of them to envision the channel models adopted by these works [64–68]. It will give us insight into the context of the limitation of the indoor VLC channel models compared to the outdoor V2V-VLC environment. Note that, path loss and capacity are highly dependent on the channel characteristics. Therefore, an appropriate vision of the channel characteristics is of extreme importance. It is to be noted that the indoor VLC channel models are based on the Lambertian emission pattern [69], which fails to capture the asymmetrical illumination characteristics of vehicle’s low-beam and high-beam headlamps in the outdoor vehicular-VLC scenario. Thus the indoor VLC channel models do not apply to the outdoor V2V-VLC environment.

In [70], the impact of a realistic light radiation pattern on V2V-VLC has been examined by taking into account the simulation model based on empirical data for typical automotive headlight and taillight modules. The authors in [71] suggested a new path loss expression that takes the shape of a negative exponential function while using a similar simulation environment using Zemax software. Furthermore, the ray-tracing simulation outcomes showed that the linear model in [43] only functions at distances of under 20 metres. The proposed path loss expression has been demonstrated to be true for longer transmission lengths [71]. By using a non-parameterized, data-driven strategy, the authors in [72] tackled the issue of path loss prediction between two communicating vehicles. A low-complexity least-squares-based post-distortion technique for a multi-hop V2V-VLC link was also suggested in [73]. A modular IEEE 802.11 compliant radio framework-based graphical networking unit (GNU) solution for outdoor vehicular VLC has been presented in [74]. In [75], an unique Rx design, a visible light positioning technique, and a VLC-based vehicle localization method have all been

suggested. A performance investigation study was conducted by the authors in [76] employing various vehicle taillights as the Tx's in a vehicular light communication system. It has been demonstrated that the link span and transmission coverage FOV depend, respectively, on the transmit power levels and the taillight illumination parameters. An experimental demonstration of a bidirectional V2V-VLC has been reported in [77] to help with the installation of next-generation ITS active safety systems. It has been reported in [78] that a novel framework for the machine learning (ML)- based channel modelling of the vehicular VLC exists. The main goal was to incorporate several input factors related to vehicle mobility and environmental impacts in order to increase the model's accuracy for path loss.

Moreover, in this thesis, we also analyze the capacity of the V2V-VLC system considering the practical discrete inputs. Considering the existing literature, different bounds on the capacity of optical channels were derived [79], [80–83]. For instance, the authors in [80], [82], [83] have analyzed the bounds on the capacity in the VLC domain. However, all these works emphasized deriving the lower/upper bounds and not the exact closed-form expression of the capacity. Moreover, most of the existing literature is focused on the continuous-input continuous-output memoryless channel (CCMC) capacity by considering gaussian inputs [84–86], which is not realistic for a real and non-negative V2V-VLC signal. Therefore, the classic CCMC capacity does not provide an appropriate metric for the V2V-VLC system. To this end, a more practical capacity for a vehicular VLC with discrete inputs needs to be investigated, named discrete-input continuous-output memoryless channel (DCMC) capacity [87].

1.4.4 State-of-the-Art (Experimental Research on Outdoor V2V-VLC and I2V-VLC)

In this subsection, we emphasize **experimental research efforts in vehicular VLC to motivate our contributions**. To provide insights into the background, we begin with some theoretical studies on vehicular VLC. However, we mainly emphasize the experimental works on V2V-VLC and I2V-VLC. By considering an I2V-VLC system

with street lights as the VLC TxS, the authors in [88] adopted a non-sequential ray tracing-based simulation approach (using a Zemax software) for channel modeling. Moreover, the performance was analyzed in terms of the path loss and BER. Moreover, some theoretical studies on I2V-VLC systems have been reported in [89–93] as a part of the next generation ITSs.

Considering the experimental works, in [94], experimental results for a 185 m V2V-VLC link with a BER of $10^{-7} - 10^{-6}$ were reported. In [95], using the optical orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OOFDMA)-based uplink for V2V-VLC, it was shown that the LED nonlinear distortion and the shot noise can significantly affect the error vector magnitude due to the out-of-band noise/interference induced inter-user interference. In [96], an experimental investigation illustrating the impact of the interference from lights on the performance of a 25 Mb/s OOK V2V-VLC link was reported. It was shown that the minimum required deviation angle for error-free transmission was 1.5° for a scenario where the transmit optical power and the interference light are almost equal [96]. As a part of the next-generation ITSs (minimizing road accidents), the authors in [97] designed a prototype V2V-VLC system with low complexity and high reliability. Experimental evaluation of the prototype showed that the proposed system can give an early warning to drivers at speeds up to 80 km/h [97]. An experimental investigation of three low-complex optical OFDM (O-OFDM) schemes for vehicular VLC was reported in [98]. Experimental results showed that contrary to simulation results reported in the literature, asymmetrically clipped optical OFDM (ACO-OFDM) outperforms unipolar OFDM (U-OFDM) due to the lower peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) [98]. To alleviate the impact of strong background radiation on OFDM-based outdoor VLC systems, in [99], a novel Rx architecture employing attenuation diversity was proposed. The experimental results showed that with direct current biased optical OFDM (DCO-OFDM) and under strong background lights, the BER was reduced to a reasonable level [99]. In [100], the impact of using different lens combinations in vehicular VLC was experimentally investigated. Similar to the non-sequential ray-tracing approach [46], in [100], based on the estimated optical channel coefficient for the vehicular scenario, the system SNR performance was characterized for different

lens combinations [100].

Further, in [101], using carrierless amplitude-phase (CAP) modulation, an experimental demonstration of 312.5 Mbit/s CAP vehicular VLC over a 10 m link was reported. In [102], the authors experimentally showed a communication range of at least 50 m. It was also shown that the initial 2-8 m transmission distance was not covered by the Rx's FOV for vehicles on adjacent lanes [102]. In [103], LED-based V2V-VLC with a modified fixed decision threshold (MFDT) scheme was experimentally investigated, showing that the link was reliable under rain. In [104], an initial experimental investigation of I2V-VLC employing a traffic light-based Tx was reported, where it was shown that the modulation depth can be reduced by 50% in order to track the light source when sending '0'symbol. In [105], an I2V-VLC using a traffic light and a photodiode as the Tx and the Rx, respectively, was investigated, showing a BER of 10^{-3} over a transmission range of up to 188 m. In [106], the performance of multi-hop VLC-based vehicular systems in an outdoor environment was investigated, in terms of SNR during the day and night time. To enhance the SNR of V2V-VLC systems considering the mobility, in [107], the use of dual PDs with selection combining was investigated. In [108], the authors experimentally investigated the effects of fog on the V2V-VLC link when using a camera-based Rx. The findings showed that, for the three modulation index situations, the link is error-free up to 20 m of visibility and degrades below the 10 m meteorological visibility [108].

1.4.5 Motivation

After discussing a comprehensive literature review and state-of-the-art in Subsections 1.4.1-1.4.4, we motivate the significant contributions of this thesis as follows:

- The existing literature on DMT mainly emphasizes RF systems (with complex channel coefficients), for instance, [30, 58–60]. However, applying the concept of DMT to the OWC systems requires careful attention because of the real and positive channel coefficients. Firstly, the channel characteristics play a vital role while applying the concept of DMT to indoor and outdoor OWC systems. Secondly,

the presence of multiple system parameters in the OWC systems require careful attention in deciding which parameters will affect the optimal DMT. Moreover, considering the existing literature, no study on DMT in VLC-based communication systems is done. Further, none of the reported works have analyzed the limited-feedback-based DMT for the FSO system.

- The comprehensive modeling of a V2V-VLC system was not emphasized in any of the works mentioned in Subsections 1.4.2 and 1.4.3. To be more precise, these works did not model or envision the following practical characteristics of a dynamic V2V-VLC environment: (i) Random path loss resulting from the vehicle's random mobility, (ii) Random lateral shift, (iii) Random longitudinal/inter-vehicle separation, (iv) Modeling of the joint impact of path loss and AT, etc.
- Further, it is observed that most of the existing literature on V2V-VLC has studied simulation-based path loss [43], [70–72], [78]. Moreover, considering a dynamic V2V-VLC model, the impact of the critical outdoor propagation characteristics needs to be investigated on both LOS and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) V2V-VLC propagation models. Also, none of the reported works have analyzed the DCMC capacity to envision the maximum attainable capacity by the V2V-VLC channel. **Hence, a comprehensive approach/framework to quantify the path loss and DCMC capacity under the adverse challenges of an outdoor V2V-VLC environment needs to be developed.**
- In the existing literature, such as [43], [46], [49], an ideal V2V-VLC scenario has been studied. To be specific, the impact of shadowing due to the presence of nearby parked/mobile vehicles, has not been considered. These nearby parked/mobile vehicles act as a physical obstruction between the Tx and the Rx. In real-time outdoor V2V-VLC scenarios, there may be a temporary interruption in the LOS communication. It happens between two communicating vehicles due to the lateral shift (lateral movement) of one of the vehicles, where the LOS path is blocked by other nearby vehicles. Consequently, the link performance is affected significantly. **Therefore, investigation of the channel**

model incorporating shadowing, is crucial to represent practical V2V communication scenarios.

- Furthermore, considering all the experimental works highlighted in Subsection 1.4.4, none of the works have designed the indoor testbed for an outdoor I2V-VLC system. **Note, before the real-time implementation of any communication system in the outdoor environment, it is crucial to validate the system's performance in a controlled indoor environment.**

1.5 Key Contributions

Taking into account the motivation derived from the previous subsection, in this section, we highlight the key contributions of this thesis as follows:

- To overcome the practical limitations of the conventional STLS scheme [5] and improve the overall performance of the terrestrial outdoor FSO system, we propose two novel clustering-based TLS schemes (namely TTLS and METWS). We consider both perfect and imperfect CSI-based communication scenarios. Moreover, different performance metrics, such as BER, diversity gain, etc., are also analyzed. The entire study is acknowledged with interesting remarks and striking observations.
- We investigate the DMT for the OWC systems. To this end, we mainly focus on indoor VLC and outdoor FSO systems. For the DMT investigation of the indoor VLC system, we consider the random radial movement of the end-user in the proposed system model. The optimal DMT for both the SISO and MIMO VLC systems are analyzed for the first time. Novel analytical expressions for the probability distribution function (PDF), outage probability, and outage diversity order for the SISO-VLC and MIMO-VLC systems are derived. Moreover, we extend our study to the outdoor FSO system. For the first time, a limited feedback-based DMT is investigated for the FSO system under different trans-

mission scenarios. To this end, we consider a MIMO-FSO setup and investigate the DMT for single-rate and adaptive-rate transmission scenarios.

- A comprehensive outdoor V2V-VLC model is proposed and analyzed under the practical characteristics of an outdoor V2V-VLC system. We consider random mobility of the vehicle. Therefore, differing from the existing literature, a more practical V2V-VLC model is proposed. Also, a unique channel model that accounts for the combined effect of outdoor V2V-VLC random path loss and atmospheric turbulence (AT) is considered. Additionally, we evaluate the proposed V2V-VLC model's performance using several metrics, including path loss, outage probability, average BER (ABER), diversity, and DCMC capacity, taking the influence of various weather conditions into account. Furthermore, the impact of several practical outdoor propagation characteristics on the proposed V2V-VLC model is investigated comprehensively.
- We propose a **shadowing-based** outdoor V2V-VLC model. The performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model is analyzed with the DMT metric. Moreover, to minimize the path loss at the Rx, a novel hemispherical optical concentrator-based Rx structure (offering an omnidirectional gain) is also proposed. It is observed that the proposed Rx structure enhances the DMT performance gain significantly. Further, the performance of the proposed Rx structure is also compared with the conventional single photon avalanche diode (SPAD)-based Rx. Furthermore, to validate our derived DMT results, we have developed a MATLAB software-based platform which is unique from the works reported in the literature.
- An indoor experimental testbed for an outdoor I2V-VLC system is designed. For the first time, we experimentally demonstrate the communication between the traffic light (i.e., the Tx) and the camera (i.e., the Rx) under different realistic I2V-VLC scenarios in a controlled indoor environment. Moreover, different performance metrics are experimentally examined, such as BER, peak SNR (PSNR), and capacity. Further, LOS blockage-based communication scenarios are also

experimentally analyzed. Furthermore, **all the experimental findings are demonstrated for different exposure times of the camera for the first time, which is a very critical parameter when using a camera-based Rx.**

1.6 Organization of Thesis

The research work presented in this thesis focuses on the design and performance investigation of the OWC systems in indoor and outdoor scenarios. In this thesis, we mainly focus on the terrestrial outdoor FSO, indoor VLC, and outdoor VLC systems. The thesis is organized into seven chapters. The summary of the research work presented in each chapter is briefly outlined as follows:

Chapter 1: This chapter provides an overview of the OWC system with a focus on the diversity techniques for the terrestrial outdoor FSO system, VLC systems (indoor and outdoor), a comprehensive literature review, motivation, and thesis contributions.

Chapter 2: This chapter proposes two novel clustering-based TLS schemes (namely TTLS and METWS) to improve the overall performance of the terrestrial outdoor FSO system. Considering the practicality, both perfect and imperfect CSI-based communication scenarios are considered. The performance of both the proposed schemes is analyzed using BER, diversity gain, etc. Firstly, the two proposed schemes are studied for a MISO set-up, and then the performance of the two proposed schemes is also demonstrated for the MIMO set-up. Moreover, to gain more insights, the performance of the two proposed schemes is also compared with the conventional STLS and RC schemes. Further, the performance of the two proposed TLS schemes is analyzed covering the entire AT regime for the first time.

Chapter 3: In this chapter, we investigate the DMT for the OWC systems. To this end, we mainly focus on indoor VLC and outdoor FSO systems. For the DMT investigation of indoor VLC system, we consider the random radial movement of the end-user in the proposed system model. The optimal DMT for both the SISO and MIMO VLC systems are analyzed. Novel analytical expressions for the probability

distribution function (PDF), outage probability, and outage diversity order for the SISO-VLC and MIMO-VLC systems are derived. Moreover, we extend our study to the outdoor FSO system. For the first time, a limited feedback-based DMT is investigated for the FSO system under different transmission scenarios. To this end, we consider a MIMO-FSO setup and investigate the DMT for single-rate and adaptive-rate transmission scenarios.

Chapter 4: This chapter emphasizes the **comprehensive modeling** of a V2V-VLC system and **performance investigation** under practical considerations. Differing from the existing literature, we model the lateral movement and the longitudinal/inter-vehicle separation of the vehicle as **random** with a specific PDF. To be more specific, random mobility of the vehicle is considered. The combined effect of path loss and AT is taken into consideration using a novel channel model. Note that path loss has a significant impact on the V2V-VLC system. Additionally, we model the LOS blocking and road surface reflections with a corresponding path loss and examine their effects on the proposed model. Further, different performance metrics such as path loss, outage probability, ABER, diversity, and DCMC capacity are investigated. The impact of the different weather conditions is also examined on the proposed V2V-VLC model. Furthermore, the impact of several practical outdoor propagation characteristics on the proposed V2V-VLC model is investigated comprehensively.

Chapter 5: In this chapter, a V2V-VLC model under shadowing is proposed. Using the DMT metric, the proposed V2V-VLC model's performance is examined. Moreover, a novel hemispherical optical concentrator-based Rx structure (offering an omnidirectional gain) is also proposed, which enhances the DMT performance gain significantly. A composite channel model with the combined impact of shadowing and AT is considered to analyze the optimal DMT for the proposed V2V-VLC model. Novel analytical expressions for the path loss, PDF of the channel matrix, joint PDF of the ordered singular values of the channel matrix, outage probability (in terms of the multiplexing gain and other VLC parameters), and outage diversity order are developed.

Chapter 6: This chapter emphasizes an indoor experimental testbed design for an

outdoor I2V-VLC system. An experimental demonstration of the communication between the traffic light (i.e., the Tx) and the camera (i.e., the Rx) under different realistic I2V-VLC scenarios is emphasized. Moreover, we emphasize the intensity measurements of the Tx and obtain the beam profile using MATLAB software. Based on the beam profile, channel modeling is implemented. Further, LOS blockage-based I2V-VLC scenarios are also investigated, and some striking insights are envisioned. Furthermore, all the experimental findings are demonstrated for different exposure times of the camera for the first time.

Chapter 7: This chapter concludes the thesis by summarizing the contributions. Areas for further research and description of the possible extensions to the work presented in this thesis are also provided.

Chapter 2

Clustering-Based TLS Schemes for a Terrestrial Outdoor FSO System

In this chapter, we present and discuss two novel clustering-based TLS schemes (namely TTLS and METWS) to enhance the diversity and overall performance of the FSO systems. Both perfect and imperfect feedback scenarios are considered to study the two proposed schemes. Moreover, the error performance as well as the diversity performance is analyzed for both the proposed schemes. Further, the performance of the two proposed schemes is also compared with the conventional STLS and RC schemes. It is observed that the proposed METWS is able to provide full diversity despite feedback errors.

2.1 Introduction

FSO transmission employing IM/DD offers high-speed communication links for many applications. However, AT induces fluctuations in the transmitted optical beam, which deteriorates the communication performance significantly [1], [2]. To overcome this problem, spatial diversity techniques can be used over FSO links [16], [17]. The most commonly used techniques to achieve spatial diversity are RC, STLS, and OSTBCs. These techniques provide full diversity in the FSO systems. For RC, the same information symbol is transmitted from all the transmit apertures/lasers [4]. In contrast to

Publication based on this chapter is [J1] and [C1].

RC, STLS activates the laser with the maximum irradiance at the Rx, which requires a feedback link to have CSIT. OSTBC uses both space and time for transmission. On the other side, TLS offers the best possible error performance in the FSO system.

Considering the existing works such as [5], the STLS scheme is proposed and analyzed analytically. The STLS scheme outperforms the RC technique under IM/DD, as demonstrated in [5]. Inspired by [5], the STLS scheme is examined in [18–23] using various channel models. A proposed STLS extension for a MIMO-FSO system with few feedback bits is presented and analyzed in [24]. In this chapter, a clustering-based TTLS method/approach is proposed under a practical (erroneous) feedback scenario, in contrast to [5], [18–24], which consider perfect feedback. Under a practical feedback scenario, it is found that the proposed TTLS scheme significantly outperforms the conventional STLS scheme. Moreover, differing from [25], in this chapter, a new clustering-based METWS, in which the larger fraction of the total transmit power is allocated to the best transmit aperture from each cluster, while the rest power is equally divided into other transmit apertures is proposed and analyzed.

To this end, **the chapter has the following contributions:**

- To overcome the practical limitations of the conventional STLS scheme, two novel clustering-based TLS schemes (namely TTLS and METWS) are proposed and analyzed. Moreover, we analyze the error performance of the two proposed schemes under both perfect and imperfect feedback links.
- Additionally, in this work, an exact closed-form BER expression for the imperfect/erroneous feedback scenario is derived for the proposed TTLS scheme, in contrast to [5], [18–24], wherein only a perfect/ideal feedback scenario is considered. Asymptotic BER expressions are also developed to investigate the diversity performance.
- Further, if we compare our proposed work with the existing literature, [5], [18–25], to the best of our knowledge, the performance of TLS schemes is not examined covering the entire turbulence regime. In this work, the two proposed schemes are studied for different channel models (such as negative exponential, gamma-

gamma (G-G), and lognormal (LN)) and thus covering the entire turbulence regime of FSO. Therefore, the completeness of the study is emphasized.

- Finally, the performance of the two proposed schemes is also compared with the conventional STLS and RC schemes, and new insights are envisioned.

2.2 Preliminaries

In this section, we discuss the system model and channel model under consideration.

2.2.1 System Model

A general MISO-FSO system with L_t transmit apertures and a single receive aperture, employing IM/DD is considered. An OOK symbol $s \in \{P, 0\}$ is transmitted in a transmission time interval. Let us define the weight vector and the channel irradiance vector for L_t transmit apertures as: $\mathbf{w} \triangleq [w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{L_t}]^T$ and $\mathbf{I} \triangleq [I_1, I_2, \dots, I_{L_t}]$. Note that $[\cdot]^T$ stands for transpose. Before transmission, the symbol s is multiplied by a transmit power weight w_i such that $\sum_{i=1}^{L_t} w_i \leq \frac{N_A}{2}$ (transmit power constraint of TTLS), and $w_i \in \{0, \frac{1}{2}\}$ depending upon the transmit aperture is active or inactive. Note that N_A is the number of active transmit apertures. The transmit power constraint of METWS will be discussed later. Therefore, the received electrical signal corresponding to L_t transmit apertures can be written as:

$$y = \frac{\rho}{L_t} \mathbf{I} \mathbf{w} s + e = \frac{\rho}{L_t} \sum_{i=1}^{L_t} I_i w_i s + e, \quad (2.1)$$

where ρ denotes the photodetector responsivity and e is zero-mean additive white gaussian noise (AWGN) of σ^2 variance; I_i is the real-valued irradiance of the link between i^{th} transmit aperture and the receive aperture. We assume $I_i s$ to be independent and identically distributed (i.i.d).

2.2.2 Channel Model

We consider negative exponential fading caused by AT, for which the distribution of channel irradiance I_i is [1]:

$$f_{I_i}(I) = \frac{1}{I_o} \exp\left(-\frac{I}{I_o}\right), I_o > 0, \quad (2.2)$$

where I_o is the mean received irradiance and we assume it to be unity. Hence, the distribution of I_i will be:

$$f_{I_i}(I) = \exp(-I). \quad (2.3)$$

Remark 2.1: The negative exponential turbulence model corresponds to a very strong turbulence regime [1]. Therefore, the two proposed schemes are examined for a worst-case transmission scenario. It is analyzed that the two proposed schemes perform significantly better even in a worst-case scenario. However, to observe the performance under other channel models, simulation-based results for the G-G and LN channel models under the combined impact of AT and PE are also discussed. In this way, the proposed schemes are studied for different channel models, and therefore, the completeness of the study is emphasized.

Further, it is assumed that $\mathbb{E}[|s|^2] = E_s$, and the value of mean channel irradiance, i.e., $\mathbb{E}[I_i] = 1$, where $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ denotes the expectation operator. From (2.1), it can be seen that the total received average SNR is given by $\frac{\mathbb{E}\left[\left|\frac{\rho}{L_t} \sum_{i=1}^{L_t} I_i w_i s\right|^2\right]}{\mathbb{E}[|e|^2]} = \frac{\frac{\rho^2}{L_t^2} \mathbb{E}\left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^{L_t} I_i w_i\right)^2\right] \mathbb{E}[|s|^2]}{\sigma^2} = \frac{\frac{\rho^2}{L_t^2} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{L_t} w_i \mathbb{E}[I_i]\right)^2 E_s}{\sigma^2} = \frac{\rho^2 E_s}{\sigma^2}$. However, in the following analysis, we use a quantity $\bar{\gamma}$ which we name the average SNR per diversity branch and it is defined as $\bar{\gamma} \triangleq (\rho^2/L_t^2) \mathbb{E}[|s|^2] \mathbb{E}[I_i^2] / \mathbb{E}[|e|^2] = \rho^2 E_s / (L_t^2 \sigma^2)$.

2.2.3 Detection

A maximum-likelihood Rx for the received signal y given in (2.1) can be written as:

$$\hat{s} = \min_{s \in \{P, 0\}} \left| y - \frac{\rho}{L_t} \sum_{i=1}^{L_t} I_i w_i s \right|^2, \quad (2.4)$$

where \hat{s} denotes the detected symbol at the Rx.

Now, in the subsequent section, we will discuss the different transmission schemes with their respective generalized weight vector structure. Moreover, we will see how the received electrical signal given in (2.1) changes according to the different transmission schemes.

2.3 Different Transmission Schemes with Generalized Weight Vector Structure

The discussion related to the generalized weight vector structure for the different transmission schemes considered in this work is given as follows:

1. **RC scheme:** It is one of the simplest transmission schemes in which the same information symbol is transmitted from all the transmit apertures. Moreover, the implementation of this scheme does not require any feedback link. Unlike wireless RF communication systems, transmit diversity in FSO communication can be implemented through repetition coding [3], [4]. For RC, the generalized weight vector structure \mathbf{w}_{RC} is given as: $\mathbf{w}_{RC} = [1, 1, 1, \dots, 1]^T$. Therefore, the received electrical signal at the receive aperture corresponding to RC transmission scheme is given by:

$$y_{RC} = \frac{\rho}{N_A} \mathbf{I} \mathbf{w}_{RC} s + e. \quad (2.5)$$

For RC scheme, $N_A = L_t$.

2. **Conventional STLS scheme:** In this scheme, we select a transmit aperture or transmit laser with maximum channel irradiance out of L_t available transmit lasers. This scheme assumes CSI at the Tx and Rx. Further, it makes a selection of the optical path with the highest value of channel irradiance showing the ability to extract full diversity. Moreover, it provides better performance when compared to other alternatives in which the CSI at the Tx is not considered, such as RC. The channel irradiance corresponding to the STLS scheme, I_m , is given by:

$$I_m = \max(I_1, I_2, \dots, I_{L_t}). \quad (2.6)$$

It should be noted that STLS scheme is able to provide full diversity only in the presence of perfect feedback. On the other side, it is very sensitive to feedback errors, and in the

Figure 2.1: Block diagram of the proposed TTLS scheme for a MISO-FSO system.

erroneous feedback scenario, it loses its diversity drastically. For STLS, the generalised weight vector structure \mathbf{w}_{STLS} is given as: $\mathbf{w}_{STLS} \in \{ \mathbf{w}_1, \mathbf{w}_2, \mathbf{w}_3, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{L_t} \}$, where $\mathbf{w}_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, L_t$ is the i^{th} column of the $L_t \times L_t$ identity matrix (\mathbf{I}_{L_t}). Moreover, the received electrical signal at the receive aperture corresponding to this transmission scheme can be expressed as:

$$y_{STLS} = \frac{\rho}{N_A} \mathbf{I} \mathbf{w}_{STLS} s + e, \quad (2.7)$$

where, $N_A = 1$ for the STLS scheme.

Remark 2.2: The weight vector \mathbf{w}_{STLS} contains the weight vector corresponding to I_m , defined in (2.6). Moreover, the Rx in case of STLS as a transmission scheme sends $\lceil \log_2 L_t \rceil$ bits feedback to the Tx. These feedback bits indicate the index to the best transmit aperture $I_m, m = 1, 2, \dots, L_t$.

3. Proposed TTLS scheme: In this chapter, we propose a two transmit apertures/lasers selection based scheme for a MISO-FSO system. The block diagram of the proposed TTLS scheme is shown in Fig. 2.1. It can be seen from the figure that L_t lasers are divided into two clusters named as Cluster1 and Cluster2 with number of transmit apertures given by N_{C_1} and N_{C_2} , respectively. Two best transmit lasers are

selected (one from each cluster) with channel irradiance $I_p = \max(I_1, I_2, \dots, I_{N_{C_1}})$, $p = 1, 2, \dots, N_{C_1}$ and $I_q = \max(I_{N_{C_1}+1}, I_{N_{C_1}+2}, \dots, I_{L_t})$, $q = N_{C_1} + 1, N_{C_1} + 2, \dots, L_t$. The selection criteria for both the transmit lasers is as follows: The Rx feedbacks the CSI to the Tx to make the selection of the optical path with a greater value of channel irradiance.

In general, N_{C_1} and N_{C_2} are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} N_{C_1} &= N_{C_2} = L_t/2, L_t \text{ is even.} \\ N_{C_1} &= (L_t - 1)/2, N_{C_2} = (L_t + 1)/2, L_t \text{ is odd.} \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

For the TTLS scheme, let us denote Cluster1 and Cluster2 by C_1 and C_2 , respectively. Therefore, the generalized weight vector structure corresponding to C_1 and C_2 is given as: $\mathbf{w}_{C_1} \in \{\mathbf{w}_1, \mathbf{w}_2, \mathbf{w}_3, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{N_{C_1}}\}$, where \mathbf{w}_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, N_{C_1}$ is the i^{th} column of the $N_{C_1} \times N_{C_1}$ identity matrix ($\mathbf{I}_{N_{C_1}}$) for C_1 , and correspondingly, $\mathbf{w}_{C_2} \in \{\mathbf{w}_{N_{C_1}+1}, \mathbf{w}_{N_{C_1}+2}, \mathbf{w}_{N_{C_1}+3}, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{L_t}\}$, where \mathbf{w}_j , $j = N_{C_1} + 1, N_{C_1} + 2, \dots, L_t$ is the j^{th} column of the $N_{C_2} \times N_{C_2}$ identity matrix ($\mathbf{I}_{N_{C_2}}$) for C_2 . The received electrical signal at the receive aperture corresponding to this transmission scheme will be:

$$\begin{aligned} y_{TTLS} &= \frac{\rho}{N_A} \left([I_1, I_2, \dots, I_{N_{C_1}}] \mathbf{w}_{C_1} s \right. \\ &\quad \left. + [I_{N_{C_1}+1}, I_{N_{C_1}+2}, \dots, I_{L_t}] \mathbf{w}_{C_2} s \right) + e, \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

where $N_A = 2$, for the TTLS scheme. Accordingly, for the TTLS scheme, $\bar{\gamma} = \rho^2 E_s / (N_A^2 \sigma^2)$. Moreover, N_{C_1} and N_{C_2} are calculated as given by (2.8).

Remark 2.3: If the index of the selected transmit laser is fed back to the Tx, the number of feedback bits required is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} N &= \lceil \log_2 \left(\frac{L_t}{2} \cdot \frac{L_t}{2} \right) \rceil = \lceil 2 \log_2 L_t - 2 \rceil, L_t \text{ is even,} \\ N &= \lceil \log_2 (L_t - 1) / 2 \rceil + \lceil \log_2 (L_t + 1) / 2 \rceil \\ &= \lceil \log_2 (L_t - 1) - 1 \rceil + \lceil \log_2 (L_t + 1) - 1 \rceil, L_t \text{ is odd.} \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

Now, we summarize the above discussion of the generalized weight vector structure for the different transmission schemes in the tabular form, which is illustrated in Table 2.1. Note that the channel irradiances are defined as I_1, I_2 for C_1 , and I_3, I_4 for C_2 .

Table 2.1: Illustration of weight vector structure $w = [w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4]^T$ for 4×1 MISO-FSO system

Channel State	$I_1 > I_2 > I_3 > I_4$	$I_2 > I_1 > I_4 > I_3$	$I_1 > I_2 > I_4 > I_3$
RC	$[1, 1, 1, 1]^T$	$[1, 1, 1, 1]^T$	$[1, 1, 1, 1]^T$
STLS	$[1, 0, 0, 0]^T$	$[0, 1, 0, 0]^T$	$[1, 0, 0, 0]^T$
TTLS	$[1, 0, 1, 0]^T$	$[0, 1, 0, 1]^T$	$[1, 0, 0, 1]^T$

Remark 2.4: We have considered an arbitrary number of transmit apertures in the proposed system model. However, we adopt the strategy of efficiently dividing the arbitrary transmit apertures into not more than two clusters. It is mainly because of two reasons. Firstly, it will increase the number of required feedback bits for another aperture selection. For example, a scenario of four clusters will require additional feedback bits for the selection of the best transmit aperture from that cluster. Secondly, the clustering of the transmit apertures into more than two clusters will deteriorate the performance of the system in an imperfect CSIT scenario (incorrect selection of the transmit aperture).

2.4 Performance Investigation of TTLS Scheme

In this section, we emphasize performance analysis of the proposed TTLS scheme. The primary objective of this analysis is to provide useful insights into the proposed TTLS scheme.

Remark 2.5: Due to the mathematical complexity, it is very cumbersome to provide the analysis for a generalized case. However, to show the performance of the two proposed schemes for an arbitrary number of transmit and receive apertures, simulation-based results for an 8×1 MISO and 8×2 MIMO set-up are also provided in Section 2.6. Moreover, if the practical perspective is taken into account, in commercial FSO applications, at the most, three to four transmit apertures can be deployed [109]. Further, the deployment of more than four transmit apertures adds to the cost and becomes a sophisticated design.

Let us define a random variable I_m such that

$$I_m \triangleq \max(I_1, I_2, \dots, I_{L_t}), \quad (2.11)$$

Applying the concept of order statistics [110], for i.i.d. random variables (RVs) of I_i , the PDF of I_m can be obtained as:

$$f_{I_m}(g) = L_t [F_{I_i}(g)]^{L_t-1} f_{I_i}(g), \quad (2.12)$$

where $F_{I_i}(g)$ and $f_{I_i}(g)$ are the negative exponential cumulative distribution function (CDF) and PDF, respectively. For a 4×1 MISO-FSO system, $N_{C_1} = N_{C_2} = L_t/2 = 2$, i.e., two transmit lasers in each cluster.

2.4.1 Performance Investigation of TTLS Scheme with Perfect Feedback

For a 4×1 MISO-FSO system employing perfect feedback information, the input-output (I/O) relation in (2.9) will be:

$$\begin{aligned} y_{TTLS} &= \frac{\rho}{2} ([I_1, I_2] \mathbf{w}_{C_1} s + [I_3, I_4] \mathbf{w}_{C_2} s) + e, \\ &= \frac{\rho}{2} (u_1 s + u_2 s) + e, \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

where $u_1 = \max(I_1, I_2)$ and $u_2 = \max(I_3, I_4)$ defines the maximum channel irradiance associated with the best transmit laser of C_1 and C_2 , respectively. By using order statistics [110], PDF of u_1 is given by:

$$f_{u_1}(u_1) = N_{C_1} [F_{I_i}(u_1)]^{N_{C_1}-1} f_{I_i}(u_1), \quad (2.14)$$

where $F_{I_i}(u_1)$ and $f_{I_i}(u_1)$ are the negative exponential CDF and PDF, respectively. Similarly, the PDF of u_2 can be expressed as:

$$f_{u_2}(u_2) = N_{C_2} [F_{I_i}(u_2)]^{N_{C_2}-1} f_{I_i}(u_2), \quad (2.15)$$

Substituting $N_{C_1} = N_{C_2} = 2$ in (2.14) and (2.15), we get:

$$f_{u_1}(u_1) = 2[\exp(-u_1) - \exp(-2u_1)]. \quad (2.16)$$

Table 2.2: Comparison of proposed TTLS and conventional STLS schemes in terms of number of feedback bits required

Number of transmit apertures (L_t)	TTLS	STLS
$L_t=3$	1	$\lceil 1.585 \rceil = 2$
$L_t=4$	2	2
$L_t=5$	$\lceil 2.585 \rceil = 3$	$\lceil 2.321 \rceil = 3$
$L_t=6$	$\lceil 3.129 \rceil = 4$	$\lceil 2.585 \rceil = 3$
$L_t=7$	$\lceil 3.585 \rceil = 4$	$\lceil 2.807 \rceil = 3$
$L_t=8$	4	3

$$f_{u_2}(u_2) = 2[\exp(-u_2) - \exp(-2u_2)]. \quad (2.17)$$

The average probability of error associated with perfect feedback is given by:

$$P_e(\bar{\gamma}) = \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty Q(\sqrt{(u_1 + u_2)^2 \bar{\gamma}}) f_{u_1}(u_1) f_{u_2}(u_2) du_1 du_2, \quad (2.18)$$

where $Q(\cdot)$ is the Gaussian q-function. After substituting (2.16) and (2.17) in (2.18), a closed-form solution of (2.18) is obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P_e(\bar{\gamma}) = & \underbrace{\mathcal{I}\left(\sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}, 1, 0\right)}_{\mathfrak{S}_1} - 2\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{\frac{1}{2\bar{\gamma}}} \underbrace{\mathcal{I}\left(1, 0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\bar{\gamma}}}\right)}_{\mathfrak{S}_2} + 2\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{\frac{3}{2\bar{\gamma}}} \underbrace{\mathcal{I}\left(1, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\bar{\gamma}}}\right)}_{\mathfrak{S}_3} \\ & - \underbrace{\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} \mathcal{I}\left(1, 0, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}\right)}_{\mathfrak{S}_4} - \underbrace{\mathcal{I}\left(\sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}, 2, 0\right)}_{\mathfrak{S}_5} + \underbrace{\mathcal{I}\left(1, -\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}\right)}_{\mathfrak{S}_6}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

Proof: Refer to Appendix A.

To evaluate \mathfrak{S}_1 , \mathfrak{S}_3 , \mathfrak{S}_5 and \mathfrak{S}_6 , we use (14a) given in [111], where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}_1 &= \left[1 - e^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{8\bar{\gamma}}}} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}}\right) \right], \\ \mathfrak{S}_3 &= \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}} \left[e^{-\frac{1}{\bar{\gamma}}} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\bar{\gamma}}}\right) - e^{\frac{1}{2\bar{\gamma}}} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\bar{\gamma}}}\right) \right], \\ \mathfrak{S}_5 &= \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - e^{\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}\right) \right], \\ \mathfrak{S}_6 &= \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}} \left[e^{\frac{1}{2\bar{\gamma}}} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\bar{\gamma}}}\right) - e^{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}\right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Note that $\text{erfc}(\cdot)$ is the complementary error function. Further, to evaluate \mathfrak{S}_2 and \mathfrak{S}_4 , we use the following closed form:

$$\int_c^\infty \text{erfc}(az)dz = \mathcal{I}(a, 0, c) = \frac{e^{-a^2c^2}}{a\sqrt{\pi}} - c \text{erfc}(ac). \quad (2.20)$$

Therefore, $\mathfrak{S}_2 = \frac{e^{-\frac{1}{2\bar{\gamma}}}}{\sqrt{\pi}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\bar{\gamma}}} \text{erfc}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\bar{\gamma}}}\right)$ and $\mathfrak{S}_4 = \frac{e^{-\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}}{\sqrt{\pi}} - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} \text{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}\right)$.

2.4.2 Performance Investigation of TTLS Scheme with Errorneous Feedback

When the feedback bits are decoded incorrectly, TX selects the incorrect aperture with $\min(I_1, I_2)$ from C_1 and $\min(I_3, I_4)$ from C_2 . Let us define a random variable r_1 , where $r_1 \triangleq \min(I_1, I_2)$. From order statistics [110], and for a 4×1 MISO-FSO system, r_1 is distributed as follows:

$$f_{r_1}(r_1) = 2[\exp(-2r_1)]. \quad (2.21)$$

Similarly, for C_2 , we define another random variable $r_2 \triangleq \min(I_3, I_4)$ such that r_2 is distributed as:

$$f_{r_2}(r_2) = 2[\exp(-2r_2)]. \quad (2.22)$$

The probability that feedback bits will be correctly detected at the Tx is denoted by P_c . Therefore, the average BER considering imperfect feedback can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} P_e(\bar{\gamma}) = & \underbrace{P_c^2 \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty Q\left(\sqrt{(u_1 + u_2)^2 \bar{\gamma}}\right) f_{u_1}(u_1) f_{u_2}(u_2) du_1 du_2}_{P_{e_1}(\bar{\gamma}) \text{ (corresponding to bits 00)}} \\ & + \underbrace{(1 - P_c)^2 \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty Q\left(\sqrt{(r_1 + r_2)^2 \bar{\gamma}}\right) f_{r_1}(r_1) f_{r_2}(r_2) dr_1 dr_2}_{P_{e_2}(\bar{\gamma}) \text{ (corresponding to bits 11)}} \\ & + \underbrace{P_c(1 - P_c) \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty Q\left(\sqrt{(u_1 + r_2)^2 \bar{\gamma}}\right) f_{u_1}(u_1) f_{r_2}(r_2) du_1 dr_2}_{P_{e_3}(\bar{\gamma}) \text{ (corresponding to bits 01)}} \\ & + \underbrace{P_c(1 - P_c) \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty Q\left(\sqrt{(r_1 + u_2)^2 \bar{\gamma}}\right) f_{r_1}(r_1) f_{u_2}(u_2) dr_1 du_2,}_{P_{e_4}(\bar{\gamma}) \text{ (corresponding to bits 10)}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

where $P_{e_3}(\bar{\gamma}) = P_{e_4}(\bar{\gamma})$ due to the similar possibility of error in one of the two feedback bits. Therefore, a closed-form solution corresponding to (2.23) is obtained as follows:

$$P_e(\bar{\gamma}) = P_{e_1}(\bar{\gamma}) + P_{e_2}(\bar{\gamma}) + 2P_{e_3}(\bar{\gamma}). \quad (2.24)$$

Proof: Refer to Appendix B.

Remark 2.6: For a 4×1 MISO-FSO system, it can be inferred from Table 2.2 that the proposed TTLS scheme requires two feedback bits. Therefore, corresponding to two feedback bits, there would be four possible cases as depicted in (2.23). Note that $P_{e_1}(\bar{\gamma})$ corresponds to BER when feedback bits are correctly decoded. Further, $P_{e_2}(\bar{\gamma})$, $P_{e_3}(\bar{\gamma})$ and $P_{e_4}(\bar{\gamma})$ corresponds to BERs corresponding to three erroneous possibilities of the feedback bits.

2.4.3 Diversity Order Investigation of TTLS Scheme

The diversity is the slope of decay of BER versus SNR plot at asymptotically high values of SNR. Mathematically, at very high SNR, BER can be written as:

$$\lim_{\bar{\gamma} \rightarrow \infty} P_e(\bar{\gamma}) \propto \bar{\gamma}^{(-D_o)}, \quad (2.25)$$

where D_o denotes the diversity order. For determining the diversity order of the TTLS scheme, we need to find D_o . For this, we need the asymptotic BER expressions corresponding to the integral form of $P_{e_1}(\bar{\gamma})$, $P_{e_2}(\bar{\gamma})$, and $P_{e_3}(\bar{\gamma})$ in (2.24). To this end, we apply the change of variables method to (2.24) and employ the Taylor series expansion of an exponential function. For instance, when we apply the change of variables method (substituting $u_1^2 \bar{\gamma} = x$ and $u_2^2 \bar{\gamma} = y$) to the integral form of $P_{e_1}(\bar{\gamma})$ of (2.24), the BER expression is given by (2.26). The Taylor series expansion corresponding to the exponential functions in (2.26) is further expressed as:

$$P_{e_1}(\bar{\gamma}) = P_c^2 \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty Q(\sqrt{x} + \sqrt{y}) \left(e^{-\sqrt{\frac{x}{\bar{\gamma}}}} - e^{-2\sqrt{\frac{x}{\bar{\gamma}}}} \right) \left(e^{-\sqrt{\frac{y}{\bar{\gamma}}}} - e^{-2\sqrt{\frac{y}{\bar{\gamma}}}} \right) \frac{dx}{\sqrt{\bar{\gamma}x}} \frac{dy}{\sqrt{\bar{\gamma}y}}}_{M_1}. \quad (2.26)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
e^{-\sqrt{\frac{x}{\bar{\gamma}}}} &= 1 - \sqrt{\frac{x}{\bar{\gamma}}} + \frac{x}{2\bar{\gamma}} - \frac{1}{6}\left(\frac{x}{\bar{\gamma}}\right)^{3/2} + \dots, \\
e^{-2\sqrt{\frac{x}{\bar{\gamma}}}} &= 1 - 2\sqrt{\frac{x}{\bar{\gamma}}} + \frac{2x}{\bar{\gamma}} - \frac{4}{3}\left(\frac{x}{\bar{\gamma}}\right)^{3/2} + \dots. \\
\text{Similarly, } e^{-\sqrt{\frac{y}{\bar{\gamma}}}} &= 1 - \sqrt{\frac{y}{\bar{\gamma}}} + \frac{y}{2\bar{\gamma}} - \frac{1}{6}\left(\frac{y}{\bar{\gamma}}\right)^{3/2} + \dots, \\
e^{-2\sqrt{\frac{y}{\bar{\gamma}}}} &= 1 - 2\sqrt{\frac{y}{\bar{\gamma}}} + \frac{2y}{\bar{\gamma}} - \frac{4}{3}\left(\frac{y}{\bar{\gamma}}\right)^{3/2} + \dots.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.27}$$

On substituting (2.27) into (2.26), and considering only the dominant terms (the term with minimum exponent of $\bar{\gamma}$, for $\bar{\gamma} \rightarrow \infty$) in the above Taylor series representations, the asymptotic BER expression corresponding to (2.26) for the diversity order analysis is given by:

$$P_{e_1}(\bar{\gamma})^{asy} = \underbrace{P_c^2 \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty Q(\sqrt{x} + \sqrt{y}) \frac{1}{(\bar{\gamma}^2)} dx dy}_{M_1} \tag{2.28}$$

Similarly, we can determine the asymptotic BER expressions corresponding to $P_{e_2}(\bar{\gamma})$ and $P_{e_3}(\bar{\gamma})$ such that the overall asymptotic BER expression corresponding to (2.24) for the diversity order analysis is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
P_e(\bar{\gamma})^{asy} &= \underbrace{P_c^2 \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty Q(\sqrt{x} + \sqrt{y}) \frac{1}{(\bar{\gamma}^2)} dx dy}_{M_1} \\
&+ \underbrace{(1 - P_c)^2 \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty Q(\sqrt{z} + \sqrt{t}) \frac{1}{(\bar{\gamma})\sqrt{zt}} dz dt}_{M_2} \\
&+ \underbrace{P_c(1 - P_c) \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty Q(\sqrt{x} + \sqrt{t}) \frac{1}{(\bar{\gamma}^{3/2})\sqrt{t}} dx dt}_{M_3},
\end{aligned} \tag{2.29}$$

where M_1 , M_2 , and M_3 are the asymptotic BER expressions corresponding to $P_{e_1}(\bar{\gamma})$, $P_{e_2}(\bar{\gamma})$ and $P_{e_3}(\bar{\gamma})$.

Remark 2.7: For $P_c = 1$, i.e., when feedback bits are decoded error free, the diversity order of (2.29) is determined by exponent of $\bar{\gamma}$ of M_1 , i.e., $D_o = 2$ (full diversity). However, for any other non-zero value of P_c , i.e., when there is error in decoding the

feedback bits, the diversity order is determined by exponent of $\bar{\gamma}$ of M_2 , i.e., $D_o = 1$ (diversity order corresponding to dominant BER expression). Note that dominant BER corresponds to the BER expression with the minimum exponent of $\bar{\gamma}$. Therefore, the TTLS scheme loses its diversity when the feedback bits are decoded erroneously.

2.5 Performance Investigation of METWS

In the Subsection 2.4.3, we analyzed the diversity order of the proposed TTLS scheme, and observed when an erroneous feedback scenario is considered, the TTLS scheme loses its diversity to some extent. To retain the full diversity, we propose METWS, in which the larger fraction of the total transmit power is allocated to the best transmit aperture from each cluster while the rest power is equally divided into other transmit apertures. Now, for a 4×1 MISO-FSO system, the weight vector structure for the METWS scheme is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{w}_1 &= [w, 2 - w]^T, \\
 \mathbf{w}_2 &= [2 - w, w]^T, \\
 \mathbf{w}_3 &= [w, 2 - w]^T, \\
 \mathbf{w}_4 &= [2 - w, w]^T,
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.30}$$

where w satisfies $1 \leq w \leq 2$. Let us discuss the above weight vector structure with the help of the following points:

1. For $w = 1$, the total available power is equally distributed among the two transmit apertures which leads to a uniform power-allocation-based MISO-FSO system (referred to as unweighted / repetition coding).
2. In the case that the feedback bits are correctly decoded at the transmitter, the transmitter selects the weight vector \mathbf{w}_k , if $I_k > I_l$ for $k \neq l$, where $l, k \in \{1, 2\}$ for C_1 and \mathbf{w}_s , if $I_s > I_t$ for $s \neq t$, where $s, t \in \{3, 4\}$ for C_2 .
3. However, due to an unguided wireless medium, quantized-feedback bits received at the Tx are susceptible to error and, as a result, the Tx can sometimes select an

incorrect weight vector that is associated with a deep faded channel as discussed in [112], [113].

4. For METWS, the transmit power constraint is given as $\frac{1}{L_t} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_{C_1}} w_i + \sum_{j=N_{C_1}+1}^{L_t} w_j \right) \leq \frac{N_A}{L_t}$. Note that $\sum_{i=1}^{N_{C_1}} w_i$ corresponds to the summation of the transmit weights corresponding to one of the possible weight vectors, \mathbf{w}_m , associated with C1, i.e., Cluster 1, where $m \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_{C_1}\}$. Similarly, $\sum_{j=N_{C_1}+1}^{L_t} w_j$ corresponds to the summation of the transmit weights corresponding to one of the possible weight vectors, \mathbf{w}_n , associated with C2, i.e., Cluster 2, where $n \in \{N_{C_1} + 1, N_{C_1} + 2, \dots, L_t\}$. Further, the factor $\frac{1}{L_t}$ is incorporated to have a fair comparison between the proposed METWS and the conventional STLS scheme.

For METWS, the channel irradiance vector is given as: $\mathbf{I} = [I_1, I_2, I_3, I_4]$. Moreover, to illustrate the concept of proposed METWS, we assume that the CSI at the receiver is given as: $I_1 > I_2$ (for C_1) and $I_3 > I_4$ (for C_2). For a 4×1 system, Table 2.2 indicates that in order to send the index of the best transmit aperture for both C_1 and C_2 , the receiver needs to send two quantized feedback bits to the Tx. Furthermore, the decoding of these two quantized feedback bits at the Tx for the transfer of the considered CSI can have the following possibilities:

Case 1: If feedback bits are correctly decoded at the transmitter corresponding to the CSI given as: $I_1 > I_2$ (for C_1) and $I_3 > I_4$ (for C_2), the received signal can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= \frac{\rho}{N_A} \mathbf{I} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{w}_1 \\ \mathbf{w}_3 \end{bmatrix} s + e, \\ &= \frac{\rho}{N_A} (wI_1 + (2-w)I_2 + wI_3 + (2-w)I_4) s + e, \end{aligned} \quad (2.31)$$

where $N_A = 4$ for METWS employing 4×1 MISO-FSO system. Moreover, the transmitter selects correct weight vector \mathbf{w}_1 and \mathbf{w}_3 corresponding to the correct decoding of the feedback bits related to the index of the best aperture for both C_1 and C_2 .

Case 2: If feedback bits are erroneously decoded at the Tx, the received signal can have the following three possibilities:

a) if the feedback bits related to the index of the best aperture are decoded as: $I_1 > I_2$ (for C_1) and $I_4 > I_3$ (for C_2), the received signal will be:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= \frac{\rho}{N_A} \mathbf{I} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{w}_1 \\ \mathbf{w}_4 \end{bmatrix} s + e, \\ &= \frac{\rho}{N_A} (wI_1 + (2-w)I_2 + (2-w)I_3 + wI_4)s + e. \end{aligned} \quad (2.32)$$

With this state of CSI, the Tx selects correct weight vector \mathbf{w}_1 for C_1 corresponding to the correct aperture selection from C_1 and incorrect weight vector \mathbf{w}_4 for C_2 corresponding to the incorrect aperture selection from C_2 .

b) if the feedback bits related to the index of the best aperture are decoded as: $I_1 < I_2$ (for C_1) and $I_3 > I_4$ (for C_2), the received signal is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= \frac{\rho}{N_A} \mathbf{I} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{w}_2 \\ \mathbf{w}_3 \end{bmatrix} s + e, \\ &= \frac{\rho}{N_A} ((2-w)I_1 + wI_2 + wI_3 + (2-w)I_4)s + e. \end{aligned} \quad (2.33)$$

With this state of CSI, the Tx selects incorrect weight vector \mathbf{w}_2 for C_1 corresponding to the incorrect aperture selection from C_1 and correct weight vector \mathbf{w}_3 for C_2 corresponding to the correct aperture selection from C_2 .

c) if the feedback bits related to the index of the best aperture are decoded as: $I_1 < I_2$ (for C_1) and $I_4 > I_3$ (for C_2), the received signal can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= \frac{\rho}{N_A} \mathbf{I} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{w}_2 \\ \mathbf{w}_4 \end{bmatrix} s + e, \\ &= \frac{\rho}{N_A} ((2-w)I_1 + wI_2 + (2-w)I_3 + wI_4)s + e. \end{aligned} \quad (2.34)$$

With this state of CSI, the Tx selects incorrect weight vector \mathbf{w}_2 for C_1 and \mathbf{w}_4 for C_2 , corresponding to the incorrect aperture selection from both C_1 and C_2 .

Now, we extend our discussion of the weight vector structure to a general $L_t \times 1$ MISO-FSO system. The generalized weight vector structure for a $L_t \times 1$ FSO system

is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{w}_1 &= \left[w, \frac{(N_C-w)}{N_C-1}, \frac{(N_C-w)}{N_C-1}, \dots, \frac{(N_C-w)}{N_C-1} \right]^T, \\
\mathbf{w}_2 &= \left[\frac{(N_C-w)}{N_C-1}, w, \frac{(N_C-w)}{N_C-1}, \dots, \frac{(N_C-w)}{N_C-1} \right]^T, \\
&\vdots \\
&\vdots \\
\mathbf{w}_{L_t} &= \left[\frac{(N_C-w)}{N_C-1}, \frac{(N_C-w)}{N_C-1}, \dots, \frac{(N_C-w)}{N_C-1}, w \right]^T,
\end{aligned} \tag{2.35}$$

where w is the error tolerant parameter that satisfies $1 \leq w \leq N_C$ with $N_C \in \{N_{C_1}, N_{C_2}\}$. In the case that feedback bits are correctly decoded at the Tx, the Tx puts weight w at the two best selected transmit apertures related to the channel irradiances corresponding to I_p and I_q , for C_1 and C_2 , respectively. Further, it assigns a normalized weight ($\frac{N_C-w}{N_C-1}$) to other apertures instead of allocating total transmit power to a single aperture. However, when the feedback bits are incorrectly decoded at the Tx, there are $(N_C - 1)$ incorrect choices of weight vector selection which are given as: \mathbf{w}_2 through \mathbf{w}_{L_t} .

$$\begin{aligned}
P_e(\bar{\gamma})^{METWS} &= \underbrace{4P_c^2 \int_{I_3=0}^{\infty} \int_{I_4=0}^{I_3} \int_{I_1=0}^{\infty} \int_{I_2=0}^{I_1} Q \left(\sqrt{(wI_1 + (2-w)I_2 + wI_3 + (2-w)I_4)^2 \bar{\gamma}} \right) e^{-I_2} e^{-I_1} e^{-I_4} e^{-I_3} dI_2 dI_1 dI_4 dI_3}_{\text{Case 1}} \\
&+ \underbrace{4P_c(1-P_c) \int_{I_3=0}^{\infty} \int_{I_4=0}^{I_3} \int_{I_1=0}^{\infty} \int_{I_2=0}^{I_1} Q \left(\sqrt{(wI_1 + (2-w)I_2 + (2-w)I_3 + wI_4)^2 \bar{\gamma}} \right) e^{-I_2} e^{-I_1} e^{-I_4} e^{-I_3} dI_2 dI_1 dI_4 dI_3}_{\text{Case 2 a)}} \\
&+ \underbrace{4P_c(1-P_c) \int_{I_3=0}^{\infty} \int_{I_4=0}^{I_3} \int_{I_1=0}^{\infty} \int_{I_2=0}^{I_1} Q \left(\sqrt{((2-w)I_1 + wI_2 + wI_3 + (2-w)I_4)^2 \bar{\gamma}} \right) e^{-I_2} e^{-I_1} e^{-I_4} e^{-I_3} dI_2 dI_1 dI_4 dI_3}_{\text{Case 2 b)}} \\
&+ \underbrace{4(1-P_c)^2 \int_{I_3=0}^{\infty} \int_{I_4=0}^{I_3} \int_{I_1=0}^{\infty} \int_{I_2=0}^{I_1} Q \left(\sqrt{((2-w)I_1 + wI_2 + (2-w)I_3 + wI_4)^2 \bar{\gamma}} \right) e^{-I_2} e^{-I_1} e^{-I_4} e^{-I_3} dI_2 dI_1 dI_4 dI_3}_{\text{Case 2 c)}}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.36}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P_e(\bar{\gamma})_{(asy)}^{METWS} = & \underbrace{4P_c^2 \int_{u=0}^{\infty} \int_{v=0}^u \int_{y=0}^{\infty} \int_{x=0}^y Q \left(\sqrt{(w\sqrt{y} + (2-w)\sqrt{x} + w\sqrt{u} + (2-w)\sqrt{v})^2 \bar{\gamma}} \right)}_{M_4} \frac{dx}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}x)}} \frac{dy}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}y)}} \frac{du}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}u)}} \frac{dv}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}v)}} \\
& + \underbrace{4(1-P_c)^2 \int_{u=0}^{\infty} \int_{v=0}^u \int_{y=0}^{\infty} \int_{x=0}^y Q \left(\sqrt{((2-w)\sqrt{y} + w\sqrt{x} + (2-w)\sqrt{u} + w\sqrt{v})^2 \bar{\gamma}} \right)}_{M_5} \frac{dx}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}x)}} \frac{dy}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}y)}} \frac{du}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}u)}} \frac{dv}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}v)}} \\
& + \underbrace{4P_c(1-P_c) \int_{u=0}^{\infty} \int_{v=0}^u \int_{y=0}^{\infty} \int_{x=0}^y Q \left(\sqrt{(w\sqrt{y} + 2-w\sqrt{x} + (2-w)\sqrt{u} + w\sqrt{v})^2 \bar{\gamma}} \right)}_{M_6} \frac{dx}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}x)}} \frac{dy}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}y)}} \frac{du}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}u)}} \frac{dv}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}v)}} \\
& + \underbrace{4P_c(1-P_c) \int_{u=0}^{\infty} \int_{v=0}^u \int_{y=0}^{\infty} \int_{x=0}^y Q \left(\sqrt{((2-w)\sqrt{y} + w\sqrt{x} + w\sqrt{u} + (2-w)\sqrt{v})^2 \bar{\gamma}} \right)}_{M_7} \frac{dx}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}x)}} \frac{dy}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}y)}} \frac{du}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}u)}} \frac{dv}{2\sqrt{(\bar{\gamma}v)}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.37}$$

Taking the above discussion into account, the analytical BER expression of METWS for a 4×1 MISO system is given by (2.36). The first set of four integrals corresponds to Case 1, which represents the BER expression corresponding to the correct decoding of the feedback bits related to the index of the best aperture from C_1 and C_2 . The second set of four integrals corresponds to Case 2 a), which represents the BER expression corresponding to the correct aperture selection from C_1 and incorrect aperture selection from C_2 . The third set of four integrals corresponds to Case 2 b), which represents the BER expression corresponding to the incorrect aperture selection from C_1 and correct aperture selection from C_2 . The fourth set of four integrals corresponds to Case 2 c), which represents the BER expression corresponding to the incorrect aperture selection from both C_1 and C_2 . Following the same methodology, we can obtain the analytical BER expression for the general $L_t \times 1$ MISO-FSO system. It is a tedious task to obtain a closed-form solution of (2.36). However, to obtain the closed-form of (2.36), we have also referred to some related works on the asymptotic analysis [114], [115]. It is worth mentioning that the approach used in [114] to determine the closed-form of Eq. (3) incorporating the PDF of β is not comparable to our case of Eq. (2.36). There is a mismatch of the PDF of the parameter β . Therefore, we keep the BER expression of (2.36) in the integral form. However, to compare the diversity order of TTLS and METWS, we need to obtain the asymptotic BER expression of METWS. So, we apply the change of variables method to (2.36) and employ the Taylor series expansion of an

Figure 2.2: Comparison of the proposed TTLS scheme with STLS and RC under perfect feedback for a 4×1 MISO-FSO System.

exponential function. By considering only the dominant terms corresponding to the lowest exponent of $\bar{\gamma}$, (2.36) can be rewritten as (2.37).

Remark 2.8: For $P_c = 1$, i.e., when feedback bits are decoded error-free, the diversity order of (2.37) is defined by exponent of $(\bar{\gamma})$ of M_4 and it is equal to 2, whereas M_5 , M_6 and M_7 evaluates to zero. However, for any other non-zero value of P_c , i.e., when there is an error in decoding the feedback bits, the diversity order is defined by either of M_5 , M_6 and M_7 , since all three have the same exponent of $\bar{\gamma}$ and it is equal to 2. From (2.37), it is clear that METWS is able to provide full diversity despite feedback errors.

2.6 Results and Discussion

In this section, we provide a detailed discussion of the proposed TTLS scheme and METWS. The simulation results are acquired by modeling the considered fading channel through MATLAB, and the analytical plots are obtained by employing the theoretical results deduced from the previous sections.

Figure 2.3: Comparison of the proposed TTLS scheme with STLS and RC under erroneous feedback for a 4×1 MISO-FSO System.

2.6.1 Performance of the Proposed Schemes over Negative Exponential Channel Model

Figure 2.2 illustrates the error performance curves of RC, STLS, and the proposed TTLS schemes assuming perfect feedback link (error-free feedback link). We make use of (2.19) to plot the analytical BER curve for the proposed TTLS scheme. The simulation curve is also presented to verify the correctness of the derived analytical BER expression. It can be seen from the figure that the proposed TTLS scheme performs in between RC and STLS under a perfect feedback scenario for the entire range of SNR. It is observed that RC loses approximately 2.5 dB for all BER values as compared to the TTLS. On the other hand, STLS outperforms RC by a margin of approximately 5 dB and TTLS by a margin of 1.5 dB only. The diversity order of the proposed TTLS scheme can be obtained by calculating the slope of the BER curve at a very high SNR. For instance, BER is 2.454×10^{-4} at 20 dB whereas it is 2×10^{-6} at 30 dB and therefore slope can be obtained as $\log_{10}(2.454 \times 10^{-4}/2 \times 10^{-6})$, which is approximately equal to 2 (full diversity). Note that the same diversity is analytically

observed in Subsection 2.4.3 using asymptotic BER expression given by (2.28). This verifies the correctness of the analytical diversity order. Since error performance curves of all the considered schemes are parallel to each other, the diversity order is also the same for these schemes under the error-free feedback link.

Observation 2.1: Under perfect feedback scenario, STLS scheme slightly outperforms the proposed TTLS scheme. However, both the schemes achieve the same diversity order.

A more practical comparison of the conventional STLS and proposed TTLS scheme is illustrated in Fig. 2.3 assuming, an imperfect (erroneous) feedback link. The probability of correct detection of the feedback bits, i.e., P_c is assumed to be 0.99 (1 percent feedback error). The figure illustrates how the imperfect feedback link affects STLS and TTLS performance. The diversity order of the STLS will be $1/2$, which is similar to the diversity order of a SISO link-based negative-exponential channel, if the diversity order is calculated from the slope of the BER curve. Since STLS provides SISO link-based performance and no diversity under imperfect feedback link, the performance advantage observed for STLS in [18-24] cannot be practically attained. On the other hand, the proposed TTLS scheme outperforms the conventional STLS scheme by a significant margin.

Observation 2.2: Under the erroneous feedback scenario, the conventional STLS scheme gives the worst performance while the proposed TTLS scheme can provide significant performance gain.

Let us compare the performance of the proposed TTLS scheme with the conventional STLS scheme from the practical communication system design perspective. From a deep inspection of Fig. 2.3, we can have the following insightful observations:

Observation 2.3: The performance comparison of the proposed TTLS and the conventional STLS schemes depicted in Fig. 2.3 can be divided into two SNR regimes, i.e., low and high. For a low SNR regime, i.e., SNR range of $\approx 0-8$ dB, the conventional STLS scheme slightly outperforms the proposed TTLS scheme. However, the corresponding $BER \approx 10^{-2}$ is very high, and it cannot be the target BER for any practical communication system design. Further, it is worth mentioning that the crossover in

the plots of conventional STLS and the proposed TTLS in Fig. 2.3 at low SNR is because of the impact of very strong turbulence corresponding to the negative exponential channel model. Moreover, at low SNR, the impact of noise is also dominant. Another reason for the crossover in the plots of STLS and TTLS is because the STLS scheme corresponds to a SISO link-based communication system. Now, the BER plot of a SISO link-based system does not have a typical waterfall curve. Therefore, the crossover comes into account. Furthermore, in the subsequent subsection, wherein we will observe the performance of the proposed schemes under the G-G and LN channel models, it will be shown that the crossover in the plots of STLS and TTLS becomes almost negligible due to the lesser impact of AT.

Observation 2.4: Note that in Fig. 2.3 after SNR=10 dB, the proposed TTLS scheme completely outperforms the conventional STLS scheme. Moreover, the reliability of any practical communication system design is governed by the term *diversity*, and it is an *asymptotic* parameter as mathematically defined in (2.25). It can be seen from Fig. 2.3 that at high SNR, the diversity, as well as BER performance of the proposed TTLS scheme, is significantly better as compared to the conventional STLS scheme. Further, a practical SNR range, i.e., 0-35 dB, is considered in this work. This practical SNR range can be cross-verified with a very recent research work [116]. Therefore, differing from the existing literature, we considered a very practical range of SNR in this work, even lower than [116].

We have observed that the proposed TTLS scheme is not able to provide full diversity when an erroneous feedback link scenario is considered. Therefore, to retain the full diversity, we introduce another proposed scheme METWS as discussed in Section 2.5. In Fig. 2.4, we compare the performance of the proposed METWS with RC for a fix weight parameter $w = 1.9$ and consider two different scenarios of feedback error with $P_c = 0.99$ and $P_c = 0.98$. We use (2.37) to plot the asymptotic BER curve for the two different feedback scenarios. In both the considered scenarios, we observe that the METWS performs better as compared to RC and provides significant performance gain. Moreover, METWS can provide a diversity order of 2 (full diversity) despite feedback errors. Note that, asymptotic BER performance curves using (2.37) are plotted

Figure 2.4: Comparison of METWS with RC for a fix weight parameter $w = 1.9$ and different values of P_c .

Figure 2.5: Optimization of the weight parameter w by minimizing (2.37) for $P_c = 0.99, 0.95, 0.9, 0.8$; w^* denotes the optimized value of w minimizing BER.

for the proposed METWS in Fig. 2.4. Therefore, at lower SNR values, the conventional RC scheme outperforms the proposed METWS. However, at higher/asymptotic SNR values, the proposed METWS completely outperforms the RC scheme despite feedback errors. To be specific, the performance comparison of the proposed METWS and the conventional RC scheme is more appropriate at higher SNR values. In Fig. 2.5, the asymptotic BER equation given by (2.37) is used to determine the optimized values of the weight parameter w . We plot the BER curve for $0.1 < w < 1.9$ to find the optimized values of w for different feedback errors, i.e., for different values of P_c in a 4×1 MISO-FSO system. The optimized values of w for different values of P_c are calculated by numerically minimizing (2.37). The numerical computation of the optimized value of w can be swiftly done by numerically evaluating (2.37) using software like MATLAB/ MATHEMATICA. Note that w^* denotes the optimized value of w , which minimizes the BER. The SNR value is taken as 27 dB. For a particular value of P_c , the corresponding optimized value of w , i.e., w^* is given in the figure. For example, when $P_c = 0.95$, the value of w^* is found to be 1.8. It can be observed from the figure that w^* moves towards two with an increasing value of P_c .

Figure 2.6 shows the comparison of the proposed METWS with STLS and RC for $P_c = 0.99$ and the corresponding optimum value of w , i.e., $w^* = 1.9$. We use (2.37) to plot the asymptotic analytical BER curve of METWS. It can be observed from the figure that the proposed METWS performs better as compared to RC for all the BER values, whereas the STLS scheme performs the worst in the considered imperfect feedback link scenario. However, the proposed METWS clearly shows a significant performance gain of 2-2.5 dB as compared to RC. Furthermore, the BER curves of METWS and RC are parallel to each other, which indicates that the proposed METWS and RC have the same diversity order, whereas the conventional STLS scheme can provide only a SISO link-based diversity performance under a practical (erroneous) feedback link scenario.

Remark 2.9: The asymptotic BER for METWS is derived and plotted. Therefore, a fair comparison at high SNR is desired. Moreover, due to the asymptotic BER plot of METWS, the crossover in the plots of the conventional STLS/RC and the proposed

Figure 2.6: Comparison of METWS with STLS and RC for $P_c = 0.99$ and corresponding optimum weight parameter $w^* = 1.9$ for a 4×1 MISO-FSO system.

METWS exists.

2.6.2 Simulation-Based Results of the Proposed Schemes over G-G and LN Channel Models

In this subsection, we will examine how well the two proposed schemes function under the consideration of the G-G and LN channel models. The combined impact of AT and PE for the G-G channel model can be characterized by the following PDF [117]:

$$f_{I_i}(I) = \frac{\alpha\beta\zeta^2}{A_0\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} G_{1,3}^{3,0} \left(\frac{\alpha\beta I}{A_0} \left| \begin{matrix} \zeta^2 \\ \zeta^2 - 1, \alpha - 1, \beta - 1 \end{matrix} \right. \right), \quad (2.38)$$

where α and β are the AT parameters meant for characterizing the irradiance fluctuations. Further, $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function, and $G_{p,q}^{m,n}(\cdot)$ is the Meijer-G function [118, Subsection 2.24]. In this work, the parameter (α, β) is taken as $(4, 1.9)$ to model the moderate AT regime. The parameters A_0 and ζ are defined in [117]. Further, the LN channel model is used to model the weak AT regime. The combined impact of AT

Figure 2.7: Performance of the proposed TTLS scheme and METWS over G-G and LN channel models for an 8×1 MISO-FSO system under imperfect feedback link with $P_c = 0.98$ and $\zeta = 3.35$.

and PE for the LN channel model can be characterized by the following PDF [117]:

$$f_{I_i}(I) = \frac{\zeta^2 I^{\zeta^2-1}}{2(A_o)\zeta^2} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{\ln\left(\frac{I}{A_o}\right) + q}{\sqrt{8\sigma^2}}\right) \times \exp(2\sigma^2\zeta^2(1 + \zeta^2)), I > 0, \quad (2.39)$$

where $q = 2\sigma^2(1 + 2\zeta^2)$.

In Fig. 2.7, the performance curves for the proposed TTLS and METWS over the G-G and LN channel models are presented and discussed. For both the channel models, the combined effect of AT and PE is taken into account. Moreover, an imperfect feedback link scenario is considered. It can be observed from the figure that for both the proposed schemes, the performance corresponding to the LN channel model is significantly better as compared to the G-G model. *Note that this performance gain offered by the LN channel model is mainly because the LN channel model characterizes the weak AT regime, i.e., the lesser effect of AT on the performance.*

2.6.3 Extension of the Proposed Schemes to MIMO-FSO Scenario

From the analytical analysis of the proposed TTLS scheme and METWS for a 4×1 MISO-FSO system, we have observed the mathematical complexity in obtaining the average BER expressions. However, for completeness of the study, we provide the simulation-based results of the proposed schemes for an 8×1 MISO and 8×2 MIMO set-up in Fig. 2.8. The aim of providing these simulation plots is to show that the proposed TTLS scheme and METWS outperform the conventional STLS and RC schemes for an arbitrary number of transmitting and receive apertures despite erroneous feedback. To examine the performance under the worst-case scenario, a very strong turbulence regime-based negative exponential channel model is considered.

Similar to the MISO-FSO scenario, the received electrical signal corresponding to the MIMO-FSO scenario at the j^{th} , $j = 1, 2, \dots, L_r$ receive aperture can be expressed as:

$$y_j = \rho \mathbf{I}_j \mathbf{w} s + e_j, \quad (2.40)$$

where \mathbf{I}_j is the channel irradiance vector, $\mathbf{I}_j \triangleq [I_{j,1}, I_{j,2}, \dots, I_{j,L_t}]$, and \mathbf{w} is the weight vector structure as discussed for the proposed schemes. Further, e_j denotes the zero-mean AWGN of σ^2 variance. Using the equal gain combining (EGC) technique, the receiver can combine the received electrical signals as:

$$y = \sum_{j=1}^{L_r} y_j = \rho \sum_{j=1}^{L_r} \mathbf{I}_j \mathbf{w} s + \sum_{j=1}^{L_r} e_j. \quad (2.41)$$

For the EGC, a maximum-likelihood receiver is defined as:

$$\hat{s} = \min_{s \in \{A, 0\}} \left| y - \rho \sum_{j=1}^{L_r} \mathbf{I}_j \mathbf{w} s \right|^2. \quad (2.42)$$

In Fig. 2.8, we plot the performance curves of the proposed TTLS scheme and METWS for an 8×1 MISO and 8×2 MIMO set-up under an imperfect feedback link scenario with $P_c = 0.98$. For an 8×1 MISO set-up, TTLS performs better as compared to METWS for $\text{SNR} < 20$ dB, and afterward, METWS performs better. Further, for

Figure 2.8: Simulation-based performance of the proposed TTLS scheme and METWS under erroneous feedback for an 8×1 MISO and 8×2 MIMO set-up with $P_c = 0.98$.

an 8×2 MIMO set-up, at low SNR, TTLS slightly outperforms METWS. However, at high SNR, METWS outperforms TTLS by a significant margin of 4-5 dB. On the other side, both TTLS and METWS outperform the conventional STLS and RC schemes. It is expected that there will not be a significant difference in the performance of the conventional STLS scheme for an 8×1 MISO and 8×2 MIMO set-up. Therefore, only the 8×2 MIMO set-up-based performance curve is depicted in Fig. 2.8 for the conventional STLS scheme.

Remark 2.10: Note that the MIMO system provides a significant performance gain as compared to the MISO system. It is mainly because of the more number of independent propagation paths offered by the MIMO set-up that improves the reliability of the communication system.

Remark 2.11: The validity of **Remark 2.4** is proved by considering a four cluster-based transmission scenario. It can be observed from Fig. 2.8 that the performance of the two proposed schemes deteriorates when four clusters are taken into account as compared to a two-cluster-based scenario. For an 8×1 MISO set-up, the possible

combinations of the clusters for the two best aperture selection are $C1 - C2$, $C1 - C3$, $C1 - C4$, $C2 - C3$, $C2 - C4$, and $C3 - C4$. Note that $N_{C_1} = N_{C_2} = N_{C_3} = N_{C_4} = Lt/4$. The transmit apertures are evenly distributed, i.e., two transmit apertures in each cluster. Because of the more number of clusters, the imperfect CSIT highly affects the performance under a four cluster-based transmission scenario. Additionally, the multiple clusters-based aperture selection scheme increases the feedback overhead as compared to the proposed two clusters-based aperture selection strategy. Therefore, in this work, we efficiently divide the arbitrary number of transmit apertures into not more than two clusters.

2.7 Conclusions

Two novel clustering-based TLS schemes (namely TTLS and METWS) have been presented and examined in this chapter to enhance the diversity and overall performance of the FSO systems. The conventional STLS scheme gives the worst performance when feedback errors (practical feedback scenario) are taken into consideration. However, the proposed TTLS scheme analyzed in this chapter outperforms the conventional STLS scheme despite feedback errors. However, when compared with the RC scheme, the TTLS scheme is not able to provide full diversity in the imperfect feedback link scenario. Further, to retain the full diversity, we also proposed a new METWS in which the power allocation has been done through a weight vector. It has been observed through the simulation and analytical results that the proposed METWS outperforms STLS as well as RC despite feedback errors, and thereby providing a significant performance gain.

Chapter 3

Diversity-Multiplexing Tradeoff for OWC Systems

In this chapter, we emphasize investigating the DMT for OWC systems. We mainly focus on indoor VLC and outdoor FSO systems. We first consider the indoor VLC scenario and then the outdoor FSO scenario. Note that the existing literature on DMT is mainly focused on RF systems [30, 58, 60]. Contrary to this, in this chapter, we investigate the DMT of the indoor VLC system for the first time. The DMT analysis starts by considering an elementary SISO-VLC system. Afterward, the analysis is also extended to the MIMO-VLC system. Moreover, considering the practicality, random mobility of the end-user is incorporated for the considered indoor VLC system. Further, new analytical expressions for the PDF corresponding to the random radial movement of the end-user, outage probability (in terms of the multiplexing gain and other VLC parameters), and outage diversity order for the SISO-VLC and MIMO-VLC systems are derived. Furthermore, we extend our study to the outdoor FSO system. For the first time in literature, a limited feedback-based DMT is investigated for the FSO system under different transmission scenarios. Considering the outdoor FSO system, we consider a MIMO-FSO setup and investigate the DMT for single-rate and adaptive-rate transmission scenarios. Some new insights are envisioned in the form of **interesting observations**

Publication based on this chapter are [C2] and [J2].

3.1 Introduction

OWC is a modern communication technology that has attracted significant attention in the research community. OWC is anticipated to be an essential alternative for future low-mobility indoor wireless communications. As far as indoor OWC is concerned, it includes two main technologies: infrared communications and VLC. The indoor OWC system, also known as VLC, corresponds to the transmission of the optical signal from the visible spectrum (400 THz to 800 THz). For illumination and data communications, VLC systems often employ LEDs [1], [2].

The research has included VLC-based studies over the past few years that have taken a variety of factors into account, such as channel characterization [32], different modulation schemes [33], different coding schemes [34], development of MIMO-VLC systems [35], performance investigation of non-orthogonal multiple access [36], transceiver design [37], and channel capacity [38]. **However, none of the works have investigated the DMT of an indoor VLC.** Moreover, considering the outdoor FSO system, there is no work in the literature emphasizing the DMT with limited feedback under different transmission scenarios. The study in [31] analyzed the DMT without considering the concept of CSIT. Further, single-rate and adaptive-rate transmission scenarios were not considered in [31]. Motivated by the aforesaid discussion, in this chapter, we investigate the DMT of OWC systems. To this end, the chapter has the following contributions:

- Considering a practical indoor VLC scenario, random mobility of the end-user is incorporated in the considered VLC system model. For the proposed indoor VLC system, the optimal DMT for both SISO and MIMO systems is analyzed.
- Further, novel analytical expressions for the PDF corresponding to the radial movement of the end-user, outage probability (in terms of the multiplexing gain and other VLC parameters), and outage diversity order for the SISO-VLC and MIMO-VLC systems are developed. Moreover, an optimization problem formulation-based technique is adopted to derive the optimal DMT.

- Furthermore, we extend our study to the outdoor FSO system. For the first time, a limited feedback-based DMT is investigated for the FSO system under different transmission scenarios. To this end, we consider a MIMO-FSO setup and investigate the DMT for single-rate and adaptive-rate transmission scenarios.
- By performing joint power and rate control, we derive the optimal DMT of the MIMO-FSO system in terms of the outage upper bound in both cases (single-rate and adaptive-rate) in a recursive fashion.
- Finally, some new insights are envisioned in the form of **interesting observations** that have not been previously marked in the literature.

3.2 Indoor VLC System

Considering an indoor VLC scenario, let there be N transmitting LEDs and M end-users in a room. To send information to the end-users, the room's ceiling is covered with N transmitting LEDs. A particular transmitting LED is denoted by l_j , $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and a particular end-user is denoted by u_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$. As shown in Fig. 3.1, the LED transmitter is placed at a height D (in metres) from the u_i end-user with angle of irradiance ϕ_{u_i} , the angle of incidence ψ_{u_i} and radius r_{u_i} on the polar coordinate plane. The euclidean distance between the l_j^{th} LED and the u_i^{th} PD Rx is denoted by d_{u_i} .

The intercell interferences received from other transmitting LEDs are approximated with the additive Gaussian process [32], [35]. Further, the semi-angle at the half-illuminance of LED (half-power angle), $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}}$, can be mathematically related to the maximum radius of a LED cell footprint, R_e , as $R_e = \frac{D \sin(\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}})}{\cos(\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}})}$. The order of Lambertian emission (mode number expressing directivity of the source beam) is defined as [1], [32]:

$$L_o \triangleq -\frac{\ln 2}{\ln(\cos(\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}}))}, \quad (3.1)$$

where $0^\circ < \Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} < 90^\circ$. The channel coefficient of the LOS link between LED and end-user u_i is given by [32]:

$$h_{u_i} = \frac{A_D(L_o + 1)\rho}{2\pi d_{u_i}^2} \cos^{L_o}(\phi_{u_i}) Tg(\psi_{u_i}) \cos(\psi_{u_i}), \quad (3.2)$$

Figure 3.1: Geometry of the indoor LOS VLC propagation model.

where A_D is a physical surface area of the PD, ρ is the PD responsivity, T is the gain of the optical filter, and $g(\psi_{u_i})$, the optical concentrator, is defined as [34]:

$$g(\psi_{u_i}) \triangleq \begin{cases} \frac{n^2}{\sin^2(\Psi)}, & 0 \leq \psi_{u_i} \leq \Psi \\ 0, & \psi_{u_i} > \Psi \end{cases}, \quad (3.3)$$

where n is the refractive index of lens at a PD and $\Psi \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$ is the FOV of the PD Rx. It is assumed that the surface of the PD Rx is parallel to the ground and the PD has no orientation towards the LED. Thus, it holds that $\phi_{u_i} = \psi_{u_i}$.

Based on the geometry, as shown in the figure, the following relations hold:

$$d_{u_i} = \sqrt{r_{u_i}^2 + D^2}, \quad (3.4a)$$

$$\cos(\phi_{u_i}) = \frac{D}{\sqrt{r_{u_i}^2 + D^2}}, \quad (3.4b)$$

$$\chi = \frac{A_D(L_o + 1)\mathfrak{R}}{2\pi} T g(\psi_{u_i}) D^{L_o+1}. \quad (3.4c)$$

Accordingly, the channel coefficient h_{u_i} in (3.2) can be rewritten as:

$$h_{u_i} = \frac{\chi}{(r_{u_i}^2 + D^2)^{\frac{L_o+3}{2}}}. \quad (3.5)$$

Assuming that the user position is random over the circular area, the radial distance

of the u_i^{th} end-user is modeled by a uniform distribution with the PDF:

$$f_{r_{u_i}}(r_{u_i}) = \frac{2r_{u_i}}{R_e^2}, \quad (3.6)$$

where $0 \leq r_{u_i} \leq R_e$.

Moreover, the instantaneous SNR of the VLC channel of the u_i^{th} end-user is defined as [1]:

$$\gamma \triangleq \frac{\rho^2 h_{u_i}^2 P_t^2}{\sigma^2}, \quad (3.7)$$

where P_t is the transmitted optical intensity of each LED and σ^2 represents the noise variance.

Remark 3.1: In addition to the LOS link, a complete VLC channel also includes diffused components that result from light reflections from interior surfaces. The strongest diffused component is reportedly at least 7 dB (electrical) lower than the weakest LOS component, according to [34]. Hence, only the LOS link is taken into account.

Definitions: We introduce some important definitions to characterize the DMT of the indoor VLC system.

- For any function of γ , i.e., $f(\gamma)$, the following equality:

$$\lim_{\gamma \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log f(\gamma)}{\log \gamma} = v, \quad (3.8)$$

is denoted as $f(\gamma) \doteq \gamma^v$, where \doteq represents exponential equality.

- An outage event has the interpretation that the channel does not support a target data rate, or in other words, when the instantaneous channel capacity, $C(\mathbf{H})$, is less than the target data rate, $R(\gamma)$. Mathematically,

$$P_{out}(R, \gamma) \triangleq \Pr(C(\mathbf{H}) < R(\gamma)), \quad (3.9)$$

where $P_{out}(R, \gamma)$ is the outage error probability and the probability is defined over the random channel matrix \mathbf{H} . In this chapter, we use Telatar's capacity

formula, which is used to find capacity of any wireless communication system and is given by [119]:

$$C(\mathbf{H}) \triangleq \frac{1}{2} \log_2 \left(\det \left(\mathbf{I}_M + \frac{\gamma}{N^2} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^T \right) \right), \quad (3.10)$$

where $\det(\cdot)$ denotes the determinant, the identity matrix of order $M \times M$ is denoted as \mathbf{I}_M and \mathbf{H}^T denotes the transpose of matrix \mathbf{H} . Since the channel coefficients are real and positive in IM/DD VLC system, hence (3.10) contains \mathbf{H}^T instead of \mathbf{H}^\dagger , where \mathbf{H}^\dagger denotes hermitian of the matrix \mathbf{H} .

Since the capacity expression given in (3.10) corresponds to an IM/DD VLC system, the expression in (3.10) is slightly different from that given in [119]. The first difference is the factor $1/2$ due to half degrees of freedom offered by the real-valued channel gains as compared to the complex-valued channel gains. The second difference is the term N^2 ; this is because the received electrical signal is directly proportional to the optical power in the VLC system. Moreover, the maximization of the capacity is done over the total transmit power constraint, which depends upon the peak power of the input signal and it is positive for an IM/DD VLC system.

- Let d and r denote the diversity and multiplexing gains, respectively, then [60]:

$$d = - \lim_{\delta \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log P_{out}(R, \gamma)}{\log \gamma}, \quad (3.11)$$

and

$$r = \lim_{\gamma \rightarrow \infty} \frac{R(\gamma)}{\frac{1}{2} \log \gamma}. \quad (3.12)$$

3.3 DMT Analysis of Indoor VLC System

In this section, we will derive the outage probability and outage diversity order for the channel gain given by (3.5). We begin with deriving the optimal DMT for an elementary SISO-VLC system. The derived DMT of the SISO-VLC system is then used as a benchmark to verify the correctness of the MIMO-VLC DMT.

3.3.1 Outage Probability and DMT Analysis for SISO-VLC System

For a SISO-VLC system, the channel capacity expression given in (3.10) conditioned on h_{u_i} can be written as:

$$C(h_{u_i}) = \frac{1}{2} \log(1 + \gamma h_{u_i}^2). \quad (3.13)$$

From (3.9) and (3.12), the outage probability at very high SNR is obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{out}(R, \gamma) &= \Pr \left(\frac{1}{2} \log(1 + \gamma h_{u_i}^2) \leq \frac{r}{2} \log(\gamma) \right) \\ &\approx \Pr \left(h_{u_i} \leq \gamma^{\frac{-(1-r)}{2}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

Now, in order to compute (3.14), we need to determine the PDF of h_{u_i} . By utilizing the PDF of r_{u_i} given by (3.6), the PDF of h_{u_i} can be derived by applying the concept of transformation of RVs to (3.5):

$$f_{h_{u_i}}(h_{u_i}) = \frac{2}{R_e^2(L_o + 3)} \chi^{\frac{2}{L_o+3}} h_{u_i}^G = B h_{u_i}^G. \quad (3.15)$$

In (3.15), $h_{u_i} \in [h_{u_i \min}, h_{u_i \max}]$, where $h_{u_i \min} = \frac{\chi}{(R_e^2 + D^2)^{\frac{L_o+3}{2}}}$, $h_{u_i \max} = \frac{\chi}{D^{L_o+3}}$, $B = \frac{2}{R_e^2(L_o+3)} \chi^{\frac{2}{L_o+3}}$, and $G = \frac{L_o+5}{L_o+3}$, such that the optimal outage diversity order $d_{out}^*(r)$ is non-negative. Therefore, from (3.14) we get:

$$P_{out}(R, \gamma) = \int_0^{\gamma^{\frac{-(1-r)}{2}}} f_{h_{u_i}}(h_{u_i}) dh_{u_i} = \frac{B}{1+G} \left[\gamma^{-(1+G)\frac{(1-r)}{2}} \right]. \quad (3.16)$$

Further, using (3.8), (3.16) can be written as:

$$P_{out}(R, \gamma) \doteq \gamma^{-(1+G)\frac{(1-r)}{2}}. \quad (3.17)$$

On substituting (3.17) into (3.11), the optimal outage diversity order is obtained as:

$$d_{out}^*(r) = (1+G) \frac{(1-r)}{2}, \quad (3.18)$$

where $r \in (0, Z)$. Further, we define $Y \triangleq \max(N, M)$ and $Z \triangleq \min(N, M)$. Note that Z is the maximum multiplexing gain in the VLC channel. For a SISO-VLC system, $r \in (0, 1)$. The derived expression in (3.18), will be used as a benchmark for verifying the correctness of the outage diversity order for the MIMO-VLC system in the subsequent subsection.

3.3.2 Outage Probability and DMT Analysis for MIMO-VLC System

In this subsection, we will derive the outage probability and the outage diversity order for a MIMO-VLC system. For a general $N \times M$ MIMO-VLC system, where N being the number of transmitting LEDs and M corresponds to the number of photodetectors, outage occurs when the channel matrix \mathbf{H} is nearly singular. Therefore, we must focus on the probability that the singular values of \mathbf{H} are close to zero. On substituting (3.10) into (3.9) and applying eigenvalue decomposition (EVD) of $\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^T$, we have:

$$P_{out}(R, \gamma) = \Pr \left(\sum_{k=1}^Z \log \left(1 + \frac{\gamma}{N} \lambda_k \right) < \gamma^r \right), \quad (3.19)$$

where $\lambda_k, k = 1, 2, \dots, Z$, are real and non-negative eigenvalues of $\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^T$ and $0 \leq \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_Z$. Let us define $\lambda_i \triangleq \gamma^{-\alpha_i}$ [30]. Therefore, at high SNR, $(1 + \frac{\gamma}{N} \lambda_i) \doteq \gamma^{(1-\alpha_i)^+}$, where x^+ denotes $\max(0, x)$. Here, α_i indicates the level of the singularity of channel matrix \mathbf{H} . Further, larger the α_i 's are, the more singular \mathbf{H} is. Thus, (3.19) can be rewritten at high SNR as:

$$P_{out}(R, \gamma) \doteq \Pr \left[\sum_{i=1}^Z (1 - \alpha_i)^+ < r \right], \quad (3.20)$$

where $\mathcal{A} = \left\{ \alpha : \alpha_1 \geq \dots \geq \alpha_Z \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^Z (1 - \alpha_i)^+ \leq r \right\}$ describes the outage event in terms of singularity levels. The outage probability can be computed as the probability that $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$:

$$P_{out}(R, \gamma) \doteq \int_{\mathcal{A}} p(\alpha) d\alpha, \quad (3.21)$$

where $p(\alpha)$ represents the joint PDF of α_i 's. The PDF of α derived in [58] is valid for the complex channel gain matrix \mathbf{H} . However, the PDF of α in terms of the PDF of \mathbf{H} , when \mathbf{H} is real, is derived as:

$$p_{(\alpha)}(\alpha) = K_{N,M} (\log \gamma)^Z \left(\prod_{i=1}^Z \gamma^{-\frac{(Y-Z+1)\alpha_i}{2}} \right) \times \prod_{i < j} |\gamma^{-\alpha_i} - \gamma^{-\alpha_j}| \times \left[\int_{\mathbf{V}_{M,M}} \int_{\mathbf{V}_{M,N}} p_{\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{Q})} d\mathbf{Q} d\mathbf{U} \right], \quad (3.22)$$

where $K_{N,M}$ is normalization constant, $\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}\{\gamma^{-\alpha_1/2}, \dots, \gamma^{-\alpha_Z/2}\}$, $\text{diag}(\cdot)$ denotes the diagonal, $\mathbf{V}_{M,M}$ and $\mathbf{V}_{M,N}$ are the Stiefel manifolds [120]. On substituting (3.22) into (3.21), the outage probability can be written as:

$$P_{out}(R, \gamma) \doteq \int_{\mathcal{A}} K_{N,M} (\log \gamma)^Z \left(\prod_{i=1}^Z \gamma^{-\frac{(Y-Z+1)\alpha_i}{2}} \right) \times \prod_{i < j} |\gamma^{-\alpha_i} - \gamma^{-\alpha_j}| \times \left[\int_{\mathbf{V}_{M,M}} \int_{\mathbf{V}_{M,N}} p_{\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{Q})} d\mathbf{Q} d\mathbf{U} \right]. \quad (3.23)$$

Since we are interested only in the SNR exponent of the $P_{out}(R, \gamma)$, i.e., $\lim_{\gamma \rightarrow \infty} \log P_{out}(R, \gamma) / \log(\gamma)$, we can make some approximations in the integral given in (3.23). Firstly, the term $K_{N,M} (\log \gamma)^Z$ has no influence on the γ exponent. Secondly, for any $j > i$, $|\gamma^{-\alpha_i} - \gamma^{-\alpha_j}| \doteq \gamma^{-\alpha_j}$, where $\alpha_j < \alpha_i$. Therefore, after considering these approximations, (3.23) can be rewritten as:

$$P_{out}(R, \gamma) \doteq \int_{\mathcal{A}} \gamma^{-\sum_{i=1}^Z \frac{Y-Z+2i-1}{2} \alpha_i} \times \left[\int_{\mathbf{V}_{M,M}} \int_{\mathbf{V}_{M,N}} p_{\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{Q})} d\mathbf{Q} d\mathbf{U} \right]. \quad (3.24)$$

Moreover, the channel gains are independent to each other, hence:

$$p_{\mathbf{H}}(\mathbf{H}) = \prod_{i=1}^M \prod_{j=1}^N f_{h_{ij}}(h_{ij}) = \left(\frac{2}{R_e^2(L_o+3)} \chi^{\frac{2}{L_o+3}} \right)^{NM} \prod_{i=1}^M \prod_{j=1}^N h_{ij}^G, \quad (3.25)$$

where the PDF $f_{h_{ij}}(h_{ij})$ is given by (3.15). Further, we need to find the exponent of the γ of the term $f(\gamma) = \left[\int_{\mathbf{V}_{M,M}} \int_{\mathbf{V}_{M,N}} p_{\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{Q})} d\mathbf{Q} d\mathbf{U} \right]$ given in (3.24). Since we are interested in the near zero behaviour of the PDF of \mathbf{H} to compute the outage diversity order, the PDF of \mathbf{H} in terms of the polynomial of γ is given by [119, Eq.(19)]. We must note that $h_{ij} = [\mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{Q}]_{ij}$ is a polynomial expression of γ [58], and the coefficients are functions of \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{Q} . The term with the highest order is $\gamma^{-\frac{\alpha_Z}{2}}$ and its corresponding coefficient is nonzero. Accordingly, for high SNR ($\gamma \rightarrow \infty$), we can write $h_{ij} \doteq \gamma^{-\frac{\alpha_Z}{2}}$. The term $\left(\frac{2}{R_e^2(L_o+3)} \chi^{\frac{2}{L_o+3}} \right)^{NM}$ can be neglected at high SNR, since it does not influence the exponent of γ . Therefore, we have $f(\gamma) \doteq \gamma^{-\frac{MN\alpha_Z G}{2}}$. On substituting $f(\gamma)$ into (3.24), the outage probability is obtained as:

$$P_{out}(R, \gamma) \doteq \gamma^{-\inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^Z \frac{Y-Z+2i-1}{2} \alpha_i + \frac{MN\alpha_Z G}{2} \right\}} \quad (3.26)$$

On substituting (3.26) into (3.11), the optimal outage diversity order for the MIMO-VLC system is given as:

$$d_{out}^*(r) = \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^Z \frac{Y - Z + 2i - 1}{2} \alpha_i + \frac{NM\alpha_Z G}{2} \right\}, \quad (3.27)$$

where $\mathcal{A} = \left\{ \alpha : \alpha_1 \geq \dots \geq \alpha_Z \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^Z (1 - \alpha_i)^+ \leq r \right\}$ describes the outage event in terms of singularity levels. Further, to check the correctness of the derived outage diversity order expression given by (3.27), we substitute $N = M = 1$ into (3.27), which reduces it into an expression for the outage diversity SISO-VLC system given by (3.18).

Remark 3.2: To obtain the optimal α'_i s, we solve the optimization problem subject to the constraints defined in the set \mathcal{A} . This can be done with the help of MATLAB software.

3.4 Outdoor FSO System

For an outdoor FSO scenario, we consider a MIMO-FSO system with N transmit lasers/apertures and M photodetectors. The channel changes independently from one block to the next but remains constant during a fading block comprising of T channel usage. An $M \times N$ random matrix $textbf{H}$ represents the channel during a fading block l . In this work, we consider IM/DD technique for MIMO-FSO system employing LOS links. Therefore, all the coefficients of \mathbf{H} are assumed to be real and positive. The element of \mathbf{H} given by $h_{yz} \geq 0$ represents the channel gain between z^{th} ($z = 1, 2, \dots, N$) laser and y^{th} ($y = 1, 2, \dots, M$) photodetector. Let $\mathbf{X} \in \mathfrak{R}^{N \times T}$ and $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathfrak{R}^{M \times T}$ represent the transmitted and received codewords, respectively, then the received signal can be written in the matrix form as:

$$\mathbf{Y}_I = \sqrt{\frac{\tau}{N^2}} \mathbf{H}_I \mathbf{X}_I + \mathbf{E}_I, \quad (3.28)$$

where $\mathbf{E} \in \mathfrak{R}^{M \times T}$ denotes the AWGN matrix. Further, each element of \mathbf{E} is Gaussian distributed with zero mean and unity variance, $\tau = (\rho P_{avg})^2$ represents the average electrical SNR at each receiver aperture, where ρ is the responsivity of the PD, P_{avg} denotes the average received optical power.

We assume that the receiver has perfect knowledge of the channel matrix. We use the mathematical symbol \mathcal{I} to represent the random variable that represents the feedback index. Moreover, \mathcal{I} accepts values from the set $\{1, 2, \dots, K\}$, where K denotes the feedback resolution and is a positive integer. For a given channel condition, the receiver feedbacks the index $\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H})$ through a noiseless, zero-delay feedback link to the transmitter. The index mapping $\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H})$ corresponds to the partitioning of the set of all possible channel matrices into K number of quantized feedback regions. Furthermore, prior to the transmission, the channel matrix corresponding to a particular quantized region is exactly known to the transmitter. Depending upon the received feedback index $\mathcal{I}=i$ by the transmitter, the codeword \mathbf{X} is transmitted from a codebook $\mathbf{C}_i=\{\mathbf{X}_i(1), \mathbf{X}_i(2), \dots, \mathbf{X}_i(M_i)\}$ of rate R_i , where all codewords are uniformly drawn from the codebook. The $\mathbf{X}_i(k)$'s are matrices of size $N \times T$. Let us define

$$P_{\mathcal{I}=i} \triangleq \frac{1}{TM_i} \sum_{k=1}^{M_i} \|\mathbf{X}_i(k)\|_F^2, \quad (3.29)$$

where $\|\mathbf{X}\|_F$ denotes the Frobenius norm of matrix \mathbf{X} . Also, $P_{\mathcal{I}=i}$ is the average total transmit power corresponding to the event when the feedback index $\mathcal{I}=i$ is received by the transmitter. Moreover, we consider a power constraint [121,122] over infinitely many fading blocks as:

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \frac{1}{T} \|\mathbf{X}\|_F^2 = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{H}} [P_{\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H})}] \leq \tau, \quad (3.30)$$

where the first equality holds with probability one. Moreover, $\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H})$, and the codebooks \mathbf{C}_i 's are SNR dependent. Thus, P_i 's and R_i 's are also SNR dependent. We also focus on the average rate over infinitely many fading blocks

$$R \triangleq \lim_{L \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L R_{\mathcal{I}(H)} = \sum_{i=1}^K \Pr(\mathcal{I} = i) R_i \quad (3.31)$$

If r denote the multiplexing gain, then

$$r = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{R(\tau)}{\frac{1}{2} \log \tau}, \quad (3.32)$$

where $R(\tau) = \frac{r}{2} \log(\tau)$ is the target data rate for a given τ . However, the system is said to have a multiplexing gain of r , in an average sense, if

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{2R}{\log \tau} = \sum_{i=1}^K r_i \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \Pr(\mathcal{I} = i) = r. \quad (3.33)$$

Moreover, we consider two different scenarios of transmission as discussed below:

- **Single-rate transmission:** The transmission rate corresponding to each value of SNR is unaffected by the feedback index. Mathematically, it is constrained as:

$$r_1 = \dots = r_K = r, \quad (3.34)$$

where r_i 's, $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$ are referred to as the *individual multiplexing gains*.

- **Adaptive-rate transmission:** The values of r_1, \dots, r_K can be optimized subject to (3.33), i.e., a variable-rate MIMO-FSO system is considered. Mathematically, a constraint is also imposed as:

$$r_i \geq r_{\min}, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, K\} \quad (3.35)$$

where $0 \leq r_{\min} \leq \min(M, N)$ is a constant. We term it as the ‘minimum multiplexing gain’.

Remark 3.3: From (3.35), it can be inferred that an acceptable quality of service is only attained at a certain minimum rate. Furthermore, without considering (3.35), it is not possible to predict the outage, i.e., the event that a particular LOS link of a MIMO-FSO system cannot support the target data rate. However, (3.35) can also be imposed for the single-rate transmission, but in that case r_{\min} has no influence on the optimal DMT. On the other side, this does not hold for the adaptive-rate case, where r_{\min} significantly influences the optimal DMT.

Remark 3.4: Since we assume perfect CSIT in this work, therefore the proposed model is valid for even long distances (5-8 Km). As far as the strong turbulence effect is concerned, we consider negative exponential channel model (specific for strong turbulence conditions) and gamma-gamma channel model (with strong turbulence regime) in our results to ensure the validity of the proposed model for strong turbulence regime as well.

3.4.1 Channel Models

In this subsection, we provide different FSO channel models covering all the AT regimes. For simplifying the presentation, we drop indexes of the channel gains. In this work, the different FSO channel models under consideration are as follows:

1. Log-Normal Channel: This channel model is valid for weak AT regime. Under weak AT, the fading of optical signal is modelled as $h = \exp(g)$, where g is a normal random variable with mean and variance of μ_g and σ_g^2 , respectively [1]. Therefore, h follows the log-normal PDF which is given as:

$$f_h(h) = \frac{1}{h\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_g^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\ln(h) - \mu_g)^2}{2\sigma_g^2}\right), \quad (3.36)$$

Since the transmitted optical power is neither attenuated nor amplified by the turbulence, $\mathbb{E}(h)=1$ which requires $\mu_g = -\sigma_g^2/2$ [1, Eq.(3.115)]. Note that $\mathbb{E}(\cdot)$ denotes the expectation operator.

2. Gamma-Gamma Channel: Under moderate-to-strong AT regime, h is distributed as:

$$f_h(h) = \frac{(\alpha\beta)^{\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}}}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} h^{\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}-1} G_{0,2}^{2,0}\left(\alpha\beta h \left| \begin{array}{c} \cdot\cdot \\ \frac{\alpha-\beta}{2}, \frac{\beta-\alpha}{2} \end{array} \right.\right), \quad (3.37)$$

where α and β are the turbulence parameters meant for characterizing the irradiance fluctuations, which depend upon the log irradiance variance (σ_g^2). Further, $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function, and $G_{p,q}^{m,n}(\cdot)$ is the Meiger-G function [118, Subsection 2.24]. In this work, the parameter (α, β) is taken as (4.2,1.4) to model the strong AT regime.

3. Negative Exponential Channel: The negative exponential distribution is given by [1]:

$$f_h(h) = \exp(-h). \quad (3.38)$$

This channel model is valid only for modeling of saturation AT regime.

3.4.2 Fundamental Definitions

We also introduce fundamental definitions to characterize the optimal DMT of the outdoor FSO system.

- For any function of τ , $f(\tau)$, the following equality:

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log f(\tau)}{\log \tau} = v, \quad (3.39)$$

is denoted as $f(\tau) \doteq \tau^v$, where \doteq represents exponential equality. Symbols $\stackrel{\cdot}{\leq}$ and $\stackrel{\cdot}{\geq}$ are similarly defined.

- Let d_{out} denote the outage diversity gain, then

$$d_{out} = - \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log P_{out}(R, P_{\mathcal{I}})}{\log \tau}, \quad (3.40)$$

where $P_{out}(R, P_{\mathcal{I}})$ is the outage error probability. The supremum of the diversity gain achieved over all the feedback schemes for a particular r is denoted as $d^*(r)$.

- An outage-based scenario comes into account when the instantaneous channel capacity, $C(\mathbf{H}, P_{\mathcal{I}})$, is less than the target data rate, $R(\tau)$. Mathematically,

$$P_{out}(R, P_{\mathcal{I}}) \triangleq \Pr(C(\mathbf{H}, P_{\mathcal{I}}) < R(\tau)), \quad (3.41)$$

where the probability is defined over the random channel matrix \mathbf{H} . The capacity expression given in [119] is valid for an uninformed transmitter, whereas the expression given in (3.42) corresponds to the capacity of an informed transmitter.

$$C(\mathbf{H}, P_{\mathcal{I}}) \triangleq \frac{1}{2} \log_2 \left(\det (\mathbf{I}_M + \mathbf{H} \mathbf{L}_{\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H})} \mathbf{H}^T) \right), \quad (3.42)$$

where $\det(\cdot)$ denotes the determinant, and the identity matrix of size M is denoted as \mathbf{I}_M , and \mathbf{H}^T denotes the transpose of matrix \mathbf{H} . Since the channel gains are real in IM/DD FSO system, hence (3.42) contains \mathbf{H}^T instead of \mathbf{H}^\dagger , where \mathbf{H}^\dagger denotes hermitian of the matrix \mathbf{H} . Note that the maximization of the capacity is done over the total transmit power constraint, which depends upon the peak power of the input signal, and it is positive for an IM/DD FSO system. Moreover, $\{\mathbf{L}_i\}_{i=1}^K$ are the positive semidefinite matrices which correspond to the covariance matrices of the input to the channel depending upon the received feedback index ($\mathcal{I} = i$) by the transmitter.

- Moreover, we define

$$\begin{aligned}
m &\triangleq \max(M, N), \\
n &\triangleq \min(M, N), \\
d_{\max}^* &\triangleq d^*(0), \\
r_{\max}^* &\triangleq \sup \{r : d^*(r) > 0\},
\end{aligned}$$

where d_{\max}^* and r_{\max}^* are the maximal diversity gain and maximal spatial multiplexing gain respectively in the channel.

- The target data rate can be explicitly related to SNR as:

$$R_i = \frac{r_i}{2} \log \tau, \quad i = 1, \dots, K, \quad (3.43)$$

where the r_i s $\in (0, \min(M, N))$, independent of SNR.

3.5 DMT Analysis of Outdoor FSO System

An outage event can be considered as a scenario when the channel is so bad that no scheme can offer reliable communication at a certain fixed data rate. Thus, it motivates us to study the DMT for such a practical scenario. For an outage event and a given feedback scheme, the outage probability, which is also SNR dependent, is thus defined as:

$$P_{out,K} \triangleq \Pr \left(\frac{1}{2} \log_2 \left(\det \left(\mathbf{I}_M + \mathbf{H} \mathbf{L}_{\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H})} \mathbf{H}^T \right) \right) < R \right), \quad (3.44)$$

where $\Pr(\cdot)$ denotes the probability. As far as DMT is concerned, outage probability is quite related to our discussion because of the upper bound yielded by an application of Fano's inequality, similar to that in [30, Lemma 5].

$$P_e \dot{\geq} P_{out,K} \doteq \tau^{-d_{out,K}(r)} \geq \tau^{-d_{out,K}^*(r)}, \quad (3.45)$$

where P_e denotes the average probability of error corresponding to a transmitted code-word being incorrectly decoded at the receiver. Further, (3.45) is valid for any feedback scheme and any code of finite length T . Moreover, the SNR exponent of the minimum

outage probability P_{out}^* is denoted by $-d_{out,K}^*(r)$ (the optimal outage diversity order). Further, this SNR exponent is valid for all feedback schemes with feedback resolution K .

3.5.1 Single-Rate Transmission

Single-rate transmission is taken into account when the constraint (3.34) is imposed. In order to determine $d_{out,K}^*(r)$, a joint optimization over $\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H}), \{P_i\}_{i=1}^K$, and $\{\mathbf{L}_i\}_{i=1}^K$ is required. Moreover, $\text{Tr}(\mathbf{L}_i) \leq P_i$, where $\text{Tr}(\cdot)$ denotes the trace of \mathbf{L}_i . With $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, \mathbf{L}_i s are considered to be scaled identity matrices dependent on the partial CSIT and the SNR. For a given $\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H})$ and $\{P_i\}_{i=1}^K$, by choosing $\mathbf{L}_i = \frac{P_i}{N^2} \mathbf{I}_N, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, K\}$. Note that \mathbf{I}_N is a $N \times N$ identity matrix. Therefore, the different bounds on the outage probability are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log \Pr \left(\frac{1}{2} \log_2 \left(\det \left(\mathbf{I}_M + P_T \mathbf{H} \mathbf{H}^T \right) \right) < R \right)}{\log \tau}, \\ & \leq \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log P_{out,K}}{\log \tau}, \\ & \leq \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log \Pr \left(\frac{1}{2} \log_2 \left(\det \left(\mathbf{I}_M + \frac{P_T}{N^2} \mathbf{H} \mathbf{H}^T \right) \right) < R \right)}{\log \tau}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.46)$$

where $R = \frac{r}{2} \log \tau$.

Remark 3.5 : If power allocation for all the feedback schemes is done in such a way that $P_i \doteq \tau^{q_i}$ where $0 < q_i < \infty, \forall i$, it then follows from (3.46) that we can restrict the analysis to the case $\mathbf{L}_i = \frac{P_i}{N^2} \mathbf{I}_N, \forall i$. This motivates us to introduce the following lemma.

Lemma 3.1(Outage Minimization): The outage-minimizing power codebook $\{P_i^*\}_{i=1}^K$ corresponding to a given SNR and rate R solves the optimization problem

which is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \max P_K \\
& s.t. [P_{out}(R, P_K) + 1 - P_{out}(R, P_1)] P_1 \\
& \quad + \sum_{i=2}^K [P_{out}(R, P_{i-1}) + 1 - P_{out}(R, P_i)] P_i \leq \tau, \\
& 0 \leq P_1 < \dots < P_K
\end{aligned} \tag{3.47}$$

where $P_{out}(R, P_{\mathcal{I}})$ is defined as in (3.41). The optimal deterministic index mapping is given by

$$\mathcal{I}^*(\mathbf{H}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } C(\mathbf{H}, P_K^*) < R \\ \min \{i : i \in \{1, \dots, K\}, C(\mathbf{H}, P_i^*) \geq R\}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \tag{3.48}$$

where $C(\mathbf{H}, P_{\mathcal{I}})$ is defined by (3.42). The minimum outage probability is $P_{out}(R, P_K^*)$.

Proof: Refer to Appendix C for the proof.

Now we are left with determining the asymptotic SNR exponent of P_K^* that solves (3.47). At high SNR, most channels do not undergo outage, thus leading to a scenario wherein some quantization regions may have a power level with an SNR exponent strictly larger than one can be employed without violating (3.30). This motivates us to present the following lemma, which, given the asymptotic SNR exponent of the transmit power, calculates the SNR exponent of the outage probability.

Lemma 3.2(Outage Diversity Order): Let Λ be a function of SNR such that $\Lambda \doteq \text{SNR}^q$ where q is a finite constant and $q \geq 1$. For any $r \in (0, n)$, with $(x)^+ = \max(x, 0)$, we have

$$P_{out}(R, \Lambda) \doteq \text{SNR}^{-J_i(r, q)},$$

where $P_{out}(R, \Lambda)$ is defined as in (3.41) and $J_i(r, q)$ is the outage diversity order, given by

$$\begin{aligned}
J_1(r, q) &\triangleq \left\{ \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(|m-n| + 2i - 1)}{2} \alpha_i - \frac{3mn\alpha_n}{4} + \frac{mn\alpha_n^2}{8\sigma_g^2} \log \tau \right\}, \\
J_2(r, q) &\triangleq \left\{ \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(|m-n| + 2i - 1)}{2} \alpha_i + \frac{mn\alpha_n}{2} (\beta - 1) \right\}, \\
J_3(r, q) &\triangleq \left\{ \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(|m-n| + 2i - 1)}{2} \alpha_i \right\}, \tag{3.49}
\end{aligned}$$

where $J_i(r, q)$, $i = 1, \dots, 3$, is the outage diversity order corresponding to log-normal channel, gamma-gamma channel and negative exponential channel.

and

$$\mathcal{A} \triangleq \left\{ \alpha : \alpha_1 \geq \dots \geq \alpha_n \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^n (q - \alpha_i)^+ \leq r \right\}.$$

Here, α_i s indicate the level of singularity of channel matrix \mathbf{H} . The larger the α_i s are, the more singular \mathbf{H} is. Further, the set \mathcal{A} describes the outage event in terms of singularity levels.

Proof: $J_1(r, q)$, $J_2(r, q)$ and $J_3(r, q)$ are derived in [31]. Further, on substituting (3.42) into (3.41), and applying eigenvalue decomposition of $\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^T$, we get

$$P_{out}(R, \Lambda) \triangleq \Pr \left(\sum_{k=1}^n \log \left(1 + \frac{\Lambda}{N} \lambda_k \right) < R \right),$$

where $\lambda_1 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_n$ are the real and non-negative eigen values of $\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^T$. By applying change of variables $\lambda_k = \text{SNR}^{-\alpha_k}$, $k = 1, \dots, n$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{out}(R, q) &\doteq \Pr \left(\prod_{k=1}^n \text{SNR}^{(q-\alpha_k)^+} < \text{SNR}^r \right) \\
&= \Pr \left(\sum_{k=1}^n (q - \alpha_k)^+ < r \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Moreover, the region \mathcal{A} only contains $\alpha_k \geq 0, \forall k$, since outside this region, the outage probability decays exponentially as $\text{SNR} \rightarrow \infty$.

For a single-rate MIMO-FSO system, we define the following proposition which recursively defines the SNR exponent of the minimum outage probability (optimal outage diversity order) using quantized feedback.

Proposition 3.1: The optimal DMT of a single-rate MIMO-FSO system with K quantization regions in the feedback link is upper-bounded by the outage bound

$$d_{out,K}^*(r) = J(r, 1 + d_{out,K-1}^*(r)), \quad (3.50)$$

where $d_{out,0}^*(r) \triangleq 0, \forall r$.

Proof: Refer to Appendix D for the proof.

$J(r, q)$ is defined as in (3.49) according to the channel model. When asymptotic scenario is taken into account, mostly the channel is not in outage, and hence the transmit power $P_1 = \tau$ is used. So, these “good” channel conditions are mapped to $\mathcal{I}=1$ (first quantization region). On the other side, the set of “bad” channel conditions in outage if P_1 is applied, results in a probability measure in the order of $\tau^{-J(r,1)}$ are mapped to $\mathcal{I}=2$ (second quantization region). Thus, for the bad channel conditions, we may use a power P_2 in the order of $\tau^{1+J(r,1)}$ without violating (3.30). However, this leads to an outage probability in the order of $\tau^{-J(r,1+J(r,1))}$. We provide a proof given in Appendix D, that computes a lower bound and an upper bound on $d_{out,K}^*(r)$. The lower bound is obtained by choosing

$$P_1 = \frac{\tau}{K}, P_2 = \frac{\tau}{K P_{out}(R, P_1)}, \dots, P_K = \frac{\tau}{K P_{out}(R, P_{K-1})}. \quad (3.51)$$

It follows from (3.51) that we can employ the following index mapping together with the power codebook $\{P_i\}_{i=1}^K$ in order to attain the outage bound:

$$\mathcal{I}^*(\mathbf{H}) = \begin{cases} K, & \text{if } C(\mathbf{H}, P_K) < R \\ \min \{i : i \in \{1, \dots, K\}, C(\mathbf{H}, P_i) \geq R\}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3.52)$$

Corollary 3.1: For a single-rate based MIMO-FSO system, we have

(a) Log-Normal Channel:

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} d_{out,K}^*(r) = \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{N_t N_r}{2} - \frac{3}{4} N_t N_r + \frac{N_t N_r}{8\sigma_g^2} \log(\tau)^k$$

As $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, $\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} d_{out,K}^*(r) = \infty, \forall K$,

and

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow n} d_{out,K}^*(r) = \infty, \forall K.$$

(b) Gamma-Gamma Channel:

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} d_{out,K}^*(r) = \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\frac{NM \min(\alpha, \beta)}{2} \right)^k$$

and

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow n} d_{out,K}^*(r) = 0, \forall K.$$

(c) Negative Exponential Channel:

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} d_{out,K}^*(r) = \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\frac{NM}{2} \right)^k$$

and

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow n} d_{out,K}^*(r) = 0, \forall K.$$

Proof: We consider the negative exponential channel for the illustration purpose and on similar lines, the proof for the other channel models can be established. For r sufficiently close to zero and any $q \geq 1$, (3.49) is minimized by $\alpha_i^* = q, i=1, \dots, n-1$, and $\alpha_n^* = q - r$ leading to $\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} J(r, q) = \left(\frac{NMq}{2} \right)$. Applying Proposition 1, we obtain

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} d_{out,K}^*(r) = \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\frac{NM}{2} \right)^k, \forall K.$$

Moreover, it can also be verified that $\lim_{r \rightarrow n} J(r, 1) = 0$, Using Proposition 1 gives

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow n} d_{out,K}^*(r) = 0, \forall K.$$

Remark 3.6: A significant conclusion that can be drawn from corollary 1 is the impact of partial CSIT in the MIMO-FSO system, which is much more as compared to the SISO-FSO system. This is because, over a SISO channel, the optimal diversity gain has a linear proportionality to K .

3.5.2 Adaptive-Rate Transmission

Under the well-behaved channel conditions, rate adaptation is significant for transmitting more information. For an adaptive-rate based MIMO-FSO system, one may try to perform the joint optimization (optimal power and rate allocation) corresponding to each SNR. However, it is a tedious task, even in the SISO case with perfect CSIT. Thus, we provide an alternative method and find an upper bound on the outage bound itself, and which allows us to reuse the results of the single-rate transmission.

Proposition 3.2: The optimal DMT of an adaptive-rate MIMO-FSO system with $K \geq 2$ quantization regions in the feedback link and a minimum multiplexing gain r_{\min} , where $r_{\min} \in (0, n)$, and $r \in [r_{\min}, n)$ is upper-bounded by the outage bound

$$d_{out,K}^*(r, r_{\min}) = J(r_{\min}, 1 + d_{out,K-1}^*(r, r_{\min})),$$

where $d_{out,1}^*(r, r_{\min}) \triangleq J(r, 1), \forall r \geq r_{\min}$.

Proof: Refer to Appendix E for the proof

Efficient rate adaptation relies on the proper tracking and prediction of the channel at the transmitter. By performing the joint optimization, the outage bound is obtained by considering a two-rate system. As far as the rate corresponding to a particular quantization region is concerned, the rate of one quantization region dominates the average multiplexing gain of the system in asymptotic conditions. Moreover, power control is employed over the rest $K - 1$ quantized feedback regions. However, minimum rate is employed for these $K - 1$ quantized feedback regions. The alternative approach introduced for the adaptive-rate problem employs an optimal combination of channel inversion and water-filling to reduce outage and improve throughput, respectively [22].

At very high SNR, this alternative approach reduces to channel inversion alone, resulting in a similar structure to the single-rate transmission case. Further, as $\tau \rightarrow \infty$ the effect of water-filling has almost no effect.

Corollary 3.2: For an adaptive-rate based MIMO-FSO system, in the extreme conditions, when $r_{\min} \rightarrow 0$ and $K \geq 2$, a simple outage bound can be obtained

(a) Log-Normal Channel:

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{r_{\min} \rightarrow 0} d_{out,K}^*(r, r_{\min}) &= \left(\frac{NM}{2} - \frac{3}{4}NM + \frac{NM}{8\sigma_g^2} \log(\tau) \right)^{K-1} \times J(r, 1) \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \left(\frac{NM}{2} - \frac{3}{4}NM + \frac{NM}{8\sigma_g^2} \log(\tau)^k \right). \end{aligned}$$

(b) Gamma-Gamma Channel:

$$\lim_{r_{\min} \rightarrow 0} d_{out,K}^*(r, r_{\min}) = \left(\frac{NM \min(\alpha, \beta)}{2} \right)^{K-1} \times J(r, 1) + \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \left(\frac{NM \min(\alpha, \beta)}{2} \right)^k.$$

(c) Negative Exponential Channel:

$$\lim_{r_{\min} \rightarrow 0} d_{out,K}^*(r, r_{\min}) = \left(\frac{NM}{2} \right)^{K-1} + \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \left(\frac{NM}{2} \right)^k.$$

The proof is almost identical to that of corollary 1 and therefore omitted for brevity.

Remark 3.7: We have provided an alternative approach to an adaptive-rate problem where joint optimization (optimal power and rate allocation) is a challenging task. To counter this problem, a simple outage bound for the different channel models covering all the AT regimes is given.

3.6 Results And Discussion

In this section, we present and discuss the numerical results derived in the previous sections. Moreover, we will investigate different system configurations to determine which system provides the optimal DMT.

Figure 3.2: Asymptotic outage probability versus SNR plots for $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 60^\circ$ and different multiplexing gains for a 4×4 MIMO-VLC system.

3.6.1 DMT of Indoor VLC System

In Fig. 3.2, we plot in the outage performance plots for a 4×4 MIMO-VLC system. The main objective of giving these plots is to show the outage performance for different indoor VLC scenarios. We use (3.26) to obtain the outage probability versus SNR plots. It can be seen from (3.26) that the outage probability mainly depends on the parameters, such as half-power angle, multiplexing gain and the optimal α'_i 's of the 4×4 MIMO channel matrix. To obtain the optimal α'_i 's, we solve the optimization problem subject to the constraints defined in the set \mathcal{A} . This can be done with the help of MATLAB software. It can be clearly seen from the figure that as the multiplexing gain increases, the outage performance deteriorates.

Figure 3.3 shows the optimal DMT curves for a SISO-VLC ($M = N = 1$) system. We use (3.18) to plot these optimal DMT curves. From (3.18), it is clear that the optimal outage diversity gain, $d_{out}^*(r)$ is dependent on the multiplexing gain (r) and the order of Lambertian emission (L_o). However, the latter instead depends on the half-power angle ($\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}}$) of the LED Tx. Therefore, we provide the optimal DMT curves for

Figure 3.3: Optimal DMT curves for SISO-VLC system.

different values of $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}}$. For $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 20^\circ$, the optimal outage diversity gain, $d_{out}^*(0) \approx 1$, is attained at a minimum multiplexing gain ($r = 0$). However, the optimal outage diversity gain, $d_{out}^*(1) = 0$, at a maximum multiplexing gain ($r = Z = 1$) for a SISO-VLC system. This shows the optimal tradeoff between the diversity gain and the multiplexing gain. For $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 40^\circ$ and $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 60^\circ$, $d_{out}^*(0) \approx 1.2$ and 1.25 , respectively.

Observation 3.1: The slight increase in the optimal diversity gain for a SISO-VLC system is due to the increase in the half-power angle ($\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}}$) of the LED transmitter.

In Fig. 3.4, the optimal DMT curves are plotted for a 4×4 MIMO-VLC system. We use (3.27) to plot these optimal DMT curves. From (3.27), it is clear that the optimal outage diversity gain $d_{out}^*(r)$ not only depends on the half-power angle ($\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}}$), but also the optimal α'_i 's of the channel matrix. For $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 20^\circ$, the optimal outage diversity gain, $d_{out}^*(0) \approx 17$, is attained at a minimum multiplexing gain ($r = 0$), as shown in Fig. 4. However, the optimal outage diversity gain of $d_{out}^*(4) = 0$ is obtained at a maximum multiplexing gain ($r = Z = 4$) for a 4×4 MIMO-VLC system. Further, it can be seen from the figure that for $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 40^\circ$ and $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 60^\circ$, $d_{out}^*(0) \approx 19$ and 20 , respectively.

Figure 3.4: Optimal DMT curves for 4×4 MIMO-VLC system.

Observation 3.2: The optimal DMT corresponding to 4×4 MIMO-VLC system is significantly better as compared to the SISO-VLC system.

Figure 3.5 shows optimal DMT curves for an 8×8 MIMO-VLC system. It can be seen from the figure that for $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 20^\circ$, the optimal outage diversity gain of $d_{out}^*(0) \approx 70$, is attained at a minimum multiplexing gain ($r = 0$). However, the optimal outage diversity gain, $d_{out}^*(8) = 0$, is attained at a maximum multiplexing gain ($r = Z = 8$) for a 8×8 MIMO-VLC system. Further, for $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 40^\circ$ and $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 60^\circ$, it is shown in the figure that $d_{out}^*(0) \approx 75$ and 80 , respectively. As far as the comparison of optimal DMT of 8×8 and 4×4 MIMO-VLC system is concerned, the 8×8 MIMO-VLC system provides a significant improvement in the optimal DMT.

Observation 3.3: The significant improvement in the optimal DMT of an 8×8 MIMO-VLC system is due to the larger number of independent propagation paths. Besides, the dependency of the outage diversity gain on the half-power angle of the LED transmitter and the optimal α'_i s of the 8×8 MIMO channel matrix is another reason for this significant improvement.

In Fig. 3.6, the optimal DMT curves are plotted for a 2×4 ($N \times M$) MIMO-VLC

Figure 3.5: Optimal DMT curves for 8×8 MIMO-VLC system.

system. It can be seen from the figure that for $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 20^\circ$, the optimal outage diversity gain of $d_{out}^*(0) \approx 8.5$, is attained at a minimum multiplexing gain ($r = 0$). However, the optimal outage diversity gain, $d_{out}^*(2) = 0$, is attained at a maximum multiplexing gain ($r = Z = 2$) for a 2×4 MIMO-VLC system. Further, for $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 40^\circ$ and $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}} = 60^\circ$, it is shown in the figure that $d_{out}^*(0) \approx 9.5$ and 10 , respectively.

Observation 3.4: If we compare the DMT performance curves of 2×4 ($N \times M$) and 4×4 ($M \times M$) MIMO-VLC systems, it is observed that 4×4 MIMO-VLC system provides significantly better DMT performance. It is mainly because of the larger number of independent propagation paths offered by a 4×4 MIMO-VLC system. Note that the outage diversity gains corresponding to different values of $\Phi_{\frac{1}{2}}$ for a 2×4 MIMO-VLC system are almost half as compared to the 4×4 MIMO-VLC system.

3.6.2 DMT of Outdoor FSO System

It is discussed in the previous sections that the log-normal channel is used for modelling of low AT regime. The typical value of σ_g taken for a FSO system is less than one. Further, to model the strong AT regime in case of gamma-gamma channel, the

Figure 3.6: Optimal DMT curves for 2×4 ($N \times M$) MIMO-VLC system.

parameter (α, β) is taken as $(4.2, 1.4)$, as given in [1]. We compare our results with the no-CSIT-based MIMO-FSO DMT [31] to validate the outcomes of our proposed model.

In Fig. 3.7, the optimal DMT curves for single-rate and adaptive-rate based 2×2 MIMO-FSO system with a near-zero minimum multiplexing gain ($r_{\min} = 0.001$) are compared. We first compare the optimal DMT curves for a single-rate MIMO-FSO system employing negative exponential channel model with different values of feedback resolution (K). For $K = 2$, it can be seen from Fig. 3.7 that the maximum optimal diversity gain that can be attained is given as $d_{out,K}^*(0) = 6$. The minimum diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(2) = 0$, at a maximum multiplexing gain given by $r_{\max}^* = \min(N, M) = 2$, for a 2×2 MIMO-FSO system. This minimum diversity gain is due to the optimal tradeoff between the diversity gain and the multiplexing gain. For $K = 3$, the maximum optimal diversity gain that can be attained is given as $d_{out,K}^*(0) = 14$ (a drastic increase). Now, we compare the DMT curves for an adaptive-rate based 2×2 MIMO-FSO system with different values of feedback resolution. It can be clearly seen from the figure that for an adaptive-rate based 2×2 MIMO-FSO system, the

Figure 3.7: Optimal DMT of single-rate and adaptive-rate ($r_{\min} = 0.001$) transmission over a 2×2 negative exponential MIMO-FSO channel with different feedback resolution K .

maximum optimal diversity gain for $K = 2$ and $K = 3$ is same as that of the single-rate based 2×2 MIMO-FSO system, i.e., $d_{out,K}^*(0)$ is same for $K = 2$ and $K = 3$, respectively. However, for $K = 2$, the minimum optimal diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(2) = 2$ (nonzero). Further, for $K = 3$, the minimum optimal diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(2) = 6$. So, we observe that in both the cases of $K = 2$ and $K = 3$, the minimum diversity gain is nonzero for an adaptive-rate based MIMO-FSO system. Additionally, there is a significant improvement in the achievement of the minimum optimal diversity gain due to the adaptive-rate based transmission. We also consider the case of $K = 1$ (no-CSIT). Even with this considered scenario of no-CSIT [31], we attain a finite optimal diversity gain given as $d_{out,K}^*(0) = 2$.

Figure 3.8 illustrates the comparison of optimal DMT curves for single-rate and adaptive-rate based 2×2 MIMO-FSO system employing gamma-gamma channel model with a near-zero minimum multiplexing gain ($r_{\min} = 0.001$). Further, we consider the strong AT scenario. We first consider the case of single-rate based 2×2 MIMO-FSO

Figure 3.8: Optimal DMT of single-rate and adaptive-rate ($r_{\min} = 0.001$) transmission over a 2×2 gamma-gamma MIMO-FSO channel with different feedback resolution K .

system to compare the DMT curves with different values of feedback resolution (K). For $K = 2$, the maximum optimal diversity gain that can be achieved is given as $d_{out,K}^*(0) \approx 11$. The minimum diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(2) = 0$, at a maximum multiplexing gain given by $r_{\max}^* = \min(N, M) = 2$, for a 2×2 MIMO-FSO system. For $K = 3$, the maximum optimal diversity gain that can be achieved is given as $d_{out,K}^*(0) \approx 33$ (a drastic increase). Now, we compare the DMT curves for an adaptive-rate based 2×2 MIMO-FSO system for different values of K . It is quite clear from the figure that for an adaptive-rate transmission, the maximum optimal diversity gain for $K = 2$ and $K = 3$ is same as that of the single-rate based transmission. On the other side, for $K = 2$, the minimum optimal diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(2) = 3$ (more as compared to the negative exponential channel model). Further, for $K = 3$, the minimum optimal diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(2) \approx 11$ (same as that of the maximum optimal diversity gain of single-rate and adaptive-rate 2×2 system with $K = 2$). Additionally, we consider the case of no-CSIT ($K = 1$). This scenario of CSI attains a finite optimal diversity gain of $d_{out,K}^*(0) = 3$ (more as compared to the

Figure 3.9: Optimal DMT of single-rate and adaptive-rate ($r_{\min} = 0.001$) transmission over a 2×2 log-normal MIMO-FSO channel with different feedback resolution K .

negative exponential channel model).

Observation 3.5: In Figs. 3.7 and 3.8, it can be observed that the DMT performance corresponding to the proposed technique/model in this work is significantly better as compared to the no-CSIT case [31]. This is because [31] does not employ any CSIT dependent power and rate control technique. Moreover, the improved DMT performance is valid for both single-rate as well as adaptive-rate transmission. The main differences between Figs. 3.7 and 3.8 are: 1) Fig. 3.7 shows the DMT performance of a 2×2 negative exponential MIMO-FSO channel whereas Fig. 3.8 shows the DMT performance of a 2×2 gamma-gamma MIMO-FSO channel. 2) The DMT performance of gamma-gamma MIMO-FSO channel is significantly better as compared to the negative exponential MIMO-FSO channel for both single-rate as well as adaptive-rate transmission scenarios.

Figure 3.9 illustrates the comparison of optimal DMT curves for single-rate and adaptive-rate based 2×2 MIMO-FSO system employing log-normal channel model with a near-zero minimum multiplexing gain ($r_{\min} = 0.001$). It can be clearly seen

Figure 3.10: Optimal DMT for adaptive-rate transmission over a 4×4 negative exponential MIMO-FSO channel with minimum multiplexing gain $r_{\min} = 0.001, 1, 2, 3$.

from the figure that the maximum optimal diversity gain obtained is infinite, $\forall r$ for single-rate as well as adaptive-rate system. However, this infinite diversity gain is valid only for weak turbulence regime, since the log-normal channel model is valid for weak turbulence regime. This achievement does not hold for strong and moderate turbulence regimes. Hence, this is the limitation of the log-normal channel model. Furthermore, for certain values of α and β , the gamma-gamma channel model reduces to log-normal channel model. So, it is almost redundant to discuss the optimal tradeoff for the log-normal channel in the subsequent discussion. Therefore, from now onwards, the main focus would be on the negative exponential and gamma-gamma channel models which covers the entire turbulence regime (weak to strong). Moreover, the detailed description related to the limitation of the log-normal channel in terms of accuracy can be found in [1].

In Fig. 3.10, the optimal DMT curves for an adaptive-rate based 4×4 MIMO-FSO system employing negative exponential channel model with different values of r_{\min} are compared. The different values of r_{\min} are taken as $r_{\min} = 0.001, 1, 2, 3$.

Moreover, we consider $K = 2$. For $r_{\min} = 0.001$, the maximum optimal diversity gain that can be attained by an adaptive-rate based 4×4 MIMO-FSO system is given as $d_{out,K}^*(0, 0.001) = 72$. The minimum optimal diversity gain that can be attained is given as $d_{out,K}^*(4, 0.001) = 8$, at a maximum multiplexing gain given by $r_{\max}^* = \min(N, M) = 4$, for a 4×4 MIMO-FSO system. For $r_{\min} = 1$, the maximum optimal diversity gain that can be attained is given as $d_{out,K}^*(0, 1) = 72$ (same as that attained with $r_{\min} = 0.001$). However, the minimum optimal diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(4, 1) = 6$. For $r_{\min} = 2$, the maximum optimal diversity gain achieved by the considered system is given as $d_{out,K}^*(0, 2) = 68$, whereas the minimum optimal diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(4, 2) = 4$. Further, with $r_{\min} = 3$, the maximum attainable optimal diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(0, 3) = 66$, and the minimum optimal diversity gain that can be attained is given as $d_{out,K}^*(4, 3) = 2$. Moreover, we also compare the adaptive-rate based optimal DMT scenario with the optimal DMT curve corresponding to the no-CSIT [31] scenario. It is observed that when no-CSIT scenario is considered, the 4×4 MIMO-FSO system employing negative exponential channel model is efficient enough to provide an optimum maximum diversity gain of $d_{out,1}^*(0) = 8$.

Figure 3.11 illustrates the comparison of optimal DMT curves for an adaptive-rate based 4×4 MIMO-FSO system employing gamma-gamma channel model with different values of r_{\min} , and $K = 2$. For $r_{\min} = 0.001$, the maximum optimal diversity gain that can be attained by an adaptive-rate based 4×4 MIMO-FSO system is given as $d_{out,K}^*(0, 0.001) \approx 137$. The minimum optimal diversity gain that can be attained is given as $d_{out,K}^*(4, 0.001) \approx 12$, at a maximum multiplexing gain given by $r_{\max}^* = \min(N, M) = 4$ for a 4×4 MIMO-FSO system. For $r_{\min} = 1$, the maximum optimal diversity gain that can be attained is given as $d_{out,2}^*(0, 1) \approx 134$. However, the minimum optimal diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(4, 1) \approx 9$. For $r_{\min} = 2$, the maximum optimal diversity gain achieved by the considered system is given as $d_{out,K}^*(0, 2) \approx 129$, whereas the minimum optimal diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(4, 2) \approx 6$. Further, with $r_{\min} = 3$, the maximum attainable optimal diversity gain is given as $d_{out,K}^*(0, 3) \approx 128$, and the minimum optimal diversity gain that can be attained is given as $d_{out,K}^*(4, 3) = 3$. Furthermore, when no-CSIT [31] scenario is considered, the 4×4 MIMO-FSO system

Figure 3.11: Optimal DMT for adaptive-rate transmission over a 4×4 gamma-gamma MIMO-FSO channel with minimum multiplexing gain $r_{\min} = 0.001, 1, 2, 3$.

employing gamma-gamma channel model is efficient enough to provide an optimal maximum diversity gain of $d_{out,1}^*(0) \approx 12$.

Remark 3.8: The discussion related to Figs. 3.10 and 3.11 reflect some useful insights. First, the reliability degrades as a result of raising the individual rate minimum threshold. However, it should not be taken as granted that a small r_{\min} is preferable. It can be clearly seen from the figures that the optimal DMT with very coarse feedback ($K = 2$) is far better than the no-CSIT case [21]. Second, the optimal DMT curves of the gamma-gamma channel model outperforms the optimal DMT curves of the negative exponential channel model by providing a drastic increase in the diversity gain for all different values of r_{\min} . Third, when the no-CSIT scenario is considered, even then the optimal DMT of the gamma-gamma channel model outperforms the optimal DMT of negative exponential channel model.

3.7 Conclusions

We have investigated the DMT for the OWC systems. To this end, we mainly focused on indoor VLC and outdoor FSO systems. For the DMT investigation of the indoor VLC system, we considered the random radial movement of the end-user in the proposed system model. The optimal DMT for both the SISO and MIMO VLC systems have been analyzed. Novel analytical expressions for the PDF, outage probability, and outage diversity order for the SISO-VLC and MIMO-VLC systems have been derived. Moreover, we extend our study to the outdoor FSO system. For the first time, a limited feedback-based DMT is investigated for the FSO system under different transmission scenarios. To this end, we considered a MIMO-FSO setup and investigated the DMT for single-rate and adaptive-rate transmission scenarios. We have developed the optimal DMT of the MIMO-FSO system in terms of the outage upper bound in both scenarios (single-rate and adaptive-rate) by performing combined power and rate control. From the numerical results, we have observed that the optimal DMT for MIMO-VLC systems is significantly better compared to the SISO-VLC systems. This is mainly because of two reasons. Firstly, the MIMO-VLC system offers multiple independent propagation paths. Secondly, the optimal outage diversity gain in the case of the MIMO-VLC system not only depends on the half-power angle of the LED transmitter, but also the optimal singular values of the channel matrix. Further, for the outdoor FSO system, it has been observed that the DMT corresponding to the proposed CSIT-based technique is significantly better compared to the case of no-CSIT.

Chapter 4

Modeling of Outdoor V2V-VLC System Under Dynamic Scenarios

In this chapter, a dynamic V2V-VLC model is proposed for two real-time scenarios. In scenario 1, the deterministic longitudinal separation between two communicating vehicles and the random lateral shift/movement of vehicles are taken into consideration. On the other hand, in scenario 2, lateral shift of vehicles is considered to be predictable, while longitudinal/inter-vehicle separation between two vehicles is considered to be random. Additionally, we evaluate the proposed V2V-VLC model's performance in terms of various metrics while taking a cutting-edge channel model into account. We obtain new analytical closed-form expressions for ABER, outage probability, and path loss. This work, for the first time, examines the diversity property of the V2V-VLC system based on the derived ABER expressions corresponding to the two V2V-VLC scenarios. Moreover, the proposed V2V-VLC model is also analyzed considering the adverse challenges of V2V-VLC.

4.1 Introduction

V2V-VLC has nowadays become an essential component of the next-generation-based ITSs in outdoor scenarios as part of the 5G wireless networks [11], [12]. V2V communication enables two communicating vehicles to communicate the following information

Publications based on this chapter are [J3],[J5] and [C3].

to improve road safety: (i) Collision warning, (ii) Braking and speed, (iii) Lane departure and direction of travel, etc.

In [39], the idea of automotive lighting in ITSs is proposed by merging VLC and visible light positioning, taking into consideration the prior studies on vehicular VLC. In [40], a VLC-based simulation model for automotive applications is suggested. A proposal for an environment-adaptive Rx to increase communication effectiveness for automotive applications is made in [41]. In [42], a new non-stationary RS-GBSM for vehicular VLC channels is suggested. A thorough channel simulation is done in [43] to determine the impact of rain and fog on a V2V-VLC link. The authors of [44] examined several precoding and equalisation strategies for a 2×2 MIMO-based V2V-VLC system. It should be noted that precoding is a method that takes use of transmission variability by weighting the information stream. In [45], a 3-D massive MIMO-based channel model for V2V communications is put forward. The authors made a spherical wavefront assumption rather than the plane wavefront assumption that is typical of the traditional MIMO channel model [45]. In [46], a V2V-VLC simulation-based channel modelling is recently presented. Moreover, various path loss expressions are suggested, and their comparative analysis is examined [46]. A multi-hop relay-based routing algorithm and a prediction-based channel gain model are suggested for V2V-VLC networks in [49]. For V2V communications, a geometry-based stochastic channel model was recently put forth in [51].

Now, we outline the importance of the proposed V2V-VLC model by highlighting the following points:

- Vehicles dynamically change positions according to their speed, the layout of the road, and other nearby parked or moving cars in a practical V2V-VLC scenario. Due to the limited transmission range of VLC, this dynamic environment has a substantial impact on the performance of the V2V-VLC link. Consequently, it is crucial to provide accurate system modeling as part of ITSs by taking into account the actual characteristics such as random mobility and random path loss.
- Modeling the combined impact of path loss and AT is essential to understand how the outdoor environment will affect the V2V-VLC system under consideration.

In light of the aforementioned discussion, we note that the majority of the literature on V2V-VLC concentrated on the channel modelling aspect rather than the thorough modeling of the V2V-VLC system. Due to this, we stress in this chapter the thorough modelling of a V2V-VLC system under practical considerations that have not yet been addressed in the literature. **The chapter has the following contributions:**

- A two-lane road-based V2V-VLC model under two practical scenarios (as highlighted in the beginning of the chapter) is proposed. The proposed model is analyzed considering the impact of the different outdoor weather conditions.
- Moreover, a novel channel model is taken into consideration to include the combined effect of path loss and AT. Note that the V2V-VLC system is significantly impacted by path loss.
- The vehicle's lateral movement and longitudinal separation is modeled as random with a specific PDF. Consequently, in this work, a more realistic and generalised approach is employed to take into consideration the lateral shift and longitudinal separation of the vehicle. This is in contrast to the existing literature, which considers deterministic lateral shift and longitudinal separation.
- We model the reflections from the road surface and the LOS blocking with a corresponding path loss and see how these affect the proposed model.
- Several performance measures, including path loss, outage probability, ABER, and diversity property, are used to analyse the performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model for the considered scenarios. We develop new closed-form formulations for ABER, outage probability, and path loss. This work, for the first time, examines the diversity property of the V2V-VLC system based on the derived ABER expressions corresponding to the two V2V-VLC scenarios. More research is done into how various real-time outdoor propagation environment affect the proposed V2V-VLC LOS and NLOS models.

Table 4.1: Important system parameters

W_L	Width of single lane
W_v	Width of vehicle
d	Longitudinal separation between two communicating vehicles
d_h	Lateral movement of the vehicle
ϕ_1 and ϕ_2	Angles of irradiance w.r.t transmitter 1 (Tx1) and transmitter 2 (Tx2)
θ_1 and θ_2	Angles of incidence w.r.t Tx1 and Tx2
L_i	Propagation distance from the i^{th} Tx
Ψ	FOV angle of the Rx
D_R	Aperture diameter of the Rx

4.2 Preliminaries

We focus on the V2V-VLC system and channel models in this section.

4.2.1 System Model

As shown in Fig. 4.1, a two-lane road-based V2V-VLC model is proposed. The two communicating vehicles are in lanes 1 and 2, as may be seen in Fig. 4.1. The transmitters (Tx) are the backlights of the leading vehicle, and the receiver (Rx), which is a PD, is placed at the bumper of the following vehicle in lane 2. All the significant system parameters are summarised in Table 4.1. Considering Fig. 4.1, $\phi_1 = \theta_1$ and $\phi_2 = \theta_2$. The lateral shift w.r.t. i^{th} Tx is given as $d_{h_i} \triangleq d_h \pm \frac{W_v}{2}$, $i = 1, 2$. Also, the uninterrupted propagation distance (see Fig. 4.1) for the i^{th} angle is given as $L_i \triangleq \sqrt{d^2 + d_{h_i}^2}$. Since L_i is dependent on d_{h_i} , the incidence angle and d_{h_i} can be related as:

$$\theta_i = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{d}{L_i} \right). \quad (4.1)$$

Figure 4.1: Proposed two-lane road-based V2V-VLC model.

It can be seen from the proposed V2V-VLC model in Fig. 4.1 that d_h changes between 0 and $(2W_L - W_v)$. In other words, d_h is a random variable with a range of values from 0 to $(2W_L - W_v)$. It can be expressed mathematically as follows *:

$$0 \leq d_h \leq (2W_L - W_v). \quad (4.2)$$

For the Rx with a FOV (Ψ), detection of the LOS signals will take place when the following condition is satisfied:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos(\theta_i) &\geq \cos(\Psi), \\ \therefore L_i &\leq \frac{d}{\cos(\Psi)}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

Substituting the geometric relation of L_i into (4.3), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} d_{h_i}^2 &\leq d^2 \left(\frac{1 - \cos^2(\Psi)}{\cos^2(\Psi)} \right), \\ \therefore d_{h_i} &\leq d \tan(\Psi). \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

*For a specific lane and vehicle width as shown in (4.2), d_h is taken to be random within a range. Moreover, d_h varies slowly during a short period of time T within the prescribed range due to the mobility of other nearby vehicles.

Also, we have:

$$d_{h_i} = d_h \pm \frac{W_v}{2}. \quad (4.5)$$

Now, using (4.4) and (4.5), we obtain:

$$\left(d_h \pm \frac{W_v}{2}\right) \leq d \tan(\Psi). \quad (4.6)$$

Moreover, considering (4.6), the following holds:

- For d_{h_1} :

$$\begin{aligned} d_h - \frac{W_v}{2} &\leq d \tan(\Psi), \\ \Rightarrow d_h &\leq d \tan(\Psi) + \frac{W_v}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.7)$$

Thus when (4.7) is satisfied, L_1 , is detected by the Rx.

- For d_{h_2} :

$$\begin{aligned} d_h + \frac{W_v}{2} &\leq d \tan(\Psi), \\ \Rightarrow d_h &\leq d \tan(\Psi) - \frac{W_v}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

If (4.8) is met, L_2 , is detected by the Rx. Combining (4.7) and (4.8) together, we get:

$$d_h \leq d \tan(\Psi) \pm \frac{W_v}{2}. \quad (4.9)$$

4.2.2 Channel Model and Detection

Considering Fig. 4.1, the received signal is given by:

$$y = \rho \sum_{i=1}^2 h_i x + e, \quad (4.10)$$

where y denotes the received signal, ρ is the PD's responsivity, $x \geq 0$ denotes the non-negative visible-light signal corresponding to the two Tx's, and e denotes the AWGN. Moreover, h_i is the real-valued channel coefficient of the link between i^{th} Tx and the Rx, and it can be modeled as:

$$h_i = h_{a_i} (h_i^{PL})^{avg}, \quad (4.11)$$

where h_{a_i} models the AT and $(h_i^{PL})^{avg}$ denotes the average path loss. Considering the short transmission range of VLC, we model the PDF of h_{a_i} as a lognormal distribution [1]:

$$f_{h_{a_i}}(h_{a_i}) = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\left(\ln(h_{a_i})+2\sigma_x^2\right)^2}{8\sigma_x^2}\right)}{2h_{a_i}\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_x^2}}, \quad h_{a_i} > 0, \quad (4.12)$$

where $\sigma_l^2 = 4\sigma_x^2$ is the log-amplitude variance.

Remark 4.1:In this work, we examine the performance and diversity property of the proposed V2V-VLC model under the combined impact of path loss and AT as represented in (4.11), taking into account a realistic outdoor V2V-VLC scenario.

Also, a maximum-likelihood Rx can be expressed as:

$$\hat{x} = \min_{x \in \{0,1\}} \left| y - \rho \sum_{i=1}^2 h_i x \right|^2, \quad (4.13)$$

where x is an OOK symbol, and \hat{x} denotes the detected symbol at the Rx.

4.3 Performance Metrics Under Scenario 1

We take into account various performance indicators, such as path loss, outage probability, ABER, and diversity, to analyze the performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model.

Scenario 1:Here, the deterministic longitudinal separation and the random lateral movement for the two communicating vehicles are taken into consideration.

4.3.1 Average Path Loss

The path loss expression provided in [46, Eq.(7)] serves as our foundation. However, in this work, the lateral displacement of the vehicle is quantified as random, in contrast to [46], wherein it is considered to be predictable. One of the two LOS propagation paths, as shown in Fig. 4.1, has the following path loss:

$$h_1^{PL} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{D_R}{\xi} \right)^2 \frac{(\cos(\theta_1))^{2/\epsilon}}{L_1^2} \exp(-cL_1), \quad (4.14)$$

where ξ and ϵ are the correction coefficients concerning different weather conditions, and c is the extinction coefficient. The specific values of ξ , ϵ and c are provided in [46]. As $\cos(\theta_1) = \frac{d}{L_1}$, (4.14) can be written as:

$$h_1^{PL} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{D_R}{\xi} \right)^2 \frac{d^{2/\epsilon}}{L_1^{2+2/\epsilon}} \exp(-cL_1). \quad (4.15)$$

We consider that d_{h_1} is uniformly distributed, i.e., $d_{h_1} \sim \mathcal{U} \left(\frac{-W_v}{2}, 2W_L - \frac{W_v}{2} \right)$. Accordingly, $L_1 \sim \mathcal{U} \left(z_1 = \sqrt{d^2 + \frac{W_v^2}{4}}, z_2 = \sqrt{d^2 + \left(2W_L - \frac{W_v}{2} \right)^2} \right)$. Therefore, the average path loss is given by:

$$(h_1^{PL})^{avg} = \int_0^\infty h_1^{PL} f_{L_1}(L_1) dL_1, \quad (4.16)$$

where

$$f_{L_1}(L_1) \triangleq \begin{cases} \frac{1}{z_2 - z_1}, & z_1 \leq L_1 \leq z_2 \\ 0, & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases} \quad (4.17)$$

Remark 4.2: It can be observed from (4.15) that the path loss depends on L_1 . Moreover, L_1 is dependent on d_{h_1} (see the geometric relation presented in Subsection 4.2.1). Further, as d_{h_1} is uniformly distributed, the path loss is dependent on the uniformly distributed lateral movement of the vehicle.

Substituting (4.15) and (4.17) into (4.16), we get:

$$(h_1^{PL})^{avg} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{D_R}{\xi} \right)^2 \frac{d^{2/\epsilon}}{z_2 - z_1} \int_{z_1}^{z_2} \exp(-cL_1) \frac{1}{L_1^{2+2/\epsilon}} dL_1. \quad (4.18)$$

Let $k = 2 + \frac{2}{\epsilon}$ and $cL_1 = x$, a closed-form solution concerning (4.18) is obtained:

$$(h_1^{PL})^{avg} = \frac{D_R^2 d^{2/\epsilon} c^{k-1}}{2\xi^2(z_2 - z_1)} \left[\Gamma(1 - k, z_1 c) - \Gamma(1 - k, z_2 c) \right], \quad (4.19)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the upper incomplete-gamma function [118]. For the other LOS propagation path, a similar closed-form expression can be constructed. Thus, the effective path loss is given by:

$$h_{\text{Eff}}^{PL} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 (h_i^{PL})^{avg} \right). \quad (4.20)$$

4.3.2 Outage Probability

When the SNR for all of the communication links drops below a predetermined threshold SNR, the communication system experiences an outage. Considering (4.11) and (4.12), we obtain the PDF of h_i by applying the transformation of random variables:

$$f_{h_i}(h_i) = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{h_i}{(h_i^{PL})_{avg}}\right)+2\sigma_x^2\right)^2}{8\sigma_x^2}\right)}{2h_i\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_x^2}, \quad h_i > 0. \quad (4.21)$$

Thus the average received SNR is given by:

$$\gamma_i = \frac{(\rho P_t h_i)^2}{\sigma^2} = S_i h_i^2, \quad (4.22)$$

where $S_i = \frac{(\rho P_t)^2}{\sigma^2}$, P_t is the transmit optical power for each Tx, and σ^2 denotes the variance of noise e .

Remark 4.3: For V2V-VLC, the background-induced shot noise is the dominant one. More precisely, we denote the shot noise by σ_{shot}^2 , which is given by $\sigma^2 = \sigma_{\text{shot}}^2 = 2q\rho B P_R + 2qBI_2 I_{\text{bg}}$. Here, $P_R = P_t h_i$. To this end, all the parameters are defined in [123]. We model σ_{shot}^2 as Gaussian noise [123].

Additionally, the selective transmission strategy is utilized by applying the standard SNR output maximization criterion, which is stated by:

$$\gamma \triangleq \max(\gamma_1, \gamma_2). \quad (4.23)$$

Note, γ_1 and γ_2 denote the individual SNR corresponding to the two communication links, as illustrated in Fig. 4.1. Considering the adequate spacing between the Tx1 and Tx2, we consider that γ_1 is independent of γ_2 . Thus the outage probability can be mathematically formulated as:

$$P_{out} = \prod_{i=1}^2 \int_0^{\sqrt{\frac{\gamma_T}{S_i}}} f_{h_i}(h_i) dh_i. \quad (4.24)$$

In (4.24), γ_T denotes the threshold SNR. On employing (4.21) into (4.24), we get:

$$P_{out} = \prod_{i=1}^2 \int_0^{\sqrt{\frac{\gamma_T}{S_i}}} \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{h_i}{(h_i^{PL})_{avg}}\right)+2\sigma_x^2\right)^2}{8\sigma_x^2}\right)}{2h_i\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_x^2} dh_i. \quad (4.25)$$

Applying change of variables approach, i.e., $g_i = \frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{h_i}{(h_i^{PL})^{avg}}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2\right)}{2\sigma_x}$, a closed-form corresponding to (4.25) is obtained as:

$$P_{out} = \prod_{i=1}^2 Q\left(-\frac{\ln\left(\frac{\sqrt{\gamma_T}\sigma_i}{(h_i^{PL})^{avg}\rho P_t}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2}{2\sigma_x}\right), \quad (4.26)$$

where $Q(\cdot)$ is Gaussian q-function. Let $u_i = \left(-\frac{\ln\left(\frac{\sqrt{\gamma_T}\sigma_i}{(h_i^{PL})^{avg}\rho P_t}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2}{2\sigma_x}\right)$ and thus $P_{out} = \prod_{i=1}^2 Q(u_i)$.

4.3.3 ABER

The ABER can be mathematically expressed as:

$$\text{ABER} = \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty Q\left(\sqrt{\gamma_i(h_1 + h_2)^2}\right) \times f_{h_1}(h_1)f_{h_2}(h_2)dh_1dh_2. \quad (4.27)$$

To derive a closed-form expression of (4.27), we first consider the inner integral of (4.27):

$$I_1 = \int_0^\infty Q\left(\sqrt{\gamma_i(h_1 + h_2)^2}\right) f_{h_1}(h_1)dh_1. \quad (4.28)$$

Employing the relation $Q(y) = \frac{1}{2}\text{erfc}\left(\frac{y}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$ in (4.28), and substituting (4.21), for $i = 1$, into (4.28), we get:

$$I_1 = \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{2}\text{erfc}\left((h_1 + h_2)\sqrt{\frac{\gamma_i}{2}}\right) \times \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{h_1}{(h_1^{PL})^{avg}}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2\right)^2}{8\sigma_x^2}\right)}{2h_1\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_x^2} dh_1. \quad (4.29)$$

Applying change of variables approach, i.e., $g = \frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{h_1}{(h_1^{PL})^{avg}}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2\right)}{2\sigma_x}$, (4.29) can be expressed as:

$$I_1 = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_0^\infty \text{erfc}(Ae^{Bg} + D)e^{-\frac{g^2}{2}} dg, \quad (4.30)$$

where $A = (h_1^{PL})^{avg}e^{-2\sigma_x^2}\sqrt{\frac{\gamma_i}{2}}$, $B = 2\sigma_x$, and $D = h_2\sqrt{\frac{\gamma_i}{2}}$. Similarly, we apply the transformation $z = e^{Bg}$ to (4.30) and obtain:

$$I_1 = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_1^\infty \frac{1}{Bz}\text{erfc}\left(A\left(z + \frac{D}{A}\right)\right)e^{-\frac{\ln z}{B^2}} dz. \quad (4.31)$$

A closed-form expression corresponding to (4.31) can be evaluated using MATHEMATICA software as given by:

$$I_1 = \frac{B}{2\sqrt{2\pi}} \times \left(\operatorname{erfc}(D) - \frac{D \operatorname{ExpIntegralE}[\frac{1}{2}(1 + \frac{1}{B^2}), D^2]}{\sqrt{\pi}} \right), \quad (4.32)$$

where $\operatorname{ExpIntegralE}[n, z]$ gives the exponential integral function $E_n(z)$ [124]. Thus (4.27) simplifies to:

$$\text{ABER} = \int_0^\infty I_1 f_{h_2}(h_2) dh_2 = \int_0^\infty I_1 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{h_2}{(h_2^{PL})_{avg}}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2\right)^2}{8\sigma_x^2}\right)}{2h_2\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_x^2} dh_2. \quad (4.33)$$

Applying change of the variables method, i.e., $u = \frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{h_2}{(h_2^{PL})_{avg}}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2\right)}{2\sigma_x}$, (4.33) can be expressed as:

$$\text{ABER} = \int_0^\infty I_1 \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{u^2}{2}} du. \quad (4.34)$$

On substituting (4.32) into (4.34), we obtain:

$$\text{ABER} = \frac{B}{4\pi} \times \int_0^\infty \left(\operatorname{erfc}(D) - \frac{D \operatorname{ExpIntegralE}[\frac{1}{2}(1 + \frac{1}{B^2}), D^2]}{\sqrt{\pi}} \right) \times e^{-\frac{u^2}{2}} du. \quad (4.35)$$

To compute (4.35), we have the following two considerations:

$$I_2 = \int_0^\infty \operatorname{erfc}(D) e^{-\frac{u^2}{2}} du. \quad (4.36)$$

and

$$I_3 = \int_0^\infty \frac{D \operatorname{ExpIntegralE}[\frac{1}{2}(1 + \frac{1}{B^2}), D^2]}{\sqrt{\pi}} e^{-\frac{u^2}{2}} du. \quad (4.37)$$

To compute I_2 , applying the change of variables method, i.e., $g = \frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{h_2}{(h_2^{PL})_{avg}}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2\right)}{2\sigma_x}$, we get:

$$I_2 = \int_0^\infty \operatorname{erfc}(Ge^{Bg}) e^{-\frac{g^2}{2}} dg, \quad (4.38)$$

where $G = (h_2^{PL})_{avg} e^{-2\sigma_x^2} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_i}{2}}$. Applying a transformation of $z = e^{Bg}$, a closed-form expression concerning (4.38) is obtained:

$$I_2 = B \left[\operatorname{erfc}(G) - \frac{G \operatorname{ExpIntegralE}[\frac{1}{2}(1 + \frac{1}{B^2}), G^2]}{\sqrt{\pi}} \right]. \quad (4.39)$$

Similarly, a closed-form corresponding to I_3 is determined as given in (4.40).

$$I_3 = GB e^{-G^2} \times \frac{\left(2B^2 - (1 + (-1 + 2G^2)) B^2 e^{G^2} \text{ExpIntegralE}\left[\frac{1}{2}(-1 + \frac{1}{B^2}), G^2\right] \right)}{2(-1 + B^2)\sqrt{\pi}}. \quad (4.40)$$

Now, taking (4.35), (4.36) and (4.37) into account, ABER can be written as:

$$\therefore \text{ABER} = \text{abs}\left(\frac{B}{4\pi}(I_2 - I_3)\right). \quad (4.41)$$

Note that, the closed-form expressions concerning I_2 and I_3 are depicted in (4.39) and (4.40), respectively. Further, $\text{abs}(\cdot)$ denotes the absolute value. Since $I_2 < I_3$, therefore, the absolute value of ABER is taken into account in (4.41).

4.3.4 Diversity Order

The diversity signifies the slope of decay of ABER versus the SNR plot at asymptotically high values of SNR. Mathematically, at very high SNR, ABER can be expressed as:

$$\text{ABER}_{\gamma_i \rightarrow \infty} \propto \gamma_i^{-D_o}, \quad (4.42)$$

Note that, D_o is the diversity order. Considering (4.42) into account, we first determine D_o corresponding to I_2 given in (4.39), at a very high value of SNR. With (4.42), we will consider only the terms proportional to the exponent of γ_i . To this end, in (4.39), $\text{erfc}(G) = 0$. Also, note that $E_n(z) = \int_1^\infty \frac{e^{-zt}}{t^n} dt = \int_1^\infty \frac{e^{-G^2 t}}{t^{\frac{1}{2}(1 + \frac{1}{B^2})}} dt$. Thus we employ Taylor series expansion of an exponential function, i.e., e^{-G^2} . Moreover, we represent the series in a form given in (4.43) to determine the dominant term at a very high SNR as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} e^{-G^2} &= 1 - \gamma_i + \gamma_i^2 - \gamma_i^3 + \dots, \\ &= \gamma_i^3 \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_i^3} - \frac{1}{\gamma_i^2} + \frac{1}{\gamma_i} - 1 + \dots \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4.43)$$

Taking into account the dominant terms in (4.43), we have $e^{-G^2} = \gamma_i^2$. Thus, we get:

$$I_2 \propto \gamma_i^2. \quad (4.44)$$

Similarly, we can determine the exponent of γ_i concerning (4.40) as:

$$I_3 \propto \gamma_i^3. \quad (4.45)$$

Now, $I_2 - I_3 \propto (\gamma_i^2 + (-\gamma_i^3))$. Therefore, the ABER at very high SNR is given by:

$$\text{ABER}_{\gamma_i \rightarrow \infty}^{\text{Scenario1}} \propto \gamma_i^2. \quad (4.46)$$

To this end, the diversity order is obtained as $D_o = 2$.

Remark 4.4: We employ a RC scheme which is known to provide full diversity.

4.4 Performance Metrics Under Scenario 2

We expand on the analytical framework of scenario 1 to construct the performance measures of scenario 2.

Scenario 2: The longitudinal separation between the two communication vehicles is quantified as random. In contrast to scenario 1, consideration is also given to the presence of stationary or moving vehicles beside two communicating vehicles, as shown in Fig. 4.1. As a result, the NLOS signal components caused by parked or moving vehicles as well as from road surface reflection are also taken into account.

If K denotes the event concerning the LOS blockage, the probability mass function (PMF) can be modeled by Bernoulli distribution:

$$\Pr[K = k] = \begin{cases} p, & k = 1 \\ 1 - p, & k = 0, \end{cases} \quad (4.47)$$

where $\Pr[\cdot]$ denotes the probability.

Remark 4.5: The direct-path obstruction between the Tx and Rx event $k = 1$ corresponds to a blocked LOS event with probability p . Yet, the entire VLC channel includes both the LOS and NLOS signal components when $k = 0$ (there is no obstacle in the straight path between the Tx and Rx). It should be noted that the NLOS signal components result from barriers near two communicating vehicles, such as parked or moving cars or road surface reflections.

4.4.1 Average Path Loss

The total path loss at the Rx concerning LOS and NLOS can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} h_{\text{Total-Rx}}^{PL} &= \sum_{\alpha=0}^{n_d} h^{PL}(\alpha) = h^{PL}(0) + \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n_d} h^{PL}(\alpha) \\ &= p \left(n_d h^{PL}(\alpha) \right) + (1-p) \left((n_d + 1) h^{PL}(0) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (4.48)$$

where $h^{PL}(0)$ and $\sum_{\alpha=1}^{n_d} h^{PL}(\alpha)$ are the path loss for the LOS and NLOS, respectively. Also, n_d denotes the number of diffused signal components.

Remark 4.7: The probability of LOS blockage is probabilistic due to the short-distance nature of VLC (as shown in (4.48)), meaning that there won't be many blockages. Hence, it is considered that each diffused signal component's path loss is the same. In the future extension of this study, we will consider non-identical diffused signal components.

Therefore, the path loss concerning the i^{th} LOS propagation path can be expressed as:

$$h_i^{PL}(d) = p \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{D_R}{\xi} \right)^2 \frac{d^{2/\epsilon}}{L_i^{2+2/\epsilon}} \exp(-cL_i) \right) + (1-p) \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{D_R}{\xi} \right)^2 \frac{d^{2/\epsilon}}{L_i^{2+2/\epsilon}} \exp(-cL_i) \right). \quad (4.49)$$

Considering that the two communicating vehicles are sufficiently apart, we assume the PDF of d to be inverse Gaussian distribution [128]. We consider d to be random within a range of 0 to 50 m. To this end, the PDF of d can be modeled as:

$$f_d(d) = \frac{1}{0.989108} \times \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2\pi d^3}} \times e^{-\frac{\lambda(d-\mu)^2}{2\mu^2 d}}, 0 \leq d \leq 50. \quad (4.50)$$

Remark 4.8: Since VLC has a limited transmission range, d is considered to be random over a practical range of 0-50 m. Moreover, d varies slowly during a small period T within the prescribed range due to the movement of other nearby vehicles.

Therefore, the average path loss expression is given by:

$$(h_i^{PL})^{avg} = \int_0^\infty h_i^{PL}(d) f_d(d) dd. \quad (4.51)$$

On substituting (4.49) and (4.50) into (4.51), employing taylor series expansion of an exponential function, the average path loss can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
(h_i^{PL})^{avg} &= p \left(\frac{1}{0.989108} \times \frac{D_R^2 \sqrt{\lambda}}{2\xi^2} \times \int_0^{50} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi d^3}} \times \right. \\
&\times \frac{d^{2/\epsilon}}{\left(\sqrt{d^2 + d_{h_i}^2}\right)^{2+2/\epsilon}} \times \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{\left(c\sqrt{d^2 + d_{h_i}^2}\right)^n}{n!} \times \\
&\times \left. e^{-\frac{\lambda(d-\mu)^2}{2\mu^2 d}} dd \right) + (1-p) \left(\frac{1}{0.989108} \times \frac{D_R^2 \sqrt{\lambda}}{2\xi^2} \times \right. \\
&\times \int_0^{50} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi d^3}} \times \frac{d^{2/\epsilon}}{\left(\sqrt{d^2 + d_{h_i}^2}\right)^{2+2/\epsilon}} \times \\
&\times \left. \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{\left(c\sqrt{d^2 + d_{h_i}^2}\right)^n}{n!} \times e^{-\frac{\lambda(d-\mu)^2}{2\mu^2 d}} dd \right). \tag{4.52}
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, using (4.48) the effective path loss at the Rx corresponding to scenario 2 will be:

$$h_{\text{EFF}}^{PL} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 p \left(n_d (h_i^{PL})^{avg} \right) + (1-p) \left((n_d + 1) (h_i^{PL})^{avg} \right) \right). \tag{4.53}$$

The factor $(n_d + 1)$ in (4.53) corresponds to the NLOS signal components with identical path loss.

Remark 4.9: The integral in (4.52) can be swiftly evaluated. Thus further effort for simplifying (4.52) is not required.

4.4.2 Outage Probability

We build upon the framework of scenario 1 to determine the outage probability of scenario 2 as:

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{out} &= \prod_{i=1}^2 \int_0^{\frac{\ln\left(\frac{\sqrt{\gamma T} S_i}{(h_i^{PL})^{avg}}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2}{2\sigma_x}} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{g_i^2}{2}\right) \right] dg_i \\
&= \prod_{i=1}^2 Q\left(-\frac{\ln\left(\frac{\sqrt{\gamma T} \sigma_i}{(h_i^{PL})^{avg} \rho P_t}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2}{2\sigma_x}\right). \tag{4.54}
\end{aligned}$$

Considering the effective path loss corresponding to LOS and NLOS, the outage probability can be expressed as:

$$P_{out} = \prod_{i=1}^2 Q\left(-\frac{\ln\left(\frac{\sqrt{\gamma_T}\sigma_i}{h_{i,\text{Eff}}^{PL}\rho P_i}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2}{2\sigma_x}\right), \quad (4.55)$$

where $h_{i,\text{Eff}}^{PL}$ is the effective path loss corresponding to the i^{th} LOS link, and can be determined using (4.53).

Remark 4.10: The outage probability corresponding to scenario 2 given in (4.55) depends on the lateral shift of the vehicle, in contrast to scenario 1, wherein the outage probability given in (4.26) depends on the longitudinal separation between the two communicating vehicles.

4.4.3 ABER and Diversity Order

The PDF for the i^{th} propagation path concerning the LOS and NLOS signal can be expressed as:

$$f_{h_i}(h_i) = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{h_i}{h_{i,\text{Eff}}^{PL}}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2\right)^2}{8\sigma_x^2}\right)}{2h_i\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_x^2}, \quad h_i > 0. \quad (4.56)$$

Now, utilizing the similar approach of scenario 1, the closed-form expression for the scenario 2 can be expressed:

$$\text{ABER} = \text{abs}\left(\frac{B}{4\pi}(P_2 - P_3)\right). \quad (4.57)$$

A closed-form expression corresponding to P_2 is given by:

$$P_2 = B\left[\text{erfc}(N) - \frac{N\text{ExpIntegralE}\left[\frac{1}{2}\left(1 + \frac{1}{B^2}\right), N^2\right]}{\sqrt{\pi}}\right], \quad (4.58)$$

where $N = h_{2,\text{Eff}}^{PL} e^{-2\sigma_x^2} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_i}{2}}$. Further, a closed-form expression concerning P_3 is determined as given in (4.59).

$$P_3 = NB e^{-N^2} \times \frac{\left(2B^2 - \left(1 + (-1 + 2N^2)\right)B^2 e^{N^2} \text{ExpIntegralE}\left[\frac{1}{2}\left(-1 + \frac{1}{B^2}\right), N^2\right]\right)}{2(-1 + B^2)\sqrt{\pi}}. \quad (4.59)$$

Table 4.2: Comparison of the existing works and our proposed work

V2V-VLC Propagation Characteristics	Existing Works [70–78]	Our Proposed Work
Comparative study of both LOS and NLOS propagation models	×	✓
A dynamic V2V-VLC model (random propagation distance between Tx and Rx due to the random lateral movement of the vehicle)	×	✓
Modeling the impact of road surface reflection with a specific distribution function	×	✓
Modeling the impact of the interfering vehicle on the two communicating vehicles	×	✓
Accumulation of particles (dry/wet) on the headlights (transmitters) depending on the weather conditions	×	✓
A comprehensive path loss and DCMC capacity investigation with the above-mentioned V2V-VLC propagation characteristics under different weather conditions	×	✓

Adopting the similar approach of scenario 1, the diversity order corresponding to scenario 2 is also obtained as $D_o = 2$.

4.5 Average Path Loss and DCMC Capacity under Practical Outdoor Propagation Characteristics

The existing literature on V2V-VLC is mostly focused on the simulation studies, for instance, [43], [46], [70–72], [78]. However, modeling the practical outdoor vehicular VLC propagation characteristics (tabulated in Table 4.2) and analyzing their impact on the propagation model is crucial. Moreover, none of the reported works have em-

phasized a comparative study of LOS and NLOS propagation models incorporating the propagation characteristics tabulated in Table 4.2. Also, none of the reported works have analyzed the DCMC capacity to envision the maximum attainable capacity by the V2V-VLC channel incorporating the V2V-VLC propagation characteristics highlighted in Table 4.2.

Motivated by the aforesaid discussion, in this section, we aim to analyze the impact of the considered propagation characteristics on the proposed LOS and NLOS V2V-VLC models. To this end, we investigate the path loss and DCMC capacity to analyze the impact of the considered propagation characteristics (highlighted in Table 4.2) on the proposed V2V-VLC models. We first consider the LOS V2V-VLC model shown in Fig. 4.1. Further, an NLOS V2V-VLC propagation model is also analyzed.

4.5.1 Average Path Loss for LOS V2V-VLC Scenario

Building upon Eqs. (1) and (2) of [46], a more practical path loss expression considering the **random mobility** of the vehicle, and **accumulation of particles on the Tx**s is derived. Considering the use of dual Tx, and since we have $\cos \phi_i = \frac{d}{L_i}$, the combined geometrical and attenuation path loss for the V2V-VLC link between i^{th} Tx and Rx can be formulated as:

$$h_{\text{LOS}}^{\text{PL}} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{D_R^2(d)^{2/\epsilon} V_D^2}{\xi^2 (L_i)^{2+2/\epsilon}} \times \exp \left(-c L_i \left(\frac{D_R}{\xi L_i} \right)^{\epsilon/2} \right) \right). \quad (4.60)$$

Moreover, V_D is a RV that incorporates the deposit of dry/wet particles depending upon the weather conditions. Considering a uniform accumulation of particles, V_D can be modeled with a uniform PDF given by:

$$f_{V_D}(V_D) \triangleq \begin{cases} \frac{\varrho}{p_2 - p_1}, & p_1 \leq V_D \leq p_2 \\ 0, & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases} \quad (4.61)$$

where $\varrho = \exp(c)$ is a parameter that incorporates the deposit of particles on the Tx depending upon the weather condition. Moreover, $p_2 - p_1$ corresponds to the width of a rectangular-shaped Tx. Now, let us consider that d_{h_i} is uniformly distributed, i.e., $d_{h_i} \sim \mathcal{U} \left(\pm \frac{W_v}{2}, 2W_L \pm \frac{W_v}{2} \right)$. Accordingly, $L_i \sim \mathcal{U} \left(z_1 = \sqrt{d^2 + \frac{W_v^2}{4}}, z_2 = \right)$

$\sqrt{d^2 + \left(2W_L \pm \frac{W_v}{2}\right)^2}$). Note that, L_i is a uniform RV and mathematically expressed considering the geometric relation discussed in Section 4.2.1. Therefore, the average path loss for the LOS scenario will be:

$$h_{\text{LOS}}^{\text{PL,av}} = \int_{p_1}^{p_2} \int_{z_1}^{z_2} h_{\text{LOS}}^{\text{PL}} f_{L_i}(L_i) f_{V_D}(V_D) dL_i dV_D. \quad (4.62)$$

A closed-form solution corresponding to (4.62) is obtained as:

$$h_{\text{LOS}}^{\text{PL,av}} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{D_R^2(d)^{2/\epsilon} c^{q-1} \varrho \times (4096 \times 10^{-6})}{(3 \times \xi^2 \times (p_2 - p_1) \times (z_2 - z_1))} \right. \\ \times \left(\frac{-\text{ExpIntegralE} \left[\frac{(\epsilon/2)-q}{(\epsilon/2)-1}, \left(\frac{D_R c}{\xi} \right)^{\epsilon/2} \times z_1^{1-\epsilon/2} \right] z_1^{1-q}}{(\epsilon/2) - 1} + \right. \\ \left. \left. \frac{\text{ExpIntegralE} \left[\frac{(\epsilon/2)-q}{(\epsilon/2)-1}, \left(\frac{D_R c}{\xi} \right)^{\epsilon/2} \times z_2^{1-\epsilon/2} \right] z_2^{1-q}}{(\epsilon/2) - 1} \right) \right), \quad (4.63)$$

where $q = 2 + (2/\epsilon)$.

Proof: Refer to Appendix F.

Remark 4.11: It can be observed from (4.63) that the average path loss corresponding to the LOS V2V-VLC propagation model is inversely dependent on the difference factor, i.e., $A \triangleq z_2 - z_1$. In the subsequent section, we will demonstrate the impact of this difference factor on the proposed LOS V2V-VLC propagation model.

4.5.2 Average Path Loss for NLOS V2V-VLC Scenario

In this subsection, we aim to investigate novel closed-form expressions of the average path loss for the NLOS links corresponding to interfering vehicle (IV) and road surface (RS). Considering Fig. 4.2, $\delta_{I,i}$ and $\delta_{R,i}$ denote the angle of incidence (on the IV) and angle of reflection (from the IV) w.r.t. the i^{th} Tx, respectively. Moreover, $d = I_{V_1-V_2}$ (inter-vehicle separation between V_1 and V_2) = $I_{V_1-IV} + I_{IV-V_2}$. Similar to $h_{\text{LOS}}^{\text{PL}}$, we can mathematically formulate the path loss corresponding to NLOS-IV. Further, for path loss corresponding to NLOS-IV, we write $\cos \phi_i = \frac{I_{V_1-IV}}{L_i^{V_1-IV}}$ and $\cos \delta_{R,i} = \frac{I_{IV-V_2}}{L_i^{IV-V_2}}$, where $L_i^{V_1-IV}$ and $L_i^{IV-V_2}$ denote the propagation distance corresponding to $V_1 - IV$

Figure 4.2: Schematic illustration of the NLOS V2V-VLC propagation model.

and $IV - V_2$ w.r.t. i^{th} Tx, respectively. Therefore, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_{\text{NLOS,IV}}^{\text{PL}} &= 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^2 \left(\frac{A_{IV}^2 (I_{V_1-IV})^{2/\epsilon} V_D^2}{\xi^2 (L_i^{V_1-IV})^{2+2/\epsilon}} \right) \times \right. \\
 &\quad \times \left(\frac{D_R^2 (I_{IV-V_2})^{2/\epsilon}}{\xi^2 (L_i^{IV-V_2})^{2+2/\epsilon}} \right) \\
 &\quad \times \exp \left(-c (L_i^{V_1-IV} + L_i^{IV-V_2}) \right) \\
 &\quad \left. \times \left(\frac{D_R}{\xi (L_i^{V_1-IV} + L_i^{IV-V_2})} \right)^{\epsilon/2} \right), \tag{4.64}
 \end{aligned}$$

where A_{IV} is the effective area (assumed to be circular) of the IV on which the beam is incident. Further, following the similar formulation as in Subsection 4.5.1, we have $L_i^{V_1-IV} = X \sim \mathcal{U} \left(x_1 = \sqrt{I_{V_1-IV}^2 + \frac{W_v^2}{4}}, x_2 = \sqrt{I_{V_1-IV}^2 + \left(2W_L \pm \frac{W_v}{2}\right)^2} \right)$ and $L_i^{IV-V_2} = Y \sim \mathcal{U} \left(y_1 = \sqrt{I_{IV-V_2}^2 + \frac{W_v^2}{4}}, y_2 = \sqrt{I_{IV-V_2}^2 + \left(2W_L \pm \frac{W_v}{2}\right)^2} \right)$. Note that X and Y are intermediate RVs. Therefore, the average path loss for the NLOS V2V-VLC scenario corresponding to IV will be:

$$h_{\text{NLOS,IV}}^{\text{PL,av}} = \int_{p_1}^{p_2} \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \int_{x_1}^{x_2} h_{\text{NLOS,IV}}^{\text{PL}} f_X(x) f_Y(y) f_{V_D}(V_D) dx dy dV_D. \tag{4.65}$$

Solving the integrals one-by-one, a closed-form expression corresponding to (4.65) is obtained:

$$h_{\text{NLOS,IV}}^{\text{PL,av}} = 10 \log_{10} \times \left(\frac{A_{IV}^2 I_{V_1-IV}^{2/\epsilon} D_R^2 I_{IV-V_2}^{2/\epsilon} \varrho(4096 \times 10^{-6})}{3\xi^4 \times (p_2 - p_1) \times (y_2 - y_1) \times (x_2 - x_1)} \times \frac{\exp\left(\frac{-D_{RC}}{\xi}\right) (x_1^{1-q} - x_2^{1-q})(y_1^{1-q} - y_2^{1-q})}{(q-1)^2} \right). \quad (4.66)$$

Proof: Refer to Appendix G.

Remark 4.12: It can be observed from (4.66) that the average path loss corresponding to the NLOS-IV V2V-VLC propagation model is inversely dependent on the product of the two difference factors, i.e., $B \triangleq (y_2 - y_1)(x_2 - x_1)$. In the subsequent section, we will demonstrate the impact of B on the proposed NLOS-IV V2V-VLC propagation model.

For the average path loss corresponding to road surface (RS), we define the following RVs: $Y = (\text{Cos}(\delta_{RS,i}))^{2/\epsilon}$, $L_i^{V_1-RS}$ (propagation distance corresponding to $V_1 - RS$ w.r.t. i^{th} Tx) $= R \sim \mathcal{U} \left(r_1 = \sqrt{I_{V_1-RS}^2 + \frac{W_v^2}{4}}, r_2 = \sqrt{I_{V_1-RS}^2 + \left(2W_L \pm \frac{W_v}{2}\right)^2} \right)$ and $L_i^{RS-V_2}$ (propagation distance corresponding to $RS - V_2$ w.r.t. i^{th} Tx) $= S \sim \mathcal{U} \left(s_1 = \sqrt{I_{RS-V_2}^2 + \frac{W_v^2}{4}}, s_2 = \sqrt{I_{RS-V_2}^2 + \left(2W_L \pm \frac{W_v}{2}\right)^2} \right)$, where $\delta_{RS,i}$ denotes the angle of reflection corresponding to road surface with $\delta_{RS,i} \sim \mathcal{U} \left(\left[0, \frac{\pi}{3}\right] \right)$. By applying the concept of transformation of RVs, the PDF of Y is derived as:

$$f_Y(y) = \frac{3}{k\pi y^{\frac{k-1}{k}} \sqrt{1 - y^{2/k}}}, y \in [0.5^k, 1]. \quad (4.67)$$

Following the similar approach of path loss formulation corresponding to IV, the average path loss corresponding to road surface can be expressed as:

$$h_{\text{NLOS,RS}}^{\text{PL,av}} = \int_{p_1}^{p_2} \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \int_{s_1}^{s_2} \int_{r_1}^{r_2} h_{\text{NLOS,RS}}^{\text{PL}} f_R(r) f_S(s) f_Y(y) f_{V_D}(V_D) \times dr ds dy dV_D. \quad (4.68)$$

Now, a closed-form solution corresponding to (4.68) is determined:

$$\begin{aligned}
h_{\text{NLOS,RS}}^{\text{PL,av}} &= z \times 10 \log_{10} \\
&\times \left(\frac{A_{RS}^2 I_{V_1-RS}^2 D_R^2 3\varrho}{\xi^2 \times (p_2 - p_1) \times (s_2 - s_1) \times (r_2 - r_1)} \times \right. \\
&\times \left[\frac{1}{k\pi} \times \exp\left(\frac{-D_{RC}}{\xi}\right) \times \frac{r_1^{1-q} - r_2^{1-q}}{q-1} \times \left(\frac{1}{s_1} - \frac{1}{s_2}\right) \times k \right. \\
&\times \left. \left. \left(\text{Sin}^{-1}(y_2^{1/k}) - \text{Sin}^{-1}(y_1^{1/k}) \right) \right] \right), \tag{4.69}
\end{aligned}$$

where A_{RS} is the effective area (assumed to be circular) of the road surface on which the beam is incident, and $k = 2/\epsilon$.

Proof: Refer to Appendix H.

Remark 4.13: It can be observed from (4.69) that the average path loss corresponding to the NLOS-road surface (NLOS link arising from the road surface) is inversely dependent on the product of the two difference factors with an additional term, i.e., $C \triangleq (s_2 - s_1)(r_2 - r_1)(s_1 s_2)$. In the subsequent section, we will demonstrate the impact of C on the proposed NLOS-road surface V2V-VLC propagation model.

Remark 4.14: In (4.69), z is a parameter representing the state of road surface (dry/wet) according to the weather conditions, and which is mostly dominating when the road surface is wet. For instance, $z = 0$ (for clear weather) and $z = 1$ (for rainy, moderate fog and dense fog weather conditions). Note that, we emphasize the binary values of the z as per the binary state of the road surface, i.e., either dry or wet. By wet state ($z = 1$), we mean that the road surface reflection is sufficiently worth contributing to the NLOS.

4.5.3 Mutual Information and DCMC Capacity

To derive the mutual information, the notion of considering Gaussian input is impractical [84–86]. Although Gaussian inputs are optimum but in the considered V2V-VLC system the TxS (headlights) of the vehicle transmit a VLC signal which can never be negative. Therefore, a **more practical capacity** known as DCMC capacity in which the input elements are finite valued (such as OOK modulation format) is aimed to be

investigated. Now, the PDF of the AWGN noise e in (4.10) can be written as:

$$f_e(e) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{e^2}{2\sigma^2}\right). \quad (4.70)$$

Accordingly, the PDF of the received signal y (conditioned over h_i with $\eta = 1$) can be formulated:

$$f(y|x, h_i) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{\left(y - \sum_i h_i x\right)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right). \quad (4.71)$$

Since x can take two symbols 0 and 1, the PDF of y shown in (4.71) can be written more precisely as:

$$f(y|h_i) = f(x=0)f(y|x=0, h_i) + f(x=1)f(y|x=1, h_i). \quad (4.72)$$

Now, the mutual information between input and output of the considered V2V-VLC system is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} I(x; y|h_i) &= \int f(x=0)f(y|x=0, h_i) \\ &\times \log_2 \left[\frac{f(y|x=0, h_i)}{f(x=0)f(y|x=0, h_i) + f(x=1)f(y|x=1, h_i)} \right] dy \\ &+ \int f(x=1)f(y|x=1, h_i) \\ &\times \log_2 \left[\frac{f(y|x=1, h_i)}{f(x=0)f(y|x=0, h_i) + f(x=1)f(y|x=1, h_i)} \right] dy. \end{aligned} \quad (4.73)$$

Further, the mutual information in (4.73) will be maximized when $f(x)$ is uniformly distributed. Therefore, the DCMC capacity of the considered V2V-VLC system will be:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{DCMC}}(h_i) &= \int_0^\infty 0.5f(y|x=0, h_i) \\ &\times \log_2 \left[\frac{f(y|x=0, h_i)}{0.5f(y|x=0, h_i) + 0.5f(y|x=1, h_i)} \right] dy \\ &+ \int_{\sum_i h_i}^\infty 0.5f(y|x=1, h_i) \\ &\times \log_2 \left[\frac{f(y|x=1, h_i)}{0.5f(y|x=0, h_i) + 0.5f(y|x=1, h_i)} \right] dy. \end{aligned} \quad (4.74)$$

Therefore, a closed-form solution for the ergodic DCMC capacity corresponding to (4.74) will be:

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{\text{DCMC}}^{\text{Ergodic}} &= \int_0^\infty C_{\text{DCMC}}(h_i) f_{h_i}(h_i) dh_i, \\
&= \frac{-0.180337\sigma(2.83788 + \ln \sigma^2)}{\sigma} \\
&\quad - \left(\frac{K\sqrt{\pi/2}\sigma \ln(K)}{\ln 2} - \left(\frac{2K\sqrt{2\pi}(h^{\text{PL,av}})^2 \exp(-4\sigma_x^2)}{\sigma \ln(16)} \right) \right) \\
&\quad + \left(\frac{8Kh^{\text{PL,av}}}{\ln(16)} - \frac{K\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma}{\ln(16)} \right) + \left(\left(-\frac{K\sqrt{\pi/2} \ln(2\pi\sigma^2)}{\sqrt{1/\sigma^2} \ln(4)} \right) \right) \\
&\quad + \left(-\frac{K\sqrt{\pi/2}}{2\sqrt{1/\sigma^2} \ln(2)} \right) - \left(\frac{K\sqrt{\pi/2}\sigma \ln(K)}{\ln(2)} \right) \\
&\quad + \left(\frac{K\sigma\sqrt{\pi/2}}{2\ln(2)} \right), \tag{4.75}
\end{aligned}$$

where $K = 0.5 \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}}$ and $h^{\text{PL,av}}$ is the average path loss corresponding to LOS/NLOS links as given in Eqs. (4.63), (4.66), and (4.69).

Proof: Refer to Appendix I.

Remark 4.15: It can be observed from (4.75) that the ergodic DCMC capacity has a strong dependence on the PL^{av} , i.e., the average path loss corresponding to LOS/NLOS links. Therefore, the data rate offered by the proposed V2V-VLC propagation models is highly dependent on the path loss. Consequently, the data rate of a practical V2V-VLC propagation model is constrained by the path loss. To this end, we will demonstrate the DCMC capacity corresponding to the proposed LOS and NLOS V2V-VLC propagation models in the subsequent section.

4.6 Results and Discussion

In this section, we present and discuss the numerical results investigated in the previous sections. We emphasize *comprehensive striking insights* that have not been previously identified in the literature. Additionally, we do Monte Carlo simulations to verify the accuracy of our derived results. Note that, the outdoor V2V-VLC system is significantly affected by the weather conditions. Therefore, performance indicators,

Table 4.3: Key simulation parameters under consideration [1, 46]

Parameter	Value
W_L	5 m
W_v	2.5 m
σ_l^2	0.8
σ^2	1
ρ	1
P_t	10 W
n_d	10
p	0.5
d	20 m (ABER for scenario 1)
d_h	2 m (ABER for scenario 2)
D_R	5 cm
Ψ	180°

including path loss, outage probability, ABER, and diversity property under various weather scenarios, will play a significant role in our discussion. Also, Table 4.3 has a thorough tabulation of all the simulation parameters relevant to the proposed V2V-VLC model.

4.6.1 Effect of Path Loss

We explore Fig. 4.1 to provide an interesting perspective on the impact of path loss concerning the proposed V2V-VLC model. Given that LED-based VLC is primarily designed for short-range communications, path loss has a substantial impact on the V2V-VLC. We illustrate the path loss curves for scenario 1 under various weather conditions and distances in Fig. 4.3. In order to depict the path loss curves, we use (4.20). According to Fig. 4.3, the path loss range for clear weather is about between -18 and -34 dB for the specified distance range. It ranges from -18 to -36 dB for moderate fog. The path loss range for dense fog is somewhere between -18 to -38 dB.

Figure 4.3: Path loss performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model concerning scenario 1 [(-) sign in the path loss values indicates the loss in the form of a path loss penalty].

Observation 4.1: We stress the path loss penalty provided by the considered random lateral shift of the vehicle. The path loss penalties for the moderate and dense fog weather conditions are 2 and 3 dB, respectively, compared to the clear weather, at a distance of 40 m, for example. As a result, the penalty for the proposed V2V-VLC system under the vehicle’s random lateral movement in terms of path loss is substantial.

We illustrate the path loss curves for different weather conditions and various lateral shifts for scenario 2 in Fig. 4.4. To plot the path loss curves, we use (4.53). According to Fig. 4.4, the path loss range for clear weather is between -10 to -24 dB for the specified range of lateral shift. When compared to clear weather, there is a slight degradation in the performance under mild fog. The path loss range for dense fog is somewhere between -10 to -28 dB.

Observation 4.2: Unlike the indoor VLC, the outdoor V2V-VLC path loss is highly influenced by the weather, the vehicle’s random lateral movement, and the random longitudinal separation of the two communicating vehicles. Therefore, we compare

Figure 4.4: Effect of path loss on the proposed V2V-VLC model corresponding to scenario 2.

the effects of path loss on the V2V-VLC model under consideration for scenarios 1 and 2, as shown in Figs. 4.3 and 4.4, respectively. The statistics show that the longitudinal separation has a significant influence on system performance than the lateral shift under various weather scenarios. This conclusion is reinforced by the fact that we evaluated a maximum feasible range of d_h in Fig. 4.4 for a lane width of $W_L = 5$ (shown in Table 4.3). It should be noted that while d can be increased further, d_h cannot be practically increased any farther.

4.6.2 Outage Performance

We consider how the proposed V2V-VLC model will operate during outages. The outage performance curves for various distances concerning scenario 1 are plotted in Fig. 4.5. To plot the outage performance curves, we use (4.26). As seen in Fig. 4.5, the magnitude of the outage probability rises with the increase in longitudinal separation/transmission distance. As far as the effect of the σ_l^2 on the outage performance is concerned, the outage performance gets better as the value of the σ_l^2 drops. Note that

Figure 4.5: Outage performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model corresponding to scenario 1.

the considered system operates best at $\sigma_l^2=0.1$.

We show the outage performance curves for various lateral shifts concerning scenario 2 in Fig. 4.6. To plot the outage performance curves, we use (4.55). Figure 4.6 shows that the value of the outage probability grows as the lateral displacement increases. The outage performance gets better with decreasing value of σ_l^2 , similar to scenario 1.

Observation 4.3: This work examines the impact of log-amplitude variance (σ_l^2) on the outage performance of the outdoor V2V-VLC system, in contrast to the indoor VLC scenario where atmospheric turbulence is not present. Also, random path loss is taken into consideration. Consequently, this work marks a more realistic observation. As shown in Figs. 4.5 and 4.6, respectively, we examine the outage performance of scenarios 1 (for varying longitudinal separation) and 2 (for varying lateral shifts). It can be seen that the impact of lateral shift becomes more substantial compared to the longitudinal separation as the value of (σ_l^2) rises.

Figure 4.6: Outage performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model corresponding to scenario 2.

4.6.3 ABER and Diversity Performance

The proposed V2V-VLC model's ABER performance curves are shown in Figure 4.7 for scenario 1 utilising (4.41) under different weather conditions. The ABER performance curve for clear weather outperforms the other ABER performance curves, as seen in Fig. 4.7. It demonstrates how weather affects the ABER performance of the V2V-VLC system under consideration. A simulation-based ABER curve corresponding to a dense fog weather situation with $\Psi = 60^\circ$ is also shown in order to visualize the impact of FOV on the ABER performance. A narrow FOV-based Rx offers a considerable performance boost, as seen in the figure. This is mainly because of capturing less noise.

Now, we determine the diversity order for the scenario 1 considering the moderate fog ABER curve. For example, ABER is 1.488×10^{-2} at 10 dB and 1.4×10^{-4} at 20 dB. Thus slope can be obtained as $\log_{10}(1.488 \times 10^{-2}/1.4 \times 10^{-4})$, which is approximately equal to 2. It shows that full diversity of $N_t \times N_r$ is attained, where N_t and N_r are the number of TxS and RxS, respectively. Therefore, diversity is the same for all three

Figure 4.7: ABER performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model corresponding to scenario 1.

ABER performance curves since the ABER performance curves are parallel to one another.

The ABER performance curves of the V2V-VLC system under consideration for scenario 2 are shown in Fig. 4.8 for different weather scenarios. The ABER performance curve for clear weather outperforms the other ABER performance curves, which is similar to scenario 1 and can be seen in Fig. 4.8. Considering scenario 2, the ABER performance curves for clear weather and mild fog weather conditions, are nearly identical to one another. It demonstrates that the longitudinal separation has less of an effect on the ABER performance in clear and mild fog weather conditions. A simulation-based curve matching for a dense fog weather scenario with $\Psi = 60^\circ$ is also given to help readers understand how FOV affects ABER performance. A narrow-FOV based Rx offers a large performance gain of 4-5 dB, as can be seen from the figure. However, this performance boost is only applicable for a particular lateral shift or mobility of $d_h = 2$ m (as shown in Table 4.3). It is to be noted that the Tx's will be out of the restricted field of view (FOV) of the Rx even with a minor increase in the vehi-

Figure 4.8: ABER performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model corresponding to scenario 2.

cle’s lateral movement. Consequently, the ABER performance will suffer dramatically. Thus, a wide-FOV-based Rx is typically recommended for a V2V-VLC to solve the practical constraint of mobility, as stated in [46].

Now, we examine the diversity order for the moderate fog ABER performance curve. For instance, ABER is 1.268×10^{-2} at 5 dB and 1.07×10^{-4} at 15 dB. Thus the slope can be obtained as $\log_{10}(1.268 \times 10^{-2}/1.07 \times 10^{-4})$, which is approximately equal to 2 (i.e., full diversity).

Observation 4.4: We also gain comparative insights concerning the ABER performance for scenarios 1 and 2, shown in Figs. 4.7 and 4.8, respectively. For instance, the ABER for scenario 1 is higher when the SNR is 15 dB with $\Psi = 180^\circ$ and the weather is dense fog. It demonstrates the combined impact of the vehicle’s random lateral movement and the deterioration in the weather on the performance of the V2V-VLC system under consideration.

Figure 4.9: Impact of the average path loss corresponding to the proposed LOS V2V-VLC propagation model under different weather conditions [**(-) sign in the path loss values indicates the loss in the form of a path loss penalty**].

4.6.4 Path Loss and DCMC Capacity Considering the Outdoor Propagation Characteristics of Table 4.2

In the previous results of the path loss, we did not consider the impact of the critical outdoor propagation characteristics highlighted in Table 4.2. In this subsection, we will envision the impact of all the propagation characteristics highlighted in Table 4.2 on the proposed V2V-VLC model. Moreover, we will also envision the DCMC capacity corresponding to the proposed LOS and NLOS V2V-VLC propagation models. Figure 4.9 presents the proposed closed-form LOS path loss expression (considering the V2V-VLC propagation model of Fig. 4.1) given in (4.63) as a function of the transmission distance d . We also incorporate the simulation curve to acknowledge the accuracy of the derived path loss expression. Moreover, a V2V-VLC scenario, wherein there is no physical obstruction (for example, an IV) between the Tx and Rx is considered. Further, the path loss curves for different weather scenarios are plotted as shown in Fig. 4.9. Note that, the **negative sign** indicates the loss in the path loss values. Therefore,

Figure 4.10: Comparative average path loss corresponding to the LOS and NLOS V2V-VLC propagation models under moderate fog weather conditions.

the path loss increases with the increase in the transmission distance, as illustrated in Fig. 4.9. Furthermore, the **path loss penalties**, for example, at $d = 30$ m for moderate and dense fog weather conditions are ≈ 2 and 5 dB, respectively, compared with the clear weather.

Observation 4.5: To observe the impact of the considered propagation characteristics on the proposed V2V-VLC model, we also compare the path loss performance with a recent path loss model [46] for a worst-case (dense fog)-based weather scenario. It can be observed from Fig. 4.9 that there is a path loss penalty of ≈ 6 dB w.r.t. the conventional path loss model of [46]. Therefore, the propagation characteristics considered in this work (highlighted in Table 4.2) have a significant impact on V2V-VLC performance.

In Fig. 4.10, we demonstrate the proposed closed-form path loss expressions corresponding to the LOS, NLOS-IV, and NLOS-RS V2V-VLC scenarios under **moderate fog** weather conditions. For the NLOS scenarios (both IV and RS), it is assumed that the LOS path is blocked by any other parked/mobile vehicle in the vicinity, and hence

Figure 4.11: Impact of the lane width on the average path loss corresponding to the NLOS-road surface scenario under dense fog weather conditions.

only the NLOS link is available for communication. It can be seen from Fig. 4.10 that the path loss performance corresponding to the NLOS-road surface V2V-VLC scenario is the best, whereas the path loss performance corresponding to the LOS V2V-VLC scenario is the worst. However, the path loss performance for the NLOS-IV V2V-VLC scenario lies in-between. Further, the **path loss penalties** corresponding to the LOS and NLOS-IV V2V-VLC scenarios are ≈ 20 and 10 dB, compared to the NLOS-road surface V2V-VLC scenario.

Observation 4.6: Based on the results presented in Fig. 4.10, we infer some **striking insights**. Under foggy weather conditions, the NLOS-road surface link is the most suitable in terms of reliable communication. **It is mainly because of the wet road surface conditions.** We also provide the **insightful reasoning** for the results presented in Fig. 4.10 and the related discussion. Considering Eqs. (4.63), (4.66), and (4.69), we define $A \triangleq z_2 - z_1$, $B \triangleq (y_2 - y_1)(x_2 - x_1)$, and $C \triangleq (s_2 - s_1)(r_2 - r_1)(s_1 s_2)$. For any value of $I_{V_1-V_2}$ considered in Fig. 4.10, the ordering for the numerical values of A , B , and C is $A < B < C$. Moreover, $h_{\text{LOS}}^{\text{PL,av}} \propto \frac{1}{A}$, $h_{\text{NLOS,IV}}^{\text{PL,av}} \propto \frac{1}{B}$, and $h_{\text{NLOS,RS}}^{\text{PL,av}} \propto \frac{1}{C}$.

Figure 4.12: Ergodic DCMC capacity (dependent on average path loss) corresponding to LOS and NLOS V2V-VLC propagation models under moderate fog weather conditions.

Therefore, taking into account all the above considerations, the path loss curves show the behavior as presented in Fig. 4.10.

In Fig. 4.11, we examine the **impact of lane width (W_L)** on the average path loss corresponding to NLOS-RS, i.e., (4.69), under dense fog weather conditions. **It is to be noted that the lane width has a significant impact on the lateral movement (mobility) of the vehicle.** Therefore, investigation of the path loss under such a scenario is of significant interest. In Fig. 4.11, we demonstrate the average path loss values corresponding to (4.69) for varying values of W_L and a set of Rx aperture diameter values, i.e., D_R . Note that as lane width increases, the lateral movement of the vehicle increases, and consequently, the path loss also increases. To this end, for minimizing the path loss, the Rx aperture diameter needs to be increased. **As illustrated in Fig. 4.11, for $W_L = 3.4$ m and considering the path loss values of ≈ 4 dB, ≈ 3 dB, and ≈ 2 dB, the suitable ranges for the Rx aperture diameter are 2-3 cm, 3-4 cm, and 4-5 cm, respectively.** Similarly, for other

Table 4.4: Values of the difference factor $z_2 - z_1$ corresponding to (4.63)

$I_{V_1-V_2}$ (m)	Value of $z_2 - z_1$
20	0.69
40	0.35
60	0.23
80	0.17
100	0.14
120	0.11
140	0.1
160	0.08

specific values of W_L and the corresponding path loss values, the suitable ranges for the Rx aperture diameter can be examined.

Figure 4.12 depicts the ergodic DCMC capacity versus the transmission distance. We use (4.75) to plot the ergodic DCMC capacity values of the considered V2V-VLC system under a moderate-fog-based weather scenario. It can be seen from (4.75) that the DCMC capacity is **highly dependent** on the $h_{\text{LOS}}^{\text{PL,av}}$, $h_{\text{NLOS-IV}}^{\text{PL,av}}$, and $h_{\text{NLOS-RS}}^{\text{PL,av}}$ as given in Eqs. (4.63), (4.66), and (4.69), respectively. Accordingly, three different DCMC capacity curves (corresponding to LOS, NLOS-IV, and NLOS-rs) are presented in Fig. 4.12. **It can be observed from Eqs. (4.63), (4.66), and (4.69) that the path loss is inversely proportional to the difference factor. For example, the difference factor $z_2 - z_1$ (for a fixed W_v and W_L) corresponding to $h_{\text{LOS}}^{\text{PL,av}}$ in (4.63). To be more specific, taking (4.63) into account, $C_{\text{DCMC}}^{\text{Ergodic}}$ is inversely proportional to $z_2 - z_1$. Therefore, as d increases, the difference factor $z_2 - z_1$ decreases (as shown in Table 4.4), and consequently, the ergodic DCMC capacity increases, as shown in Fig. 4.12.** Similar analogy holds for the path loss Eqs. (4.66) and (4.69). *The most crucial parameter of DCMC capacity is the value of d at which the V2V-VLC channel capacity attains 90 % of C_{max} (maximum attainable capacity as shown in the Fig. 4.12.)* Further, the channel capacity (**maximum throughput**) signifies the highest rate of information transfer to achieve a small target bit error rate (BER). Therefore, an inverse relationship exists between channel capac-

ity and BER [129]. Furthermore, since channel capacity and BER are comparable, we can anticipate that the BER performance will also provide similar insights for the considered V2V-VLC system.

Remark 4.18: Considering Fig. 4.12, at $d = 110$ m, the difference factor, for example, $z_2 - z_1$ in Eq. (4.63) (LOS scenario) takes the minimum value (rounded upto one decimal). Accordingly, the $C_{DCMC}^{\text{Ergodic}}$ is maximum at $d = 110$ m. Similar analogy is valid for path loss Eqs. (4.66) and (4.69). For the illustration purpose, we consider the LOS scenario and demonstrate the different values of the difference factor $z_2 - z_1$ for the considered transmission range in Table 4.4. It can be observed in Table 4.4 that as d increases, the value of the difference factor $z_2 - z_1$ decreases. Since $C_{DCMC}^{\text{Ergodic}}$ is inversely proportional to $z_2 - z_1$, therefore, $C_{DCMC}^{\text{Ergodic}}$ increases.

Observation 4.7: We infer some **striking insights** based on the DCMC capacity curves presented in Fig. 4.12. Firstly, for an ideal (LOS) V2V-VLC scenario, 90 % of C_{max} is attained at $d \approx 85$ m. However, considering an NLOS-IV based scenario, 90 % of C_{max} is attained at $d \approx 120$ m. On the other side, for an NLOS-RS based scenario, only 80 % of C_{max} is attained, and at a high value of the transmission distance. Further, considering the **crossover** of DCMC capacity curves ($C_{DCMC}^{\text{hPL,av,NLOS,IV}}$ and $C_{DCMC}^{\text{hPL,av,NLOS,RS}}$), **it can be observed that the road surface reflection (NLOS-RS) is more worth compared to NLOS-IV but for a reasonable range of the transmission distance.**

4.7 Conclusions

Considering practical concerns, a thorough V2V-VLC model has been proposed, and its performance using various metrics is examined. Under various weather conditions, the proposed V2V-VLC model's performance has been examined. In addition, a new channel model that considers the combined effect of path loss and atmospheric turbulence is taken into account. Two practical V2V-VLC scenarios have been proposed. In scenario 1, the deterministic longitudinal separation between two vehicles and the random lateral shift of vehicles are taken into consideration, whereas in scenario 2,

the longitudinal separation between two vehicles and the lateral shift of vehicles are taken into consideration as being random and deterministic, respectively. It has been noted that the path loss penalty for the examined V2V-VLC system under the vehicle's random lateral movement is of notable importance. Also, when taking scenario 2 into account, it is found that the longitudinal separation has less of an effect on the ABER performance under clear and mild fog weather conditions. Moreover, it has been noted that path loss and atmospheric turbulence together have a considerable impact on the V2V-VLC system. Finally, by examining the diversity property, the reliability of the studied V2V-VLC system has been confirmed. Additionally, the effects of various real-time outdoor propagation parameters on the proposed V2V-VLC LOS and NLOS models are also investigated. It has been found that the proposed LOS and NLOS V2V-VLC propagation models are significantly impacted by the practical outdoor V2V-VLC propagation characteristics.

Chapter 5

Modeling of Outdoor V2V-VLC System Under Shadowing

In the previous chapter, the impact of shadowing/blocking is not addressed properly. Therefore, we focus on a comprehensive V2V-VLC model in this chapter considering a shadowing-based communication scenario. Moreover, contrary to the previous chapter, the proposed V2V-VLC model in this chapter emphasizes a 2×2 MIMO system, i.e., two TxS and two RxS are considered. Also, contrary to the previous chapter, the performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model is analyzed with the DMT metric. Apart from the shadowing, the outage of the V2V-VLC link is also considered. Further, to minimize the path loss at the Rx, a novel hemispherical optical concentrator-based Rx structure (offering an omnidirectional gain) is also proposed. It is observed that the proposed Rx structure enhances the DMT performance gain significantly. Furthermore, we derive novel closed-form expressions for path loss, outage probability (in terms of the multiplexing gain and other VLC parameters), and outage diversity order. Finally, we also develop a MATLAB-based platform to validate our derived analytical results.

5.1 Introduction

In a LOS VLC system, the communication link may experience temporary shadowing due to physical obstructions by vehicles in the same lane or nearby parked vehicles [57].

Publication based on this chapter is [J4].

Shadowing can lead to the increased path loss and therefore received signal power fluctuation and eventually, the link failure [1]. To this end, let us summarize the importance of shadowing in terms of its modeling and its critical impact on the V2V-VLC system with the help of the following supporting statements:

- In the existing works, such as [46, 49], an ideal V2V-VLC scenario has been investigated without considering the shadowing due to the presence of nearby parked/mobile vehicles (i.e., acting as a physical obstruction between the Tx and the Rx).
- In real-world scenarios, there may be a temporary break in the LOS communication between two vehicles due to the lateral shift (lateral movement) of one of the vehicles, where the LOS path is blocked by other nearby vehicles, thus affecting the link performance. Therefore, investigating the channel model incorporating shadowing, is essential to represent practical V2V communication scenarios. Therefore, in this chapter, a more realistic V2V-VLC system is modeled and analyzed.

Further, the DMT has been analyzed mostly for the RF systems. In [58], DMT was analyzed for general fading channels. A partial CSIT-based DMT was investigated in [59]. There are a few works such as [60], investigating the DMT for a real and non-negative optical signal. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is no work emphasizing the DMT of outdoor V2V-VLC scenario. Motivated by the aforesaid discussion, the chapter has the following contributions:

- A V2V-VLC model under shadowing is proposed. Apart from the shadowing, outage of the V2V-VLC link is also considered. The performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model is analyzed with the DMT metric.
- For the proposed V2V-VLC model, we consider the composite channel with the combined effect of shadowing and AT [1] to analyze the optimal DMT.
- To minimize the path loss at the Rx, a novel hemispherical optical concentrator-based Rx structure (offering an omnidirectional gain) is also proposed. It is

observed that the proposed Rx structure enhances the DMT performance gain significantly. Moreover, the performance of the proposed Rx structure is also compared with the conventional single photon avalanche diode (SPAD)-based Rx [46].

- For the proposed V2V-VLC model, we derive novel analytical expressions for the path loss, PDF of the channel matrix, joint PDF of the ordered singular values of the channel matrix, outage probability (in terms of the multiplexing gain and other VLC parameters), and outage diversity order.
- An optimization problem formulation-based technique is adopted to derive the optimal DMT. Moreover, to validate our derived results, we have developed a MATLAB software-based platform.

5.2 Preliminaries

The proposed V2V-VLC system model, channel model, noise model, proposed Rx structure, and various definitions are presented in this section.

5.2.1 Proposed V2V-VLC System Model under Shadowing and AT

We propose a V2V, VLC-based $N_t \times N_r$ system model with N_t and N_r number of TxS and RxS, respectively. The proposed system model considers two communicating vehicles (vehicle 1 and vehicle 2) as shown in Fig. 5.1. Two LED-based headlamps of vehicle 1 are used as the TxS, i.e., Tx1 and Tx2. An optimal selective combining-based Rx with two receiving front-ends is employed at the back of vehicle 2, which is separately shown in Fig. 5.2. The transmitted light signal can arrive at the Rx via (i) LOS; and (ii) NLOS paths. The NLOS paths are mainly due to the reflection from the road surface and the parked/mobile vehicles near to the two communicating vehicles. Note that, **(i) reflections from the road surface are lower in intensities compared to reflected light beams from other vehicles, and they may become**

Figure 5.1: The schematic illustration of the considered V2V-VLC model under shadowing and AT.

dominant under wet/icy surfaces, and (ii) in a practical V2V scenario, two vehicles within the same lane may not be in full alignment with each other. Therefore, any misalignment i.e., slight lateral shift (see Fig. 5.1) between vehicles will result in no LOS path, and therefore, the transmission being established via NLOS paths from other vehicles nearby. Note that, $dh_{i,j}$ is the lateral shift of the vehicle with respect to (w.r.t.) the j^{th} Tx ($j = 1, 2$) and the i^{th} Rx ($i = 1, 2$). Further, W_L and W_v denote the width of the lane and the vehicle, respectively. The received signal for the proposed V2V-VLC system model is given by:

$$\mathbf{y} = \rho \mathbf{H} \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{e}, \quad (5.1)$$

where ρ denotes the responsivity of the photodiode, $\mathbf{y} = [y_1, y_2]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 1}$ is the received signal vector, $s \geq 0$ (an OOK symbol) is the visible-light signal from the two Txes, and $\mathbf{e} = [e_1, e_2]^T$, denotes the noise vector. At a particular hemispherical optical concentrator (i^{th} receiving front-end as shown in Fig. 5.2), the received signal corresponding

Figure 5.2: The proposed Rx structure.

to the j^{th} transmitting LED can be written as:

$$y_i = \rho \sum_{j=1}^2 h_{i,j} s + e_i. \quad (5.2)$$

Remark 5.1: In Fig. 5.1, the geometry shown between vehicles 1 and 2 applies to one of the two receiving front-ends. A similar geometry applies to the other receiving front-end, which is not shown in the figure. A detailed discussion regarding the proposed Rx structure will be given in Subsection 5.2.4.

A maximum-likelihood detector-based Rx for the considered V2V-VLC model is given by:

$$\hat{s} = \min_{s \in \{0,1\}} \left| y_i - \rho \sum_{j=1}^2 h_{i,j} s \right|^2, \quad (5.3)$$

where \hat{s} denotes the detected symbol at the Rx.

5.2.2 Channel Model

We consider the composite channel with the combined effect of shadowing and AT. We aim to investigate the **impact** of the shadowing-based transmission scenario on the path loss of the considered V2V-VLC system. Because of the high dependency of the VLC on the LOS path, a shadowing-based transmission scenario will significantly impact the path loss due to the **LOS blockage** and hence, the overall performance of the considered V2V-VLC system. Note, AT is a random phenomenon, which occurs due to the changes in the temperature induced refractive index. In (5.1), \mathbf{H} denotes the 2×2 MIMO channel matrix corresponding to the j^{th} Tx and the i^{th} receiving front-end. Note that, an (IM-DD) VLC scheme is used [1], for which the channel coefficients are real and positive. Moreover, each element in \mathbf{H} can be modeled as:

$$h_{i,j} = h_{\text{eff}}^{\text{PL}} h_{i,j}^{\text{Turb}}, \quad i, j = 1, 2 \quad (5.4)$$

where $h_{i,j}$ denotes the channel coefficient and $h_{\text{eff}}^{\text{PL}}$ represents the effective path loss at the Rx concerning the LOS and NLOS, which is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} h_{\text{eff}}^{\text{PL}} &= \sum_{d=0}^{n_d} h^{\text{PL}}(d) = h^{\text{PL}}(0) + \sum_{d=1}^{n_d} h^{\text{PL}}(d) \\ &= p \left(n_d h^{\text{PL}}(d) \right) + (1-p) \left((n_d + 1) h^{\text{PL}}(0) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (5.5)$$

where $h^{\text{PL}}(0)$ and $\sum_{d=1}^{n_d} h^{\text{PL}}(d)$ denote the path losses for the LOS and NLOS, respectively, and n_d is the number of diffused signal components. Further, p denotes the probability corresponding to LOS blockage, i.e., a shadowing-based transmission scenario.

Remark 5.2: Note that, the effective path loss ($h_{\text{eff}}^{\text{PL}}$) in (5.5) is part of the channel gain as depicted in (5.4). A light beam from the LED Tx may arrive at the Rx via the LOS and NLOS paths, see Fig. 5.1. The NLOS paths (n_d) could be from the road surface or the nearby vehicles. Accordingly, the **effective** (LOS+NLOS) path loss w.r.t. the Rx is mathematically expressed in the first line of (5.5). Note, the first and second terms in the second line of (5.5) corresponds to the path losses at the Rx when the LOS path is experiencing blocking and no blocking with the probabilities of

p and $1-p$, respectively. **Moreover, the path loss expression in (5.5) is possible only because the channel is real in contrast to the RF channel.**

Furthermore, $h_{i,j}^{Turb}$ denotes the AT that signifies the impact of environmental conditions. Since VLC using LED lights is mostly intended for short-distance communications, without loss of generality, the PDF of $h_{i,j}^{Turb}$ can be modeled as a log-normal distribution as given by [1, Chapter 3]:

$$f_{h_{i,j}}^{Turb}(h_{i,j}^{Turb}) = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\left(\ln(h_{i,j}^{Turb})+2\sigma_x^2\right)^2}{8\sigma_x^2}\right)}{2h_{i,j}^{Turb}\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_x^2}}, \quad h_{i,j}^{Turb} > 0 \quad (5.6)$$

where the log-intensity variance $\sigma_l^2 = 4\sigma_x^2$.

5.2.3 Noise Model

The ambient-induced shot noise dominates particularly in the afternoon where the sun is low. Both the shot noise and the thermal noise can be modeled as Gaussian noise [123]. Let us denote the variance of the noise e_i by σ_i^2 , which is given by [123]:

$$\sigma_i^2 = \sigma_{i,Shot}^2 + \sigma_{Thermal}^2, \quad (5.7)$$

where $\sigma_{i,Shot}^2$ is the shot noise variance, and it is given as:

$$\sigma_{i,Shot}^2 = 2q\rho BP_{i,R} + 2qBJ_2I_{bg}, \quad (5.8)$$

where q is the electronic charge, ρ is the optical-to-electrical conversion efficiency, B is the equivalent noise bandwidth, J_2 is the noise bandwidth factor corresponding to a rectangular transmitter pulse shape, and I_{bg} is the background induced current. Further, the received average optical power is given by [1]:

$$P_{i,R} = P_t h_{i,j}, \quad (5.9)$$

where P_t corresponds to the average transmit optical power per LED. Furthermore, the thermal noise in (5.7) results from the two FET-based transimpedance preamplifiers employed in the Rx as shown in Fig. 5.2. It mainly includes: the feedback-resistor

Table 5.1: Noise parameter values for the considered V2V-VLC system [123]

Parameter	Value
T_k	298 K
G_{ov}	10
C_f	112 pF/cm ²
g_t	30 mS
Θ	1.5
I_{bg}	5100 μ A

noise and the FET channel noise. Thus $\sigma_{\text{Thermal}}^2$ can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_{\text{Thermal}}^2 = \underbrace{\frac{8\pi K_B T_k}{G_{ov}} C_f A_c J_2 B^2}_{\text{feedback-resistor noise}} + \underbrace{\frac{16\pi^2 K_B T_k \Theta}{g_t} C_f^2 A_c^2 J_3 B^3}_{\text{FET channel noise}}, \quad (5.10)$$

where K_B is Boltzmann's constant, T_k is the absolute temperature in Kelvins, G_{ov} is the open-loop voltage gain, C_f is the fixed capacitance per unit area, and A_c is the area of the hemispherical optical lens employed at the Rx (as depicted in Fig. 5.2). Further, Θ corresponds to the FET channel noise factor, g_t is the FET transconductance, and J_3 is the noise bandwidth factor for a full raised-cosine equalized pulse shape. Moreover, all the noise parameter values are well tabulated in Table 5.1.

5.2.4 Proposed Rx Structure and Effect of Ambient Noise

Generally, in V2V communications, a single photodetector or a camera can be used as the Rx. However, this will not be suitable in the case of the non-directed communication link with shadowing. To overcome this practical constraint, we make use of a novel Rx structure. It is to be noted that, a photodetector with a large area will lead to additional cost to the Rx design. Moreover, it increases the Rx noise. Therefore, to attain a larger signal collection area, we make use of two receiving front-ends, as shown in Fig. 5.2. The two receiving front-ends are hemispherical optical concentrators (L_1 and L_2) with the concentrator diameter D_c , concentrator FOV (Ψ), and internal refractive index (n) [130]. Note that, the hemispherical optical concentrator is best suited for the non-directed communication link [131]. It is mainly due to its ability to achieve a

wide FOV and an omnidirectional gain. *Further, the omnidirectional gain ability of the optical concentrator provides mobility, which is a practical constraint in the V2V-VLC based system. To this end, we also address the concern of mobility under shadowing.* The optical concentrators capture the intensity modulated light signals from the two Tx's. The average electrical SNR at the i^{th} hemispherical optical lens will be [1]:

$$\gamma = \frac{(\rho P_{i,R})^2}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (5.11)$$

where the photodetector responsivity (in A/W) $\rho = (D_c G_c n) \frac{\lambda q}{hc} \rho_{qe} = (D_c G_c n) \frac{\lambda}{1.24} \rho_{qe}$, G_c is the omnidirectional gain of the optical concentrator, λ (the wavelength), and ρ_{qe} is the quantum efficiency [1, Chapter 2]. Moreover, the responsivity expression corresponding to the conventional avalanche photodiode detector (APD)-based Rx is given in [1, Chapter 2]. Note that D_c , G_c and n are not present in the responsivity expression of SPAD-based Rx [46]. The optical band pass filters (BPFs) mounted onto the outer surface of each hemispherical concentrator, as shown in Fig. 5.2, are used to reduce the background induced light, thus improving the SNR [131].

Moreover, optical BPFs minimize the ambient light induced noise, and therefore, the reliability of system performance is guaranteed. To be more specific, optical BPFs minimizes the background light induce shot noise (i.e., improving the SNR) and thereby enhancing the DMT performance. At the bottom of each optical concentrator, a silicon p-i-n photodiode with a fast switching capability is mounted. The optical concentrators are followed by two FET-based transimpedance preamplifiers (A_1 and A_2), which serve the purpose of amplification. Finally, the two receiving branches are connected to a selective combining circuit, in which the branch having the larger SNR is connected to the output.

Definitions

In this subsection, we introduce some basic definitions that will be used throughout this chapter.

1. Let d_o and r denote the outage diversity and multiplexing gains, respectively,

which are defined as [60]:

$$d_o \triangleq - \lim_{\gamma \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log P_o(R, \gamma)}{\log \gamma} \text{ and } r \triangleq \lim_{\gamma \rightarrow \infty} \frac{R(\gamma)}{\frac{1}{2} \log \gamma}, \quad (5.12)$$

where $P_o(R, \gamma)$ is the outage error probability.

2. An outage event corresponds to a scenario where the channel does not support a target data rate. In other words, when the instantaneous channel capacity $C(\mathbf{H})$ is less than the target data rate $R(\gamma)$. Mathematically, we have:

$$P_o(R, \gamma) \triangleq \Pr(C(\mathbf{H}) < R(\gamma)), \quad (5.13)$$

where $\Pr(\cdot)$ denotes the probability and is defined over the random channel matrix \mathbf{H} . Also, the ergodic channel capacity is defined by [132]:

$$C(\gamma) \triangleq \frac{1}{2} \log \left(1 + \Delta \right), \quad (5.14)$$

where $\Delta = \gamma \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_r} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} h_{ij} \right)^2}{N_t N_r}$ denotes the received SNR for equal gain combining (EGC), whereas $\Delta = \gamma \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_r} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_t} h_{ij} \right)^2}{N_t^2 N_r}$ for maximum ratio combining (MRC).

Remark 5.3: The factor half in (5.14) is due to the half degrees of freedom offered by the real-valued channel coefficients. Note that, the proposed 2×2 V2V-VLC model takes into account the selective combining at the Rx, as shown in Fig. 5.2. However, considering a **general** MIMO system (N_t TxS and N_r RxS), one needs to apply a combining technique at the Rx (EGC/MRC). To this end, we will present the DMT analysis for a general MIMO system.

3. It is to be noted that, $r \in (0, q)$, and q is the maximum multiplexing gain in the free space channel. Moreover, we define $g \triangleq \max(N_t, N_r)$ and $q \triangleq \min(N_t, N_r)$.

$$h_i^{PL}(D, dh_{i,j}) = p \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^2 \left(\left(\frac{D_c (\cos(\phi_{i,j}))^{1/\epsilon}}{\zeta D_{i,j}} \right)^2 \exp(-c D_{i,j}) \right) \right) + (1-p) \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^2 \left(\left(\frac{D_c (\cos(\phi_{i,j}))^{1/\epsilon}}{\zeta D_{i,j}} \right)^2 \exp(-c D_{i,j}) \right) \right). \quad (5.15)$$

Table 5.2: Extinction and correction coefficients for different weather conditions [129, Chapter 3], [46]

Weather Condition	c	$\zeta(\text{rad})$	ϵ
Clear Weather	0	0.1585	0.0175
Moderate Fog	0.00782	0.1600	0.0172
Dense Fog	0.01565	0.1550	0.0170

5.3 Average Path Loss Calculations

In V2V-VLC communications, the **dependency** of the transmission on the LOS path is **highly critical**. Therefore, any additional path losses due to other factors such as shadowing/blocking will have a **significant** impact on the performance of the link. Therefore, these critical considerations will play a vital role in the investigation of the average path loss. To this end, in this section, we investigate the average path loss corresponding to the considered V2V-VLC system.

We build on the path loss formulation [46, Eq.(7)]. However, in our work, we quantify the lateral shift of the vehicle as random, in contrast to [46], wherein it is considered to be predictable. In addition, we propose a novel Rx structure shown in Fig. 5.2 and consider the presence of parked or other moving vehicles close to the two communicating vehicles. Due to this, this work derives a more realistic path loss expression than [46]. The path loss expression in (5.15) is written w.r.t. the i^{th} receiving front-end with shadowing. Note that, D_c is the diameter of the hemispherical optical lens employed at the Rx. Further, $\phi_{i,j}$ and $\psi_{i,j}$, are the angles of irradiance and incidence, between the j^{th} Tx and the i^{th} Rx, respectively. Based on the geometry shown in Fig. 5.1, $\phi_{i,j} = \arccos\left(\frac{D}{D_{i,j}}\right)$, where D is the transmission distance between the two vehicles in metres, $D_{i,j}$ is the LOS propagation distance from the j^{th} Tx to the i^{th} Rx, and c is the extinction coefficient for different weather conditions as given in Table 5.2. According to the geometry depicted in Figs. 5.1 and 5.3, we have $D_{i,j} = \sqrt{D^2 + dh_{i,j}^2}$. Further, $dh_{i,j} = dL_i \pm (\Delta_{tx}/2)$, where dL_i is the lateral shift of the vehicle towards the left or rightwards direction w.r.t. the i^{th} Rx, and Δ_{tx} is the horizontal separation between the two Tx's. In Fig. 5.3, the lateral shift of the

- $dh_{i,j}$ is the lateral shift w.r.t j^{th} Tx and i^{th} Rx.

Figure 5.3: Geometry corresponding to the lateral shift of the vehicle w.r.t the i^{th} receiving front-end.

vehicle is shown for the leftward direction, and a similar geometry can be shown for the rightward lateral movement. Further, ζ and ϵ are the correction coefficients (values are given in Table 5.2) for different weather conditions. Since $\cos(\phi_{i,j}) = \frac{D}{D_{i,j}}$, and considering (5.5), we can express (5.15) as:

$$\begin{aligned}
h_i^{PL}(D, dh_{i,j}) &= p \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^2 \left(n_d \frac{D_c^2 D^{2/\epsilon}}{\zeta^2 D_{i,j}^{2+2/\epsilon}} \exp(-cD_{i,j}) \right) \right) \\
&+ (1-p) \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^2 \left((n_d + 1) \frac{D_c^2 D^{2/\epsilon}}{\zeta^2 D_{i,j}^{2+2/\epsilon}} \exp(-cD_{i,j}) \right) \right). \quad (5.16)
\end{aligned}$$

Now, we consider $dh_{i,j}$ to be uniformly distributed, i.e., $dh_{i,j} \sim \mathcal{U} \left(\frac{W_v}{2}, W_L - \frac{W_v}{2} \right)$. Accordingly, $D_{i,j} \sim \mathcal{U} \left(f_1 = \sqrt{D^2 + \frac{W_v^2}{4}}, f_2 = \sqrt{D^2 + \left(W_L - \frac{W_v}{2} \right)^2} \right)$. Note that, the geometrical meaning of the uniform distribution of the lateral shift in the given interval represents the possible range of lateral shift of the vehicle for the given lane and the

vehicle width. Thus the average path loss can be expressed:

$$(h_i^{PL}(D, dh_{i,j}))^{avg} = \int_0^\infty h_i^{PL}(D, dh_{i,j}) f_{D_{i,j}}(D_{i,j}) dD_{i,j}, \quad (5.17)$$

where $f_{D_{i,j}}(D_{i,j})$ is defined by:

$$f_{D_{i,j}}(D_{i,j}) \triangleq \begin{cases} \frac{1}{f_2 - f_1}, & f_1 \leq D_{i,j} \leq f_2 \\ 0, & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases} \quad (5.18)$$

Therefore, on substituting (5.16) and (5.18) into (5.17), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} (h_i^{PL}(D))^{avg} &= p \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^2 \left(n_d \frac{D_c^2 D^{2/\epsilon}}{\zeta^2 (f_2 - f_1)} \right) \times \right. \\ &\quad \left. \int_{f_1}^{f_2} \exp(-cD_{i,j}) \frac{1}{D_{i,j}^{2+2/\epsilon}} dD_{i,j} \right) \\ &\quad + (1-p) \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^2 \left((n_d + 1) \frac{D_c^2 D^{2/\epsilon}}{\zeta^2 (f_2 - f_1)} \right) \times \right. \\ &\quad \left. \int_{f_1}^{f_2} \exp(-cD_{i,j}) \frac{1}{D_{i,j}^{2+2/\epsilon}} dD_{i,j} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (5.19)$$

Let $J = 2 + \frac{2}{\epsilon}$ and $cD_{i,j} = x$, a closed-form expression corresponding to (5.19) is obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned} (h_i^{PL}(D))^{avg} &= p \left(n_d \frac{D_c^2 D^{2/\epsilon} c^{J-1}}{\zeta^2 (f_2 - f_1)} \times \left[\Gamma(1 - J, f_1 c) - \Gamma(1 - J, f_2 c) \right] \right) \\ &\quad + (1-p) \left((n_d + 1) \frac{D_c^2 D^{2/\epsilon} c^{J-1}}{\zeta^2 (f_2 - f_1)} \times \left[\Gamma(1 - J, f_1 c) - \Gamma(1 - J, f_2 c) \right] \right), \end{aligned} \quad (5.20)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the upper incomplete-gamma function [118]. Thus, the effective path loss at the Rx corresponding to L_1 and L_2 is given by:

$$h_{\text{Eff}}^{PL} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 (h_i^{PL}(D))^{avg} \right). \quad (5.21)$$

5.4 Formulation of the Optimization Problem and DMT Analysis of the V2V-VLC System under Shadowing and AT

An optimization problem is formulated to analyze the optimal DMT for the considered V2V-VLC system. Note that, the optimization problem is formulated over the ordered singular values of the channel matrix. *Moreover, optimal singular values lead to the optimal outage diversity gain, and eventually, the optimal DMT.*

Outage Probability and DMT

We determine the upper bound on the outage probability and develop an analytical framework to obtain the outage probability. On substituting (5.14) into (5.13) and considering the case of EGC, the outage probability can be obtained as:

$$P_o(R, \gamma) = \Pr\left(\frac{1}{2} \log\left(1 + \gamma \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^{N_r} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} h_{ij})^2}{N_t N_r}\right) < R(\gamma)\right). \quad (5.22)$$

Since $h_{i,j}^{Turb} > 0$, then an upper bound of (5.22) can be obtained as expressed in (5.23):

$$\begin{aligned} P_o(R, \gamma) &< P_o^{upper}(R, \gamma) \\ &= \Pr\left(\frac{1}{2} \log\left(1 + \gamma \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_r} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} h_{ij}^2}{N_t N_r}\right) < R(\gamma)\right). \end{aligned} \quad (5.23)$$

Therefore, (5.23) can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} P_o^{upper}(R, \gamma) &= \Pr\left(\frac{1}{2} \log\left(1 + \frac{\gamma}{N_t N_r} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^T)\right) < R(\gamma)\right) \\ &= \Pr\left(\frac{1}{2} \log\left(1 + \frac{\gamma}{N_t N_r} \sum_{i=1}^q \lambda_i\right) < R(\gamma)\right) \\ &= \Pr\left(\frac{1}{2} \log\left(1 + \frac{\sum_{i=1}^q \gamma^{(1-\alpha_i)^+}}{N_t N_r}\right) < R(\gamma)\right). \end{aligned} \quad (5.24)$$

Note that, $\text{Tr}(\cdot)$ denotes trace of $\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^T$. Since we are interested in deriving the optimal outage diversity order, i.e., $d_o^*(r)$, therefore, the last equality comes into account by considering (5.12) and substituting $\lambda_i = \gamma^{-(\alpha_i)^+}$, where x^+ denotes $\max(0, x)$. Here,

α_i indicates the level of the singularity of channel matrix \mathbf{H} and λ_i 's are the real and non-negative eigen values of $\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^T$. Further, larger the α_i 's are, the more singular \mathbf{H} is. Moreover, $\sum_{i=1}^q \gamma^{(1-\alpha_i)^+} \geq \gamma^{\sum_{i=1}^q (1-\alpha_i)^+}$. Thus, the outage probability can be further upper bounded by:

$$P_o^{upper}(R, \gamma) = \Pr\left(\frac{1}{2} \log\left(1 + \frac{\gamma^{\sum_{i=1}^q (1-\alpha_i)^+}}{N_t N_r}\right) < \frac{r}{2} \log \gamma\right). \quad (5.25)$$

Therefore, at very high SNR values, and using (3.8), we may express (5.25) as below:

$$P_o^{upper}(R, \gamma) \doteq \Pr\left[\sum_{i=1}^q (1 - \alpha_i)^+ < r\right]. \quad (5.26)$$

Now, the outage probability can be determined as the probability that $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$:

$$P_o(R, \gamma) \doteq \int_{\mathcal{A}} p(\alpha) d\alpha, \quad (5.27)$$

where $p(\alpha)$ represents the joint PDF of α_i 's. Further, the PDF of α in terms of the PDF of \mathbf{H} , when \mathbf{H} is real, which is derived as:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{(\alpha)}(\alpha) &= \Omega_{N_t, N_r} \times (\log \gamma)^q \times \left(\prod_{i=1}^q \gamma^{\left(\frac{-(g-q+1)\alpha_i}{2}\right)^+} \right) \\ &\times \prod_{i < j} \left| \sum_{i=1}^q \gamma^{-(\alpha_i)^+} u_i u_i^T - \sum_{j=1}^q \gamma^{-(\alpha_j)^+} u_j u_j^T \right| \\ &\times \left[\int_{\mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_r}} \int_{\mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_t}} p_{\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{Q})} d\mathbf{Q} d\mathbf{U} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (5.28)$$

where Ω_{N_t, N_r} is a normalization constant, $\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}\{\gamma^{-\alpha_1/2}, \dots, \gamma^{-\alpha_q/2}\}$, $\text{diag}(\cdot)$ denotes the diagonal, \mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_r} and \mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_t} are the Stiefel manifolds [120], and \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{U} are unitary matrices in the singular value decomposition (SVD) of \mathbf{H} .

Remark 5.4: We adopt a Jacobian-based technique to derive the joint PDF of α_i 's. The joint PDF of α_i 's, i.e., $p_{(\alpha)}(\alpha)$ given in (5.28), is derived by determining Jacobian of SVD of \mathbf{H} and the eigen value decomposition of $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{U}^T$, where $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times S}$ is a symmetric matrix with certain properties. **The detailed proof is given in Appendix J.**

On substituting (5.28) into (5.27), the outage probability becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
P_o(R, \gamma) &\doteq \int_{\mathcal{A}} \Omega_{N_t, N_r} \times (\log \gamma)^q \times \left(\prod_{i=1}^q \gamma^{\left(\frac{-(g-q+1)\alpha_i}{2}\right)^+} \right) \\
&\times \prod_{i < j} \left| \sum_{i=1}^q \gamma^{-(\alpha_i)^+} u_i u_i^T - \sum_{j=1}^q \gamma^{-(\alpha_j)^+} u_j u_j^T \right| \\
&\times \left[\int_{\mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_r}} \int_{\mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_t}} p_{\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{Q})} d\mathbf{Q} d\mathbf{U} \right] d\alpha. \tag{5.29}
\end{aligned}$$

Taking (5.12) into account, we are interested in the SNR exponent to derive $d_o^*(r)$. Hence, we can approximate the integral given in (5.29). Firstly, the term $\Omega_{N_t, N_r} (\log \gamma)^q$ has no impact on the γ exponent, and therefore can be neglected. Secondly, bringing orthogonality into account, and for any $j > i$, $\left| \sum_{i=1}^q \gamma^{-(\alpha_i)^+} - \sum_{j=1}^q \gamma^{-(\alpha_j)^+} \right| \doteq \sum_{j=1}^q \gamma^{-(\alpha_j)^+}$, where $(\alpha_j)^+ < (\alpha_i)^+$. Therefore, after employing these approximations, the integral in (5.29) simplifies to:

$$P_o(R, \gamma) \doteq \int_{\mathcal{A}} \gamma^{-\sum_{i=1}^q \left(\left(\frac{g-q+2i-1}{2}\right)\alpha_i\right)^+} \times \left[\int_{\mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_r}} \int_{\mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_t}} p_{\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{Q})} d\mathbf{Q} d\mathbf{U} \right] d\alpha. \tag{5.30}$$

Moreover, the channel gains are independent to each other, hence:

$$p_{\mathbf{H}}(\mathbf{H}) = \prod_{i=1}^{N_r} \prod_{j=1}^{N_t} f_{h_{i,j}}(h_{i,j}), \tag{5.31}$$

where $N_r = N_t = 2$ for a 2×2 MIMO-VLC system.

As for the PDF corresponding to each element in \mathbf{H} , we consider it to be probabilistic. This is mainly due to the presence/absence of objects/obstacles between/or in the vicinity of two communicating vehicles. Let Z be an event corresponding to the PDF associated with the LOS blocking. Therefore, the PMF for this event can be modeled by Bernoulli distribution:

$$\Pr[Z = z] = \begin{cases} p, & z = 1 \\ 1 - p, & z = 0. \end{cases} \tag{5.32}$$

The event $z = 1$ corresponds to an event of PDF of blocked LOS having a probability p . However, when $z = 0$, the VLC channel comprises both the LOS and NLOS paths.

$$\begin{aligned}
P_o(R, \gamma) &\doteq \int_{\mathcal{A}} \gamma^{-\sum_{i=1}^q \left(\left(\frac{g-q+2i-1}{2} \right) \alpha_i \right)^+} \times f(\gamma) d\alpha \\
&\doteq \int_{\mathcal{A}} \gamma^{-\sum_{i=1}^q \left(\left(\frac{g-q+2i-1}{2} \right) \alpha_i \right)^+} (pf^1(\gamma) + (1-p)f^2(\gamma)) d\alpha \quad (5.33)
\end{aligned}$$

$$P_o(R, \gamma) \doteq p \times F + (1-p) \times F, \quad (5.34)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
F &= \gamma^{-\inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^q \left(\left(\frac{g-q+2i-1}{2} \right) \alpha_i \right)^+ - 2\alpha_q + \frac{1}{2\sigma_x^2} \left(4(\sigma_x^2)^2 + \left(\ln(\gamma^{-\frac{\alpha q}{2}}) - \ln \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 (h_i^{PL}(D))^{avg} \right) \right)^2 \right) \right\}} \\
&\times \gamma^{-\inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \left\{ 4\sigma_x^2 \left(\ln(\gamma^{-\frac{\alpha q}{2}}) - \ln \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 (h_i^{PL}(D))^{avg} \right) \right) \right\}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$d_o^*(r) = p \times U + (1-p) \times U, \quad (5.35)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
U &= \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^q \left(\left(\frac{g-q+2i-1}{2} \right) \alpha_i \right)^+ - 2\alpha_q \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2\sigma_x^2} \left(4(\sigma_x^2)^2 + \left(\ln(\gamma^{-\frac{\alpha q}{2}}) - \ln \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 (h_i^{PL}(D))^{avg} \right) \right) \right)^2 \right. \\
&\quad \left. + 4\sigma_x^2 \left(\ln(\gamma^{-\frac{\alpha q}{2}}) - \ln \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 (h_i^{PL}(D))^{avg} \right) \right) \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

Note that, due to the probabilistic nature of PDF (see 5.32), we can express $f(\gamma) = \left[\int_{\mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_r}} \int_{\mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_t}} p_{\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{Q})} d\mathbf{Q} d\mathbf{U} \right] = pf^1(\gamma) + (1-p)f^2(\gamma)$, as given in (5.33). Moreover, at higher SNR values, where $(\gamma \rightarrow \infty)$, we can write $h_{ij} \doteq \gamma^{(\frac{-\alpha q}{2})^+}$, which denotes the term with the highest order. Note that, the term $\left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_x^2}} \right)^4$ can be neglected since it has no effect on the exponent of γ . Therefore, the overall analytical expression for the outage probability is given by (5.34). Furthermore, the overall closed-form expression

concerning the outage diversity order is: $d_o^*(r)$, which is given by (5.35). Moreover, $q = \min(N_t, N_r) = 2$, for a 2×2 MIMO channel matrix.

Remark 5.5: Because of the **form** of the channel model (depicted in (5.4)), the derived DMT expression in (5.35) is SNR-dependent. Therefore, different to the RF channel models [58, 59], in this work (with the emphasis on the optical wireless channel) a DMT expression that considers **practical** SNR values also, is proposed.

Remark 5.6: The diversity gain in [58] mainly depends on N_t and N_r . Contrary to [24], in this work, the derived DMT expression in (5.35) also depends on other parameters such as (i) optimal singular values of the channel matrix; (ii) log-intensity variance $\sigma_l^2 = 4\sigma_x^2$; (iii) weather conditions (Eq. (5.20)); and (iv) **most importantly, the transmission distance (D), which is much shorter for a V2V-VLC link compared to the RF link**. For example, by exploiting partial CSIT, authors in [59] have shown (see Fig. 2 of [59]) that the diversity gain for a 2×2 MIMO system can be much greater than 4. **This implies that the diversity gain for a $N_t \times N_r$ system is not fixed ($N_t N_r$), rather it can be significantly enhanced by employing certain techniques such as rate adaptation etc., as discussed in [59].** Therefore, (5.35) corresponds to a completely different communication environment.

Remark 5.7: In (5.34) and (5.35), the optimal α'_i s can be obtained by solving the optimization problem subject to the constraints defined in the set \mathcal{A} . For this, we have developed a MATLAB-based platform [131, Chapter 5]. Note that, the optimal α'_i s leads to the optimal outage diversity gain, i.e., $d_o^*(r)$.

5.5 Results And Discussion

The numerical findings from the earlier sections will be presented and discussed thoroughly in this section. The entire discussion is acknowledged with some **striking insights** that have not been recognized so far in the literature. **The optimal DMT for the considered V2V-VLC system with shadowing and different weather conditions is a vital part of our discussion.** It is to be noted that, simulation of (5.35) is not possible. Note that, DMT is a **numerical technique** for analyzing

Table 5.3: Simulation parameters for the considered V2V-VLC system [1], [46]

Parameter	Value
W_L	5 m
W_v	2 m
σ_l^2	0.8
D_c	5 cm
G_c	1
n	1
λ	1500 nm
η	0.6
P_t	10 W
n_d	10
r	2
Δ_{tx}	1.2 m
dL_1	1.6 m
dL_2	1 m

the system performance. Therefore, the derived DMT result in (5.35) cannot be verified through simulations. However, considering [131, Chapter 5], (5.35) is validated using the MATLAB platform. Also, Table 5.3 provides a summary of all the important simulation parameters.

5.5.1 Path Loss Performance

We emphasize some interesting insights into the effect of path loss on the proposed system. Note that, with shadowing, the path loss significantly affects the system performance. It is mainly because of the blocked LOS path. Since VLC is highly dependent on the LOS path, therefore, shadowing has a significant impact on the VLC link. Thus, it is very crucial to envision the effect of path loss on the proposed V2V-VLC system under shadowing. In Fig. 5.4, we show the path loss plots (using (5.21)) as a function of the transmission distance for different weather conditions. As might be predicted, the path loss rises with increasing distance; for example, at a distance

Figure 5.4: Effect of path loss on the proposed V2V-VLC model with $p = 0.5$ [(-) sign in the path loss values indicates the loss in the form of a path loss penalty].

of 50 m, the path loss penalties for moderate and dense fog scenarios are 2 and 4 dB, respectively, in comparison to clear weather.

Observation 5.1: Let us consider a worst-case weather scenario (i.e., dense fog) illustrated in Fig. 5.4. Moreover, let us compare the **link path loss** of the proposed Rx architecture (**based on optical concentrators**) and the conventional **SPAD**-based Rx [46, eq. (4)]. For example, at a distance of 30 m, the proposed V2V-VLC system offers around a 10 dB loss, which is **significant**.

Remark 5.8: The performance gain envisioned in **Observation 5.1** is mainly because of the **superiority** of the proposed Rx design (i.e., employing hemispherical optical concentrators) compared to the **conventional** SPAD-based Rx (known for the better performance under weak signals [46]). *It is to be noted that, the **omni-directional gain** ability of the optical concentrators is the **primary** reason for the achievement of such a performance gain.*

Figure 5.5: Outage performance of the considered V2V-VLC system under shadowing and different weather scenarios.

5.5.2 Outage Performance

In Fig. 5.5, we use (5.34) to plot the outage performance curves for different weather conditions. The value of $p = 1$ corresponds to a perfect blockage of the LOS signal and thereby corresponds to a scenario of perfect shadowing. Recall that, $r \in (0, q)$ and $q = 2$ for a 2×2 MIMO-VLC system. It is intuitive that, as the weather condition deteriorates, a proportional degradation in the outage performance is expected. *However, the interesting observation is that, there is not much deviation in the outage performance despite perfect blocking of the LOS path, i.e., an ideal scenario of shadowing.* It is mainly because of the proposed optimal V2V-VLC system. Further, it is to be noticed that the outage performance shown in Fig. 5.5 is specifically for $D = 20$ m. However, the transmission range higher than 20 m will result in deterioration of the outage performance of the considered V2V-VLC system.

Remark 5.9: Because of the LOS nature of VLC systems, the impact of shadowing and blocking is significant on the link's performance as reported in the literature [57].

Figure 5.6: Optimal DMT performance curves of the considered V2V-VLC system with perfect shadowing under clear weather scenario.

However, it is observed in Fig. 5.5 that the outage performance does not show much deviation despite shadowing. **This is mainly because of the proposed Rx design with hemispherical optical concentrators, which is more suitable for the NLOS links with its omnidirectional gain feature.**

5.5.3 DMT Performance

We plot the optimal DMT performance curves for the proposed V2V-VLC system under different probabilistic scenarios of shadowing. Since diversity gain corresponds to the reliability of the communication system and the multiplexing gain corresponds to the data rate of the system, therefore DMT (a tradeoff between the two gains) plays a significant role in the design of V2V-VLC communication system. The DMT performance curves are plotted for a particular operating SNR and varying values of multiplexing gain, i.e., r . Moreover, we aim to provide the operating points corresponding to a particular operating SNR, which plays a significant role in the design of any communication system. *Note that, the diversity gain at a particular operating SNR*

Figure 5.7: Optimal DMT performance curves of the considered V2V-VLC system with 50 percent shadowing under different weather scenarios.

can be used to estimate the additional SNR required to achieve a specified outage probability. We use (5.35) to plot the optimal DMT curves. The analytical curves are validated by means of MATLAB platform. We consider different weather conditions to observe the impact of the weather conditions on the DMT performance of the proposed V2V-VLC system.

To begin with, we consider a clear weather (a typical sunny day of summer) condition in Fig. 5.6. However, a perfect shadowing scenario is considered, i.e., $p = 1$. The optimal DMT operating points for the proposed system under perfect shadowing are tabulated in Table 5.4. It is to be noted that, as the operational SNR increases, there is a significant improvement in the optimal DMT, see Table 5.4. In Fig. 5.6, we considered a perfect shadowing-based transmission scenario. However, in practice, total blocking of the LOS signal is not possible due to the lateral shift (see Figs. 5.1 and 5.3) of the vehicle. Therefore, in Fig. 5.7, we consider a more realistic transmission scenario by considering $p = 0.5$, i.e., LOS blocking takes place with a 50 % probability. Figure 5.7 illustrates the DMT performance of the considered V2V-VLC system under

Table 5.4: Optimal DMT operating points for the considered V2V-VLC system with perfect shadowing under clear weather scenario

Operating SNR (dB)	$d_o^*(0)$	$d_o^*(2)$
5	≈ 0.5	≈ 0.1
10	≈ 1.8	≈ 0.1
15	3	≈ 0.1
20	≈ 4.8	≈ 0.1
25	7	≈ 0.1

Table 5.5: Optimal DMT operating points for the considered V2V-VLC system with 50 percent shadowing under moderate fog weather scenario

Optical Concentrator Diameter (cm)	$d_o^*(0)$	$d_o^*(2)$
2	≈ 6	1
4	≈ 12	3
6	≈ 17	6
8	≈ 21	8

different weather scenarios. It can be seen from Fig. 5.7 that for the clear weather, the optimal outage diversity gain $d_o^*(0) \approx 7$ is attained at a minimum multiplexing gain ($r = 0$). On the other hand, the optimal outage diversity gains for the moderate and dense fog weather conditions are $d_o^*(0) \approx 6.2$ and $d_o^*(0) \approx 6$, respectively.

Observation 5.2: It can be observed from Fig. 5.7 that the impact of weather conditions on the DMT performance is significant. **For instance, at a minimum multiplexing gain ($r = 0$), there is a reduction of approximately unity outage diversity gain corresponding to the foggy weather conditions compared to the clear weather scenario.**

In Fig. 5.8, we demonstrate the asymptotic (very high SNR) DMT performance curves. It can be seen from Fig. 5.8 that for the considered SNR values, the maximum optimal outage diversity gain is attained for $\gamma = 130$ dB, and given as $d_o^*(0) \approx 150$. Therefore, a significant increase in the diversity gain is observed for an asymptotic

Figure 5.8: Optimal DMT performance of the considered V2V-VLC system at very high SNR values.

scenario. Moreover, for the considered SNR range, i.e., $\gamma = 100 - 130$ dB, accordingly, the diversity gain $d_o^*(0) = 85 - 150$. **Further, compared to Figs. 5.6 and 5.7, there is a significant improvement in the achievable outage diversity gain at $r = 1$ (i.e., half of the maximum multiplexing gain for a 2×2 MIMO V2V-VLC system.)**

In Fig. 5.9, the optimal DMT curves for a realistic transmission scenario is considered. Herein, we consider a *moderate fog* scenario and plot the optimal DMT curves for varying optical concentrator diameter D_c as shown in Fig. 5.9. Moreover, we consider a particular operating SNR for the proposed system. The operating SNR $\gamma = 20$ dB is adopted. The optimal DMT operating points for the proposed system corresponding to a particular value of D_c are tabulated in Table 5.5. To this end, we would like to reflect on a few insights. *The first interesting observation that can be drawn from Fig. 5.9 as compared to the previously discussed DMT results (Fig. 5.8) is the enhanced diversity gain at the maximum multiplexing gain ($r = 2$). Secondly, there is a significant enhancement in the DMT performance gain*

Figure 5.9: Optimal DMT performance curves of the considered V2V-VLC system with 50 percent shadowing under moderate fog weather scenario.

between the two DMT curves as depicted in Fig. 5.9. This enhancement in the DMT performance gain is mainly because of two interesting insights. *Firstly, the moderate fog weather condition corresponds to the improved visibility scenario. Secondly, the increase in the optical concentrator diameter, i.e., D_c , leads to improved signal reception.* Moreover, by utilizing an optical concentrator with a suitable diameter, the reliability of the proposed Rx design can be enhanced. **As shown in Fig. 5.9, for the target diversity gains $d_G^*(0)$ of ≈ 6 , ≈ 5 , and ≈ 4 , the suitable ranges for the optical concentrator diameter are 2-4, 4-6, 6-8 cm, respectively.**

Observation 5.3: With reference to Figs. 5.8 and 5.9, which correspond to the dense and moderate fog conditions, respectively, we observe the **severe** impact of fog on the DMT performance. **However, using optical concentrators with suitable diameter range can improve the diversity gain under the fog condition.** Moreover, it can be envisioned, from Fig. 5.8, that further increasing the SNR will tend the diversity gain to attain an asymptotic value.

Remark 5.10: Most of the literature on DMT, such as [58,59], have considered the

conventional RF channel models, for example, Rayleigh, Nakagami, with no insights on the **impact of outdoor conditions** on the optimal DMT. To this end, by considering an outdoor V2V-VLC system, we show the **joint impact** of weather conditions and shadowing on the optimal DMT, which is **significant**. Moreover, the optimal DMT is analyzed by considering a **more practical real scenario** with shadowing and blocking.

5.6 Conclusions

Due to the wideband nature of VLC, shadowing is a critical issue in fast varying outdoor V2V-VLC environments. Thus in this chapter, a novel V2V-VLC system, under the combined effect of shadowing and atmospheric turbulence (AT) has been modeled, and the considered system performance is analyzed with DMT metric. The optimal DMT has been investigated under different weather conditions and considering different probabilistic scenarios of shadowing for the proposed V2V-VLC system. To validate the derived DMT results, a MATLAB-based platform has also been developed. Moreover, we have considered all the practical/realistic characteristics of vehicular VLC. For instance, shadowing, the asymmetrical radiation pattern of low-beam and high-beam headlamps, environmental conditions, and effect from reflections. Considering the existing literature, most works have considered a wide FOV-based Rx to enhance the signal reception area, ultimately leading to the increased background-induced noise. To mitigate this problem, in this chapter, a hemispherical optical lens-based novel Rx structure has also been proposed to maximize the SNR at the receiver. Contrary to the previous chapter, wherein shadowing is not addressed, in this chapter, we mark interesting key observation. For example, it is observed that the optical concentrators-based Rx structure can significantly enhance the system performance under shadowing. It is mainly because of its omnidirectional gain ability. On the other side, it is observed through the findings of Chapter 4 that the path loss penalty corresponding to a LOS-based (non-shadowing) scenario is mostly dominated at higher values of the transmission distance.

Chapter 6

An Indoor Testbed Design for an Outdoor I2V-VLC System and Experimental Demonstration

To address the challenges of an outdoor next-generation-based ITSs, in this chapter, we emphasize an **experimental approach** to design the indoor testbed for an outdoor I2V-VLC system. Based on an indoor testbed, a realistic I2V-VLC envisions an experimental demonstration of traffic light (roadside infrastructure) to vehicle-based VLC. In order to demonstrate the proposed indoor I2V-VLC under realistic I2V-VLC scenarios, a dedicated testbed is established and validated. To this end, we experimentally investigate the BER to check the reliability of the proposed I2V-VLC system. Additionally, we measure other performance indicators, such as peak SNR (PSNR), capacity, etc., to gain further insights. For the first time, we employ MATLAB coding to control the hardware equipment, which offers flexibility in terms of the system design.

6.1 Introduction

Since road traffic injuries are anticipated to become the fifth leading cause of death by 2030 [134], the corresponding precautionary measures are the need of the hour. Consequently, many research projects have been examined to improve the traffic system.

Publication based on this chapter is [J6].

Therefore, to meet the goal of designing a better traffic system, nowadays, vehicular technology is becoming a vital and emerging area of research in the field of ITSs.

To motivate the significant contributions of this chapter, we give a detailed background on the experimental research efforts on vehicular VLC and I2V-VLC. Considering the experimental works, in [94], experimental results for a 185 m V2V-VLC link with a BER of $10^{-7} - 10^{-6}$ are reported. In [95], using the optical orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OOFDMA)-based uplink for V2V-VLC, it is shown that the LED nonlinear distortion and the shot noise can significantly affect the error vector magnitude due to the out-of-band noise/interference induced inter-user interference. In [96], an experimental investigation illustrating the impact of the interference from lights on the performance of a 25 Mb/s OOK V2V-VLC link is reported. It is shown that the minimum required deviation angle for error-free transmission is 1.5° for a scenario where the transmit optical power and the interference light are almost equal [96]. As a part of the next-generation ITSs (minimizing road accidents), the authors in [97] designed a prototype V2V-VLC system with low complexity and high reliability. Experimental evaluation of the prototype showed that the proposed system can give an early warning to drivers at speeds up to 80 km/h [97]. An experimental investigation of three low-complex optical OFDM (O-OFDM) schemes for vehicular VLC is reported in [98]. Experimental results showed that contrary to simulation results reported in the literature, asymmetrically clipped optical OFDM (ACO-OFDM) outperforms unipolar OFDM (U-OFDM) due to the lower peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) [98]. To alleviate the impact of strong background radiation on OFDM-based outdoor VLC systems, in [99], a novel Rx architecture employing attenuation diversity is proposed. The experimental results showed that with direct current biased optical OFDM (DCO-OFDM) and under strong background lights, the BER is reduced to a reasonable level [99]. In [100], the impact of using different lens combinations in vehicular VLC is experimentally investigated.

Further, in [101], using carrierless amplitude-phase (CAP) modulation, an experimental demonstration of 312.5 Mbit/s CAP vehicular VLC over a 10 m link is reported. In [102], the authors experimentally showed a communication range of at least 50 m.

It is also shown that the initial 2-8 m transmission distance is not covered by the Rx's FOV for vehicles on adjacent lanes [102]. In [103], LED-based V2V-VLC with a modified fixed decision threshold (MFDT) scheme is experimentally investigated, showing that the link is reliable under rain. In [104], an initial experimental investigation of I2V-VLC employing a traffic light-based Tx is reported, where it is shown that the modulation depth can be reduced by 50% in order to track the light source when sending '0'symbol. In [105], an I2V-VLC using a traffic light and a photodiode as the Tx and the Rx, respectively, is investigated, showing a BER of 10^{-3} over a transmission range of up to 188 m. In [106], the performance of multi-hop VLC-based vehicular systems in an outdoor environment is investigated, in terms of SNR during the day and night time. To enhance the SNR of V2V-VLC systems considering the mobility, in [107], the use of dual PDs with selection combining is investigated. In [108], the authors experimentally investigated the effects of fog on the V2V-VLC link when using a camera-based Rx. The results indicated that the link is error-free up to 20 m of visibility for the three modulation index scenarios, and deteriorates below the 10 m meteorological visibility [108].

Considering the above literature background, it is to be noted that most of the existing works on I2V-VLC systems have used street lights as the access point. Note, each street light is connected to a centralized controller (CU) via a wired connection. However, there are two main issues with these, (i) link availability, which highly depends on the CU, where any failure will result in the total communication link failure; and (ii) higher infrastructural overheads and costs, which are not desirable. Further, none of the works reported, e.g., in [14], [15], [89–93], and [104], [105] have experimentally examined the system's performance in a controlled indoor environment. **To this end, we highlight the significant contributions of this chapter as follows:**

- A **comprehensive demonstration** of an I2V-VLC system using an **indoor experimental testbed** is envisioned. We have developed dedicated MATLAB software-based codes for data generation, extracting the data from the captured images (employing a camera as an Rx), controlling the testbed, and all test and measurement equipment.

- Moreover, we experimentally demonstrate the communication between the traffic light (i.e., the Tx) and the camera (i.e., the Rx) under different realistic I2V-VLC scenarios. Different performance metrics are experimentally examined, such as BER, PSNR, and capacity. Some striking insights are envisioned that have not been previously reported in the literature.
- Further, we emphasize the intensity measurements of the Tx and obtain the beam profile using MATLAB software. Based on the beam profile, channel modeling is implemented. Therefore, a more practical approach for the channel modeling is adopted.
- We have considered the vehicle's mobility and its position within different lanes, which introduces a degree of orientation between the camera on the vehicle and the traffic light. Moreover, LOS blockage-based I2V-VLC scenarios are also investigated, and some striking insights are envisioned.
- **Insightful observations** are incorporated for all the experimental results, which reflect the impactful worth of this research work. Moreover, all the **experimental findings** are demonstrated for **different exposure times** of the camera for the first time, which is a very critical parameter when using a camera-based Rx.

6.2 Preliminaries

The proposed I2V-VLC system, the VLC Tx's beam profile, and the channel model are presented and discussed in this section.

6.2.1 Proposed I2V-VLC System

The proposed I2V-VLC system shown in Fig. 6.1 illustrating communication between the roadside traffic light (VLC Tx) and the vehicle, where the vehicle can be in either of the two lanes. The proposed system is composed of a LED (Rebel Star) and a global shutter high-speed optical camera (Canon Rebel SL1 EOS 100D) as the Tx and the

Figure 6.1: Schematic illustration of the proposed I2V-VLC system.

Rx, respectively. Note that, commercial cameras currently available in the new cars can also be utilized as Rx's. In this work, for experimental demonstration purpose, we used a LED as the traffic light, and employed an OOK data stream $u(t)$ for intensity modulation of the Tx. The intensity-modulated light $s(t)$ is transmitted through the wireless channel and captured by a high-speed camera. Therefore, the received signal is given as [130]:

$$y(t) = \rho s(t) \otimes h(t) + n(t), \quad (6.1)$$

where ρ denotes the quantum efficiency of the image sensor (IS) of the camera, \otimes denotes the convolution operator, and $h(t)$ represents the combined impulse response of the channel and camera. Moreover, $n(t)$ denotes the AWGN. Considering the outdoor VLC, the ambient/background-induced noise (n_b) is the dominant noise source. Contrary to [123], where PD is used as an Rx, in this chapter, the ambient-induced shot noise variance corresponding to the noise n_b with the camera as an Rx can be

expressed as:

$$\sigma_{\text{shot}}^2 = \sigma_b^2 = 2\rho B(P_T + P_b)H(0)_{\text{LOS}} + 2BI_{bc}, \quad (6.2)$$

where B is the equivalent noise bandwidth, P_T is the transmit optical power corresponding to the VLC Tx, P_b is the transmit power corresponding to the ambient/background light source, $H(0)_{\text{LOS}}$ is the LOS channel, and I_{bc} is the background noise current. Moreover, the average received optical power corresponding to LOS link at the camera is given by:

$$P_{R,\text{LOS}} = H(0)_{\text{LOS}}(P_T + P_b) + n_b. \quad (6.3)$$

Further, considering Fig. 6.1, the angle of incidence can be written as:

$$\beta = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{H_{T,\text{DB}}}{D_T}\right), 0 < \beta \leq \Psi_C, \quad (6.4)$$

where $H_{T,\text{DB}}$ is the height of the Tx from the camera positioned on the dashboard of the vehicle, and D_T is the horizontal distance between the Tx and the camera. Note that, $H_{T,\text{DB}} = H_{T,\text{RS}} - H_{\text{DB},\text{RS}}$. Moreover, Ψ_C is the FOV of the camera. Now, the LOS propagation distance between the traffic light and the camera can be formulated mathematically as follows:

$$H_{T,\text{DB,LOS}} = \sqrt{H_{T,\text{DB}}^2 + D_T^2}. \quad (6.5)$$

Now, considering the geometric relation given in (6.4), we can observe that the minimum distance D_T for a reliable communication is dependent on the two system parameters:

- The height difference between the traffic light and the camera, i.e., $H_{T,\text{DB}}$.
- The FOV of the camera, whereby the maximum incidence angle β_{max} equals Ψ_C :

$$D_{T_{\text{min}}} = \frac{H_{T,\text{DB}}}{\tan(\beta_{\text{max}})}, \beta_{\text{max}} = \Psi_C \quad (6.6)$$

Figure 6.2: The normalized beam profile of the VLC Tx.

6.2.2 Normalized Beam Profile and Channel Modeling

To visualize the beam profile of the traffic light (VLC Tx), we must measure the radiant intensity (radiant flux per unit solid angle) of the VLC Tx for different orientations/angles. Using a digital Lux Meter (MS 6612), we measured the intensity of the Tx at a distance of 25 cm and for a range of orientations (angles) and display the measured data in the normalized polar plot, as shown in Fig. 6.2. Note that, we convert the angles in degrees to radians while obtaining the polar plot in MATLAB software. The normalized beam profile shown in Fig. 6.2 is close to Lambertian beam profile [130]. Therefore, the channel can be modeled as [69]:

$$H(0)_{\text{LOS}} = \sigma_R^2 \left(\frac{A_{\text{IS}}(K+1)}{2\pi H_{T,\text{DB,LOS}}^2} \cos^K(\alpha) g(\beta) T_s(\beta) \cos(\beta) \right), \quad (6.7)$$

where σ_R^2 is the Rytov variance, which is introduced to incorporate the irradiance fluctuations of the optical signal resulting from turbulence. We will discuss in detail σ_R^2 in Section 6.4. Moreover, $0 \leq \beta \leq \Psi_C$, A_{IS} is the surface of the image of the VLC Tx on the IS of the camera, $g(\beta)$ and $T_s(\beta)$ are the gains of the optical concentrator and the optical filter, respectively. Further, α denotes the irradiance angle, and K is

Lambertian order of emission of the Tx, which is given by [69]:

$$K = -\frac{\ln(2)}{\ln(\cos \theta_{\frac{1}{2}})}, \quad (6.8)$$

where $\theta_{\frac{1}{2}}$ is the half power angle.

6.2.3 Fundamental Definitions

In this subsection, we introduce the fundamental definitions related to the optical camera which is used as the Rx in this work.

- **Exposure:** The amount of light allowed to hit the image sensor of the camera.
- **Exposure time/Shutter speed:** It is the amount of time for which the image sensor is exposed to light.
- **Frame rate:** The amount of time per second the camera reads and records the image is the frame rate.
- **Aperture:** An aperture is a hole or opening through which light travels. The size of the aperture is usually specified as an f-number. A lower f-number denotes a greater aperture opening which allows more light to reach the image sensor.
- **peaksnr=psnr (A,ref)** calculates the peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) for the image A, with the image ref as the reference. A higher PSNR indicates an improved image quality.

6.3 Indoor I2V-VLC Testbed Design Approach and Experimental Lab Setup

This section presents and discusses the indoor experimental testbed for the proposed I2V-VLC mainly comprising the Tx, signal loading, transmission, and decoding.

Figure 6.3: Block diagrammatic representation of the signal generation, loading, transmission, and decoding for the proposed I2V-VLC system.

6.3.1 Tx and Rx

Figure 6.3 presents a detailed block diagram representation of the signal generation, transmission, and decoding processes for the proposed I2V-VLC system. Firstly, an OOK random data stream $u(t)$ is generated in a Laptop/PC, which is then loaded into an arbitrarily waveform generator (AWG), the output of which is used for intensity modulation of the Tx via a LED driver. An optical camera is used on the Rx side to capture the intensity-modulated light $s(t)$ transmitted over the wireless channel. The signal decoding is performed by recording a video stream for a specified period of time in the camera. MATLAB software is used to process the recorded video frame-by-frame off-line using a typical image processing algorithm. Finally, the decoded data stream is compared with the transmitted data stream $u(t)$, and the BER is determined.

Remark 6.1: Two types of optical Rxs are commonly used in VLC systems: (i) PDs; and (ii) ISs cameras [1], [135]. An IS-based Rx is composed of a large number of PDs (in the form of pixels) aligned orthogonally. Moreover, in IS-based VLC systems,

Figure 6.4: Image of the experimental lab setup of a real-time I2V-VLC scenario with the communicating vehicle in lane 1.

Table 6.1: Key geometrical parameters with real-time value and scaled-down values of the experimental setup

Parameter	Real-time (m)	Scaled-down (m)
L_w	3.5	0.70
$H_{T,RS}$	3.5	0.70
$H_{DB,RS}$	2	0.40
$H_{T,DB}=H_{T,RS}-H_{DB,RS}$	1.5	0.30

the SNR is independent of the link length [1], [135], and while the projected image of the transmitting LEDs covers several pixels, the incident light power level per pixel remains unaltered. Since the camera-based Rx is composed of an array of PDs, the SNR is **significantly enhanced**, and correspondingly, the BER is **significantly reduced**. **Motivated by all the above facts, we have adopted camera as an Rx in this work.**

6.3.2 Experimental Setup

In this subsection, we discuss the proposed I2V-VLC experimental setup. Using the developed I2V-VLC testbed, we have carried out a series of tests and measurements for

Table 6.2: Key system parameters of the experimental setup

Parameter	Value
Number of data bits	10,000
Frequency of the transmitted data	30 Hz
Frequency per bit of the transmitted data	0.003 Hz
Amplitude of the transmitted signal (peak-to-peak)	0.1 V
Offset voltage	-0.2 V
$H_{T,RS}$	0.7 m
$H_{DB,RS}$	0.4 m
$H_{T,DB}$	0.3 m
Link span	0.5-6.5 m
Camera type	Canon with Global shutter
International Standard Organisation (ISO) of camera	100
Camera focal length (f)	54 mm
Camera aperture	f5.6
Camera frame rate	60 fps
Camera resolution	1280 × 720
Camera horizontal FOV	60°
LED type	SR-01
LED driver's current	134 mA

both day and night times and demonstrate results for the BER, PSNR, capacity, etc. The image of the real-time experimental setup for the proposed I2V-VLC system is shown in Fig. 6.4. There are two lanes and the vehicle could be in either of them. Note, an additional light source represents the ambient-induced noise source, as illustrated in Fig. 6.4. **Further, it is to be noted that we maintained some degree of misalignment between the Tx and the Rx to represent the random position of a vehicle within the lane (i.e., no direct alignment between the Tx and the camera is assumed), which is experimentally considered for the first time.** Therefore, a realistic I2V-VLC experimental setup is considered in this work.

Remark 2: We have considered the vehicle’s mobility and its position within different lanes (both lanes 1 and 2), which introduces a degree of orientation between the camera (receiver) on the vehicle and the traffic light (transmitter). For instance, the results in Fig. 6.5 are demonstrated for both lanes 1 and 2. Moreover, it is to be noted that we maintain some degree of misalignment between the Tx and the Rx (please see Fig. 6.4) to represent the random position of a vehicle within the lane (i.e., no direct alignment between the Tx and the camera is assumed), which is experimentally considered for the first time. **This random position of the vehicle corresponds to a high-mobility (dynamic) scenario.** Moreover, the fast moving cars may receive reflections from other surface and other cars, which are relatively of low intensities compared to the LOS. Therefore, it will not cause any major issues.

Remark 3: In Fig. 6.4, we have considered an additional light source (a desk top lamp with a standard filament light bulb acting as an ambient background illumination) and placed it close to the transmission path. **To this end, we have demonstrated the worst-case scenario of the outdoor background-induced noise in an indoor environment.** When scaled up, we have ensured that the illumination level is the same as that of the outdoor lighting.

6.4 Experimental Results and Analysis

We experimentally investigate the performance of the proposed I2V-VLC system. To this end, we demonstrate and analyze the following experimental results: (i) BER, (ii) PSNR, and (iii) capacity. Moreover, considering the indoor scenario, we scale down the **key geometrical parameters** for the experimental measurements, as shown in Table 6.1. For instance, we have adopted a scaling factor of 5, i.e., 0.2 per meter. All the **important system parameters** are tabulated in Table 6.2. A detailed information related to the camera used in this work can be found in [136]. **Using the experimental setup, see Fig. 6.4, first we carried out the BER measurement starting for $D_T = 6.5$ m and then moving towards the VLC Tx, i.e., up to $D_T = 0.5$ m.** The experiments were carried out during both day and night times. **Furthermore,**

we have emphasized the performance metrics, which are more appropriate for the system employing a camera as the Rx.

6.4.1 BER without AT

Here, we present and discuss the BER results for the proposed I2V-VLC system without considering the impact of AT. Note that, when using the camera-based Rx, the **most critical parameter** affecting the system performance is the **exposure time** E_T . **Therefore, we present the measured and simulated BER plots against D_T and for different E_T and for the vehicle in lanes 1 and 2 as depicted in Figs. 6.5(a), 6.5(b), and 6.5(c).** For the simulations, a random OOK data stream and the noise were generated in MATLAB. For decoding, a maximum-likelihood detector was adopted. We considered 10^6 channel realizations, which corresponds to each value of D_T , and computed the BER. Note, in all the plots, the lowest BER profiles are observed for E_T of $\frac{1}{500}$. For example, in Fig. 6.5(a), for $E_T = \frac{1}{500}$, BER ≈ 0.047 for D_T of 0.5 and 1.5 m, whereas, for $D_T > 2.5$ m, BER = 0 for all values of E_T . Moreover, for $E_T = \frac{1}{800}$ and $\frac{1}{1000}$, BER ≈ 0.1 for D_T of 0.5 and 1.5 m. Note that, the same BER trends are observed for Figs. 6.5(b) and 6.5(c) with almost identical BER values in Figs. 6.5(a) and 6.5(b). This is because lane changing will not impact the BER performance as long as the Tx is within the FOV of the camera. Considering Fig. 6.5(c), which shows the **BER performance during the night time**, for $E_T = \frac{1}{500}$, BER $\approx 4.5 \times 10^{-3}$, which is the lowest, for D_T of 0.5 and 1.5 m. Whereas, for $E_T = \frac{1}{800}$, BER = 8×10^{-3} for D_T of 0.5 and 1.5 m, increasing marginally to 9×10^{-3} for E_T of $\frac{1}{1000}$ and D_T of 0.5 and 1.5 m.

Observation 6.1: Intuitively, the BER should increase as the transmission distance increases. However, in our case, there is a contradiction. **To clarify this, we put forward some striking insights.** Note, there is a height difference between the VLC Tx and the camera (Rx) given by $H_{T,DB}$ (please see Fig. 6.1). When the Rx is very close to the Tx, for instance, at $D_T = 0.5$ and 1.5 m, the Tx is partially captured by the FOV of the camera due to the height difference. Consequently, the received signal is not properly decoded, and thus leading to some BER. In contrast, when the

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6.5: Measured and simulated BER performance as a function of D_T and for a range of exposure times of the proposed I2V-VLC system for the vehicle in lane: (a) 1 and the daytime, (b) 2 and daytime, and (c) 1 and night time.

Figure 6.6: Image of the experimental lab setup of a real-time I2V-VLC scenario under AT with the vehicle in lane 1 and daytime.

Tx is distant from the Rx, it is completely within the FOV of the camera, resulting in no BER.

Observation 6.2: As shown in Fig. 6.5(c), the lower BER at D_T of 0.5 and 1.5 m is due to the dark environment in the night time as well as the proximity of Rx to the Tx, i.e., brighter captured image by the camera.

Observation 6.3: The BER plots in Fig. 6.5(c) indicate that the additional light source (i.e., the ambient-induced noise source) doesn't have a deteriorating impact on the performance. This is because only the Tx is within the FOV of the camera, see Fig. 6.4.

6.4.2 BER with AT

AT is a random phenomenon that occurs due to the change in the refractive index of air with time along the signal propagation path. It results in amplitude and phase fluctuations of the propagating light beam, which consequently will affect the link performance, i.e., reduced SNR, and increased BER [1]. An important parameter, which is used to characterize the turbulence regime is Rytov variance σ_R^2 , which signifies the irradiance fluctuations of the optical signal arising from turbulence and is given

Figure 6.7: BER performance of the proposed I2V-VLC system under AT for the vehicle in lane 1.

by [137]:

$$\sigma_R^2 = 1.23C_n^2 k^{7/6} D_T^{11/6}, \quad (6.9)$$

where C_n^2 is the refractive index structure parameter, the wave number $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$, and λ is the wavelength. The value of the C_n^2 varies with altitude, but for a horizontally propagating field it is usually assumed constant [1]. C_n^2 typically ranges from $10^{-12} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$ for the strong AT to $10^{-17} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$ for the weak AT with a typical average value being $10^{-15} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$ [1]. Considering the short-transmission range of I2V-VLC, the turbulence regime can be characterized as a weak turbulence regime with $C_n^2 = 10^{-17} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$ and $\sigma_R^2 < 1$ [137]. Further, the image of the experimental setup considering the impact of AT is shown in Fig. 6.6. A hot/cold fan is used to incorporate the impact of AT. Using the experimental setup depicted in Fig. 6.6, we carried out a set of measurements for the BER under AT, see Fig. 6.7. The simulated BER plot for comparison is also shown in Fig. 6.7. Note that, for $E_T = \frac{1}{500}$, BER ≈ 0.07 for D_T of 0.5 and 1.5 m, which then drops to < 0.01 for $2.5 \leq D_T \leq 4.5$. However, beyond $D_T > 4.5$, the BER increases almost linearly. This is because the optical beam is more exposed to the AT.

Figure 6.8: PSNR performance of the proposed I2V-VLC system for the vehicle in lane 1 and daytime.

Moreover, if we further reduce the exposure time to $E_T = \frac{1}{2000}$, which is worst-case, the BER increases significantly, as shown in Fig. 6.7.

Remark 4: In this work, we have examined the performance of the proposed I2V-VLC testbed system by considering the outdoor channel conditions. In particular, we have measured the BER performance without and with AT, as illustrated in Figs. 6.5 and 6.7, respectively.

Observation 4: Considering Fig. 6.5 (demonstrating the BER results without the impact of AT), for any value of $D_T \geq 2.5$ m, $\text{BER} = 0$. Contrary to this, in Fig. 6.7 (demonstrating the BER results under the impact of AT), a non-zero finite value of BER is observed. The BER further increases with D_T . Therefore, the impact of AT becomes dominant at longer transmission distances.

6.4.3 PSNR Results

Another important metric to assess the link quality when using the camera as an Rx is the image quality metric, i.e., PSNR. We use MATLAB command `psnr(A,ref)` to

Figure 6.9: PSNR performance of the proposed I2V-VLC system for the vehicle in lane 2 and night time.

compute the PSNR, which calculates the PSNR for a particular image A, with the image ref as the reference. **A greater PSNR value indicates the better image quality.** To compute the PSNR, we pick a random frame/image corresponding to the recorded video at a particular link length. Therefore, the PSNR measurements corresponding to the randomly picked frames/images are realistic and reflect the link quality of a real-time I2V-VLC environment. Since the VLC Tx is partially captured at D_T of 0.5 and 1.5 m, therefore, we choose the reference image for the PSNR computation corresponding to $D_T = 2.5$ m. To this end, the starting value of D_T for the illustration of the PSNR results is considered to be 3.5 m.

In Fig. 6.8, we demonstrate the PSNR performance of the proposed I2V-VLC system in the daytime and when the communicating vehicle is in lane 1. We consider a reference image corresponding to a recorded video at $D_T = 2.5$ m. This reference image is compared with other images for $D_T = 3.5 - 6.5$ m, and correspondingly, the PSNR is computed, as shown in Fig. 6.8. When $E_T = \frac{1}{500}$ (with maximum exposure time), the minimum and maximum value of PSNR ≈ 38 and 40, respectively. Moreover, when

$E_T = \frac{1}{800}$, the minimum and maximum value of PSNR ≈ 33.3 and 33.8 , respectively. Further, when $E_T = \frac{1}{1000}$, the minimum and maximum value of PSNR ≈ 32.9 and 33.6 , respectively. In Fig. 6.9, we demonstrate the PSNR performance of the proposed I2V-VLC system in the night time with the communicating vehicle in lane 2. When $E_T = \frac{1}{500}$ (with maximum exposure time), the minimum and maximum value of PSNR ≈ 33 and 33.8 , respectively. Moreover, when $E_T = \frac{1}{800}$, the minimum and maximum value of PSNR ≈ 32.9 and 33.6 , respectively. Further, when $E_T = \frac{1}{1000}$, the minimum and maximum value of PSNR ≈ 32.7 and 33.4 , respectively.

Observation 6.4: It can be observed from Fig. 6.8 that as the exposure time reduces, the PSNR also reduces. However, there is not much deviation in the PSNR performance curves corresponding to $E_T = \frac{1}{800}$ and $E_T = \frac{1}{1000}$, respectively. It is mainly because utilizing the camera as an Rx offers enhanced performance, as discussed in Remark 1.

Observation 6.5: It is to be noted that there is a slight deterioration in the PSNR performance, as illustrated in Fig. 6.9, compared to Fig. 6.8. It is mainly because of the background-induced noise (due to the presence of additional light source) as shown in Fig. 6.4.

6.4.4 Capacity Results

In this subsection, we consider another key performance metric (ergodic capacity) to analyze the maximum attainable data rate. The exact expression for ergodic capacity of IM/DD systems is still unknown. However, different bounds on the capacity of optical channels are derived in the literature [80–82]. For instance, it is shown in [82] that the gap between the exact and the lower bound can be neglected for high SNR values and the capacity can be approximated as:

$$C \approx \frac{B}{2 \ln(2)} \ln \left(1 + \frac{\exp(1)\zeta}{2\pi} \right), \quad (6.10)$$

where ζ is the PSNR, as analyzed in the previous subsection, and B is the bandwidth. The bandwidth is computed as:

$$B = \frac{\text{Transmission bit rate (30 bps in our case)}}{\log_2 M \text{ (M = 2 for OOK modulation scheme)}}. \quad (6.11)$$

Figure 6.10: Ergodic capacity versus $PSNR^{D_T}$ of the proposed I2V-VLC system for the vehicle in lane 1.

In Fig. 6.10, we demonstrate the capacity versus $PSNR^{D_T}$ (with PSNR computed at a particular value of D_T) performance of the proposed I2V-VLC system. The considered range of $D_T = 3.5 - 6.5$. When $E_T = \frac{1}{500}$ (with maximum exposure time), the minimum and maximum value of capacity is $C_{min} \approx 62$ bps and $C_{max} \approx 63$ bps, respectively. Moreover, when $E_T = \frac{1}{800}$, $C_{min} \approx 59$ bps and $C_{max} \approx 59.5$ bps, respectively. Further, when $E_T = \frac{1}{1000}$, $C_{min} \approx 58.8$ bps and $C_{max} \approx 59.5$ bps, respectively. It is worth mentioning that the capacity results demonstrated in Fig. 6.10 correspond to a specific frame rate of the camera (60 fps in this work). However, a camera with a higher frame rate will offer a higher data rate.

Remark 6.2: Note that, when using camera as a Rx, the Tx and Rx need to be properly synchronized. To be more specific, if the frame rate of the camera is 60 fps, then the frequency of the transmitted signal must be ≤ 30 Hz.

Remark 6.3: The channel capacity (**maximum throughput**) signifies the highest rate of information transfer to achieve a target BER. Therefore, an inverse relationship exists between channel capacity and BER [129]. Since channel capacity and BER are

Figure 6.11: Image of the experimental lab setup of a real-time I2V-VLC scenario under LOS blockage with the vehicle in lane 1.

comparable, one can anticipate that the BER versus PSNR will also provide similar insights.

6.4.5 Impact of LOS Blockage

In this subsection, we examine the impact of the LOS blockage on the BER performance of the proposed I2V-VLC system. Because of the high dependency of the VLC on the LOS, analyzing the impact of the LOS blockage is crucial. Fig. 6.11 depicts the experimental setup of the proposed I2V-VLC system considering the LOS blockage. To gain further insights related to Fig. 6.11, we provide the schematic diagram of the proposed system under LOS blockage, as shown in Fig. 6.12. Considering Fig. 6.12, D_{Tx} denotes the center-to-center distance from the right edge of the lane 1 and the Tx. On the other side, D_o denotes the center-to-center distance from the right edge of the lane 1 and the LOS blocking object. The Tx and Rx FOVs are shown to demonstrate the part of the Tx captured by the camera under a LOS blockage-based communication scenario.

In Fig. 6.13, we demonstrate the BER performance of the proposed I2V-VLC system under LOS blockage with an E_T of $\frac{1}{500}$. We consider two different blockage scenarios (i) 60 % LOS blockage and (ii) 80 % LOS blockage scenario (worst-case

Figure 6.12: Schematic diagram of the proposed I2V-VLC system under LOS blockage.

scenario). Note that, 60 % LOS blockage scenario implies that D_o is 60 % of D_{Tx} . To be more specific, the LOS blocking object covers the 60 % of the Tx FOV. The same interpretation applies to 80 % LOS blockage scenario. For the 80 % LOS blockage, we consider $D_o = 0.18$ m. Considering 60 % LOS blockage scenario, BER = 0.4 for D_T of 0.5 m and BER = 0.2 for D_T of 1.5 m, whereas, for $D_T \geq 2.5$ m, BER is almost constant with a finite value of ≈ 0.05 . For 80 % LOS blockage scenario (which is worst-case), BER = 0.5 for D_T of 0.5 m and BER = 0.4 for D_T of 1.5 m, whereas, for $D_T \geq 2.5$ m, BER is almost constant with a finite value of ≈ 0.06 .

Observation 6.6: Compared to the BER performance of Fig. 6.5 (without LOS blockage), a significant increase is observed at D_T of 0.5 and 1.5 m in Fig. 6.13 (considering LOS blockage). Moreover, contrary to Fig. 6.5, wherein for $D_T \geq 2.5$, BER= 0, in Fig. 6.13, a non-zero finite value of BER is observed. Therefore, the impact of the LOS blockage on the proposed I2V-VLC system is envisioned. Further, despite considering worst-case LOS blockage scenario, there is not much deviation in the BER performance curves, as can be seen from Fig. 6.13. **It is mainly because utilizing the camera as an Rx offers enhanced performance, as discussed in Remark 1.**

Figure 6.13: BER performance of the proposed I2V-VLC system under LOS blockage for the vehicle in lane 1 and E_T of $\frac{1}{500}$.

6.5 Conclusions

An **experimental approach** for the **indoor testbed design** has been presented for the I2V-VLC system. A LED-based light source has been used as a traffic light (VLC Tx) for the experimental demonstration purpose, and an optical camera as a Rx. Based on the indoor testbed design of the proposed I2V-VLC system, comprehensive experimental demonstrations has been carried out for the first time in the literature. Intensity measurements for the considered VLC Tx have been carried out, and the corresponding beam profile is obtained in MATLAB. Based on the obtained beam profile, channel modeling has been done. After developing the indoor testbed, we implement it in a real-time I2V-VLC scenario by experimentally examining different performance metrics, such as BER, PSNR, and capacity. Considering the BER results, it has been observed that despite having the impact of background-induced noise (in both day and night times), the BER performance is not altered much when using camera as an Rx. Another important performance metric to assess the link quality

when using the camera as an Rx, i.e., PSNR has also been investigated. Furthermore, the ergodic capacity is also experimentally demonstrated for the proposed I2V-VLC system. Moreover, LOS blockage-based I2V-VLC scenarios have been also considered and analyzed. It has been observed that despite considering worst-case LOS blockage scenario, the BER performance is not much altered when using the camera as an Rx. Note that, all the experimental findings have been demonstrated for different exposure times of the camera, which is a very critical parameter when using the camera as an Rx.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future Works

In this chapter, a brief recap of the main contributions of this thesis, key findings, and direction for future work are discussed.

7.1 Conclusions

This dissertation has presented and analyzed the indoor and outdoor OWC systems. For the FSO system, by considering a terrestrial outdoor scenario, two novel TLS schemes (namely TTLS and METWS) have been proposed to enhance the diversity and overall performance of the FSO systems. Considering the VLC systems, we first analyzed the DMT of an indoor VLC scenario for the first time with random mobility of the user and provided new insights. Further, we investigated V2V-VLC based outdoor scenarios with a comprehensive modeling and performance analysis. Furthermore, an experimental indoor testbed design for the outdoor I2V-VLC system is proposed, and novel findings have been presented and discussed.

In the first chapter, we have provided an insightful overview of the FSO and VLC systems under consideration. To this end, we have emphasized the advantages, applications, and limitations of the FSO and VLC systems. A detailed overview of the indoor VLC and outdoor VLC (both V2V and I2V) is also provided. Further, an extensive literature review emphasizing the state-of-the-art for both FSO and VLC systems is provided w.r.t. the proposed work. Furthermore, the motivation and contributions of the work are discussed in detail.

In the second chapter, intending to enhance the diversity and overall performance of the FSO system, two novel TLS schemes (namely TTLS and METWS) have been proposed and analyzed for an outdoor terrestrial scenario. Considering a practical FSO communication scenario, both perfect and imperfect CSI-based scenarios are analyzed. The performance of the two proposed schemes has been analyzed using BER, diversity gain, etc. Firstly, the two proposed schemes are studied for a MISO set-up, and then the performance of the two proposed schemes is also demonstrated for the MIMO set-up. To gain further insights, the performance of the two proposed schemes has been compared with the conventional STLS and RC schemes. Moreover, the performance of the two proposed TLS schemes is analyzed covering the entire AT regime for the first time. Under a practical (erroneous) feedback scenario, it has been found that the proposed TTLS scheme significantly outperforms the traditional STLS scheme in terms of error performance. It is observed through the key findings that under an erroneous feedback scenario, the conventional STLS scheme slightly outperforms the proposed TTLS scheme for a low SNR regime. However, the corresponding BER is very high and it cannot be the target BER for a practical communication system. On the other side, at high SNR values, the proposed TTLS scheme completely outperforms the conventional STLS scheme under an erroneous feedback scenario. Moreover, the proposed METWS outperforms the conventional STLS as well as RC schemes despite feedback errors.

The third chapter emphasized analyzing the DMT for the OWC systems. To this end, we mainly focused on indoor VLC and outdoor FSO systems. For the DMT investigation of the indoor VLC system, we considered the random radial movement of the end-user in the proposed system model. The optimal DMT for both the SISO and MIMO VLC systems have been analyzed. Novel analytical expressions for the PDF, outage probability, and outage diversity order for the SISO-VLC and MIMO-VLC systems have been derived. Moreover, we extend our study to the outdoor FSO system. For the first time, a limited feedback-based DMT has been investigated for the FSO system under different transmission scenarios. To this end, we considered a MIMO-FSO setup and investigated the DMT for single-rate and adaptive-rate transmission

scenarios. Some striking insights are envisioned in the form of new observations for the first time. It is observed through the key findings that the optimal outage diversity gain in the case of the MIMO-VLC system not only depends on the half-power angle of the LED transmitter, but also the optimal singular values of the channel matrix. Further, the DMT performance of gamma-gamma MIMO-FSO channel is significantly better as compared to the negative exponential MIMO-FSO channel for both single-rate as well as adaptive-rate transmission scenarios.

The fourth chapter emphasized the thorough modeling of an outdoor V2V-VLC system and performance investigation under practical considerations. Contrary to the existing literature, the lateral movement and the longitudinal/inter-vehicle separation of the vehicle have been modeled as random with a specific distribution function. In addition, a new channel model that takes into account the combined effects of path loss and AT has been taken into consideration. Path loss has a substantial impact on the outdoor V2V-VLC system, which is worth highlighting. Moreover, a path loss associated with the road surface reflections and LOS blocking is also modeled. Further, under various weather scenarios, the performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model has been examined using several metrics, including path loss, outage probability, ABER, diversity, and DCMC capacity. Moreover, it has been noted that the combined impact of the path loss and atmospheric turbulence is significant on the V2V-VLC system.

In the fifth chapter, an outdoor V2V-VLC model under a shadowing-based transmission scenario has been proposed. The performance of the proposed V2V-VLC model has been analyzed with the DMT metric. Motivated by the study of Chapter 4, we aim to minimize the path loss at the Rx. To this end, we have proposed a novel hemispherical optical concentrator-based Rx structure (offering an omnidirectional gain). Moreover, a composite channel model with the combined impact of shadowing and AT is considered to analyze the optimal DMT for the proposed V2V-VLC model. Novel analytical expressions for the path loss, PDF of the channel matrix, joint PDF of the ordered singular values of the channel matrix, outage probability (in terms of the multiplexing gain and other VLC parameters), and outage diversity order are developed. It is observed that the optical concentrators-based Rx structure can significantly enhance

the system performance under shadowing. It is mainly because of its omnidirectional gain ability.

The sixth chapter presented an indoor experimental testbed design for an outdoor I2V-VLC system. We have emphasized an experimental demonstration of the communication between the traffic light (i.e., the Tx) and the camera (i.e., the Rx) under different realistic I2V-VLC scenarios. Moreover, to obtain the beam profile, we have emphasized the intensity measurements of the Tx. We consider the beam profile as a basis for the channel modeling. Different performance metrics are experimentally examined, such as BER, PSNR, and capacity. Further, LOS blockage-based I2V-VLC scenarios are also examined, and some striking insights are envisioned. Finally, all the experimental findings are demonstrated for different exposure times of the camera for the first time. It has been observed that employing an optical camera as the Rx significantly enhances the system performance. This is because camera-based Rx is composed of an array of photodetectors which eventually results in enhanced SNR and the reduced BER.

7.2 Future Scope of Work

There are several directions in which this work can be extended. Some important extensions for future work are outlined as follows:

- The two proposed TLS schemes (namely TTLS and METWS) in Chapter 2 could be analytically analyzed under the consideration of the G-G channel model, incorporating the impact of pointing error into the analysis. Further, a future extension of this work may also include the analytical study of the two proposed schemes for MIMO configurations. Moreover, similar to the proposed METWS TLS scheme, new error-tolerant TLS schemes can be proposed to further enhance the performance of the FSO systems.
- The DMT analyzed for the OWC systems in Chapter 3 emphasizes an optimization problem formulation-based technique to analyze the optimal DMT. As a

future extension of this work, some new techniques can be explored to derive the optimal DMT that offers reduced analytical complexity.

- The proposed outdoor V2V-VLC model presented and analyzed in Chapter 4 considers a two-lane road-based communication scenario. As a future extension of this work, the proposed outdoor V2V-VLC model can be extended for a multiple-lanes-based communication scenario. Moreover, analyzing the parameters related to the mobility of the vehicle (such as lateral movement and inter-vehicle separation) would be an interesting research problem.
- The shadowing-based outdoor V2V-VLC model proposed in Chapter 5 considered the two communicating vehicles to be in the same lane. As a future extension of this work, we would like to consider a more realistic V2V scenario by considering communication between two vehicles on the different lanes. Apart from this, in modeling VLC-based vehicular communications with multiple lanes, one need to consider *(i)* the vehicles lane changing rate, which is a critical parameter, particularly in urban areas where lane changing is more often, *(ii)* the speed, and dimensions (height, width, and length) of nearby vehicles, and *(iii)* the non-identical path loss.
- The indoor experimental testbed design for an outdoor I2V-VLC system presented in Chapter 6 considered a single traffic light (Tx). Moreover, the proposed work can be extended for multiple Txs. To gain further insights, the proposed testbed design can be extended for the implementation of the next-generation-based ITSs.

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Appendix A

Proof of Eq. (2.18)

The derivation for obtaining the closed-form solution of (2.18) is given as below:

$$\text{Let } I_1 = \int_0^\infty Q(\sqrt{(u_1 + u_2)^2 \bar{\gamma}}) f_{u_1}(u_1) du_1 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Substituting (2.16) in (A.1), writing q-function in terms of erfc function, and using the closed-form solutions (14a) and (14b) given in [111], a closed-form solution of I_1 is obtained as:

$$I_1 = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{u_2} \mathcal{I}(1, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, u_2 \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}) - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{2u_2} \mathcal{I}(1, 2\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, u_2 \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Hence, (2.18) becomes:

$$P_e(\bar{\gamma}) = \int_0^\infty I_1 f_{u_2}(u_2) du_2 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

On substituting (2.17) and (A.2) in (A.3), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} P_e(\bar{\gamma}) &= \int_0^\infty \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{u_2} \mathcal{I}(1, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, u_2 \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}) [2e^{-u_2} - 2e^{-2u_2}] du_2 \\ &\quad - \int_0^\infty \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{2u_2} \mathcal{I}(1, 2\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, u_2 \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}) [2e^{-u_2} - 2e^{-2u_2}] du_2 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

To simplify (A.4), we can have the following considerations:

$$R_1 = 2 \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} \mathcal{I}(1, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, u_2 \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}) du_2}_{A_1} - 2 \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{-u_2} \mathcal{I}(1, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, u_2 \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}) du_2}_{A_2} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$R_2 = 2 \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{u_2} \mathcal{I}(1, 2\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, u_2 \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}) du_2}_{B_1} - 2 \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} \mathcal{I}(1, 2\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, u_2 \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}) du_2}_{B_2} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

To evaluate A_1 and A_2 , B_1 and B_2 , we use the closed-form solution (14c) given in [111]. Therefore, (A.5) and (A.6) reduces to:

$$\begin{aligned}
R_1 = & 2 \left\{ \left[\mathcal{I} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{2}}, 1, 0 \right) - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}} e^{\frac{1}{2\gamma}} \mathcal{I} \left(1, 0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\gamma}} \right) \right] \right\} \\
& - 2 \left\{ \left[\mathcal{I} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{2}}, 2, 0 \right) - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}} e^{\frac{1}{2\gamma}} e^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \mathcal{I} \left(1, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\gamma}} \right) \right] \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{A.7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R_2 = & \left\{ \left[\mathcal{I} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{2}}, 1, 0 \right) - \mathcal{I} \left(1, -\sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}}, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}} \right) \right] \right\} \\
& - \left\{ \left[\mathcal{I} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{2}}, 2, 0 \right) - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}} e^{\frac{2}{\gamma}} \mathcal{I} \left(1, 0, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}} \right) \right] \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{A.8}$$

Appendix B

Proof of Eq. (2.24)

A closed-form solution of $P_{e_1}(\bar{\gamma})$ is given by (2.19) and a closed-form solution corresponding to $P_{e_2}(\bar{\gamma})$ can be obtained as follows: Let

$$S_1 = \int_0^\infty Q\left(\sqrt{(r_1 + r_2)^2 \bar{\gamma}}\right) f_{r_1}(r_1) dr_1. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

On substituting (2.21) into (B.1) and using the same methodology adopted for deriving (A.1), a closed-form solution of (B.1) is obtained as:

$$S_1 = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{2r_2} \mathcal{I}\left(1, 2\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, r_2\sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}\right). \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Therefore, $P_{e_2}(\bar{\gamma})$ can be expressed as follows:

$$P_{e_2}(\bar{\gamma}) = (1 - P_c)^2 \int_0^\infty S_1 f_{r_2}(r_2) dr_2. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Substituting (2.22), (B.2) into (B.3), and using (14c) given in [111], we get a closed-form solution of (B.3) as:

$$P_{e_2}(\bar{\gamma}) = (1 - P_c)^2 \left\{ \left[\mathcal{I}\left(\sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}, 2, 0\right) - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} \mathcal{I}\left(1, 0, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}\right) \right] \right\}. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Now to obtain a closed-form solution of $P_{e_3}(\bar{\gamma})$, we proceed as follows:

Let

$$X_1 = \int_0^\infty Q\left(\sqrt{(u_1 + r_2)^2 \bar{\gamma}}\right) f_{u_1}(u_1) du_1. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Substituting (2.16) in (B.5) and following the same procedure as adopted for deriving closed-form of (A.1), a closed-form solution of X_1 can be obtained as:

$$X_1 = \left[\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{r_2} \mathcal{I}\left(1, \sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, r_2\sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}\right) \right] - \left[\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} e^{2r_2} \mathcal{I}\left(1, 2\sqrt{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}}, r_2\sqrt{\frac{\bar{\gamma}}{2}}\right) \right]. \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Therefore, employing (2.22), (B.6) and (14c) given in [111], $P_{e_3}(\bar{\gamma})$ can be obtained as below:

$$P_{e_3}(\bar{\gamma}) = P_c(1 - P_c) \int_0^\infty X_1 f_{r_2}(r_2) dr_2 = P_c(1 - P_c)(\mathfrak{S}_7 - \mathfrak{S}_8 - \mathfrak{S}_9 + \mathfrak{S}_{10}), \quad (\text{B.7})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}_7 &= 2 \left[\mathfrak{I}_1 - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}} e^{\frac{1}{2\bar{\gamma}}} \mathfrak{I}_2 \right], \\ \mathfrak{S}_8 &= 2 \left[\mathfrak{I}_1 - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}} e^{\frac{1}{2\bar{\gamma}}} \mathfrak{I}_2 - \mathfrak{I}_5 + \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}} e^{\frac{1}{2\bar{\gamma}}} e^{\frac{1}{\bar{\gamma}}} \mathfrak{I}_3 \right], \\ \mathfrak{S}_9 &= \left[\mathfrak{I}_1 - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}} \mathfrak{I}_6 \right], \\ \mathfrak{S}_{10} &= \left[\mathfrak{I}_1 - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}} \mathfrak{I}_6 - \mathfrak{I}_5 + \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma}} e^{\frac{2}{\bar{\gamma}}} \mathfrak{I}_4 \right], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

where \mathfrak{S}_1 through \mathfrak{S}_6 are defined in Subsection 2.4.1.

Appendix C

Proof of Lemma 3.1

Let $\{P_i\}_{i=1}^K$ be an arbitrary power codebook. Moreover, we consider two constraints such that $0 \leq P_1 < \dots < P_K$ and $\sum_{i=1}^K \Pr(\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H}) = i) P_i \leq \text{SNR}$. It should be noticed that for an optimal feedback scheme, the above mentioned power constraints must be considered. Moreover, we need to illustrate that the optimal index mapping must be in line with (3.48).

Consider the following index mapping and a different feedback mechanism using the same power codebook:

$$\mathcal{I}^*(\mathbf{H}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } C(\mathbf{H}, P_{\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H})}) < R \\ \min \{i : i \in \{1, \dots, \mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H})\}, C(\mathbf{H}, P_i) \geq R\}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

This has the same impact on the likelihood of an outage as $\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H})$. However, the newly developed feedback scheme's average transmit power is

$$\sum_{i=1}^K \Pr(\mathcal{I}^*(\mathbf{H}) = i) P_i \leq \sum_{i=1}^K \Pr(\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H}) = i) P_i \quad (\text{C.2})$$

Taking this average transmit power constraint into consideration, we must deal with two probabilistic events. First, all the channels that are in outage are mapped to $\mathcal{I} = 1$. Second, an event that the channel is not in outage is mapped to the smallest power in the power codebook that has the ability to “invert” \mathbf{H} . When this power level is used at the transmitter, it indicates that the mutual information is more than R .

We still need to show that no set of channel conditions with positive probability measure that can be inverted by some P_i , $i \geq 2$, is mapped to $\mathcal{I} = 1$. On the other side, let us consider a set \mathcal{S} and an index $j \geq 2$ such that $\Pr(\mathbf{H} \in \mathcal{S}) = \tau_S > 0$ and $C(\mathbf{H}, P_j) \geq R$, $\mathcal{I}(\mathbf{H}) = 1$, $\forall \mathbf{H} \in \mathcal{S}$. With this, there exists a $P_j^* \in (P_{j-1}, P_j)$ such that $\Pr(P^m(\mathbf{H}; R_j) \in (P_j^*, P_j)) = \tau_S$ where $P^m(\mathbf{H}; R)$ satisfies $C(\mathbf{H}, P^m(\mathbf{H}; R)) = R$, i.e., the minimum power required to invert \mathbf{H} . With all choices of \mathcal{S} subject to $\Pr(\mathbf{H} \in \mathcal{S}) = \tau_S$ are same in terms of both average power and outage probability, we can consider

$$\mathcal{S} = \{\mathbf{H} : P^m(\mathbf{H}; R) \in (P_j^*, P_j)\}. \quad (\text{C.3})$$

Let us consider another feedback scheme with optimal index mapping $\mathcal{I}^*(\mathbf{H})$ and the power codebook

$$\{P_1, \dots, P_{j-1}, P_j^*, P_{j+1}, \dots, P_K\}. \quad (\text{C.4})$$

By construction, this results in giving the same outage probability as that obtained by the codebook $\{P_i\}_{i=1}^K$ together with $\mathcal{I}^*(\mathbf{H})$. On the other side, the newly constructed feedback scheme uses less average power, because $P_j^* < P_j$, i.e., the power constraint is inactive. Hence, the optimal index mapping must have the form (3.48), which results in outage probability of $P_{out}(R, P_K^*)$.

Furthermore, since $P_1^* < \dots < P_K^*$, the event $C(P_{i-1}^*, \mathbf{H}) > R$ also implies $C(P_i^*, \mathbf{H}) > R$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} & \Pr\left(C(P_i^*, \mathbf{H}) > R, C(P_{i-1}^*, \mathbf{H}) < R\right) \\ &= \Pr\left(C(P_{i-1}^*, \mathbf{H}) < R\right) - \Pr\left(C(P_i^*, \mathbf{H}) < R\right) \\ &= P_{out}\left(R, P_{i-1}^*\right) - P_{out}\left(R, P_i^*\right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.5})$$

Eventually, the average power of the system is given by

$$\begin{aligned} & [P_{out}(R, P_K^*) + 1 - P_{out}(R, P_1^*)] P_1^* \\ &+ \sum_{i=2}^K [P_{out}(R, P_{i-1}^*) + 1 - P_{out}(R, P_i^*)] P_i^*. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.6})$$

Since $P_{out}(R, P_K)$ is a monotonically decreasing function of P_K for any given $R > 0$, the optimal power codebook is the solution to (3.47).

Appendix D

Proof of Proposition 3.1

Consider an optimal power codebook with largest power level P_K^* . Corresponding to P_K^* , we first derive an upper bound on the SNR exponent. If SNR is denoted as τ and $\{\bar{P}_i\}$ represents the solution to (3.47)). Then, a more relaxed version of (3.47) can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \max P_K \\
 & \text{s.t. } [P_{out}(R, P_K) + 1 - P_{out}(R, P_1)] P_1 \leq \tau \\
 & \quad [P_{out}(R, P_{i-1}) - P_{out}(R, P_i)] P_i \leq \tau, i \geq 2 \\
 & \quad 0 \leq P_1 < \dots < P_K.
 \end{aligned} \tag{D.1}$$

Moreover, it is intuitive that $\bar{P}_K \geq P_K^*$. Further, the constraints of (D.1) imply $\sum_{i=1}^K \frac{\tau}{\bar{P}_i} \geq 1$. This leads to $\bar{P}_1 \leq K\tau$; otherwise, $\sum_{i=1}^K \frac{\tau}{\bar{P}_i} < K\frac{1}{K} = 1$. Since K is a finite constant, we have $\bar{P}_1 \leq \tau$. The implication of Lemma 2 results in:

$$P_{out}(R, \bar{P}_1) \stackrel{\cdot}{\geq} \tau^{-J(r,1)} = \tau^{-d_{out,1}^*(r)}. \tag{D.2}$$

Furthermore, the constraints of (D.1) require $\frac{\tau}{\bar{P}_2} + P_{out}(R, \bar{P}_2) \geq P_{out}(R, \bar{P}_1)$. This results in

$$\frac{\tau}{\bar{P}_2} + P_{out}(R, \bar{P}_2) \stackrel{\cdot}{\geq} \tau^{-d_{out,1}^*(r)}. \tag{D.3}$$

For any $\delta > 0$, if $\bar{P}_2 \doteq \tau^{-J(r,1+d_{out,1}^*(r)+\delta)}$, then

$$\frac{\tau}{\bar{P}_2} + P_{out}(R, \bar{P}_2) \doteq \tau^{-d_{out,1}^*(r)-\delta} + \tau^{-J(r,1+d_{out,1}^*(r)+\delta)}$$

which contradicts (D.1). This is because

$$J(r, 1 + d_{out,1}^*(r) + \delta) > J(r, 1) = d_{out,1}^*(r). \quad (\text{D.4})$$

Hence, $\bar{P}_2 \dot{\leq} \tau^{1+d_{out,1}^*(r)}$, and thus

$$P_{out}(R, \bar{P}_2) \dot{\geq} \tau^{-J(r, 1+d_{out,1}^*(r))} = \tau^{-d_{out,2}^*(r)}. \quad (\text{D.5})$$

Finally, by induction, we get $\bar{P}_K \dot{\leq} \tau^{1+d_{out,K-1}^*(r)}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} P_{out}(R, P_K^*) &\geq P_{out}(R, \bar{P}_K) \dot{\geq} \tau^{-J(r, 1+d_{out,K-1}^*(r))} \\ &= \tau^{-d_{out,K}^*(r)}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.6})$$

Eventually, a lower bound on P_K^* is obtained according to the following selection:

$$P_1 = \frac{\tau}{K}, P_2 = \frac{\tau}{K P_{out}(P_1)}, \dots, P_K = \frac{\tau}{K P_{out}(P_{K-1})}. \quad (\text{D.7})$$

As the above P_i 's satisfy the constraints of (3.47), we have $P_K^* \geq P_K$. By construction, $P_1 \dot{=} \tau$, $P_2 \dot{=} \tau^{1+d_{out,1}^*(r)}$, \dots , $P_K \dot{=} \tau^{1+d_{out,K-1}^*(r)}$. Therefore,

$$P_{out}(R, P_K^*) \leq P_{out}(R, P_K) \dot{=} \tau^{-d_{out,K}^*(r)}. \quad (\text{D.8})$$

Hence, proved.

Appendix E

Proof of Proposition 3.2

Consider an arbitrary class of deterministic feedback schemes \mathcal{F} providing a multiplexing gain of r . For a certain class of feedback scheme, the outage probability can be written as $P_{out,\mathcal{F}} \doteq \tau^{-d_{out,\mathcal{F}}(r)}$. We first derive an upper bound on $d_{out,\mathcal{F}}(r)$. Let $p_i, i = 1, \dots, K$, such that $P_i \doteq \tau^{p_i}$, where $p_i > 0$. Using the long-term power constraint (3.30), we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^K \Pr(\mathcal{I} = i) \tau^{p_i} \leq \tau. \quad (\text{E.1})$$

Without violating the generality, assume that $0 < p_1 \leq \dots \leq p_K$. Let us consider \bar{K} be any integer $\in \{1, \dots, K\}$ such that $p_{\bar{K}} \leq 1$ and $p_{\bar{K}+1} > 1$. In order to have the existence of such a \bar{K} , we use the convention $p_{K+1} = \infty$, else (D.3) will be violated. Further, (D.3) indicates that $\Pr(\mathcal{I} = i) \tau^{p_i} \leq \tau, \forall i$. Hence, $\Pr(\mathcal{I} = i) \leq \tau^{1-p_i}$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Pr(\mathcal{I} = i) R_i}{\log \tau} &= r_i \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \Pr(\mathcal{I} = i) \\ &= 0, \forall i \geq \bar{K} + 1. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.2})$$

Herein, \bar{K} corresponds to the number of regions having a significant contribution to the overall throughput. On the other side, $K - \bar{K}$ can be anticipated as the number of regions that correspond to improving the overall reliability.

Let $r_{\max} = \max(r_1, \dots, r_{\bar{K}})$. By (3.32), $r \leq r_{\max}$. Let us consider the first \bar{K} regions of \mathcal{F} . Moreover, the power levels associated with these regions have dominant SNR exponent less than or equal to 1. For the purpose of completeness, we consider another class of feedback schemes $\hat{\mathcal{F}}$ such that $\hat{r}_1 = r < r_{\max}$, $\hat{r}_i = r_{\min} \leq r_i, \forall i \geq 2$, and

employing $\hat{P}_1 \doteq \tau$. With this, we can write $P_{out, \hat{\mathcal{F}}} \doteq \tau^{-d_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}}(r)}$. Maximizing $d_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}}(r)$ will result an upper bound on $d_{out, \mathcal{F}}(r)$.

Our objective is to minimize the SNR exponent of outage. For this, we consider $\hat{\mathcal{F}}$ such that

$$\hat{P}_i > 1, \forall i \geq 2 \tag{E.3}$$

where $\hat{P}_i \doteq \tau^{p_i}$. On the other side, assume the contrary, i.e., $\hat{P}_2 \doteq \tau$. Thus, $d_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}}(r)$ can be upper bounded by $d_{K-1}^*(r_{\min})$. It can be easily shown that such an upper bound lies strictly below $d_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}}(r)$ when (E.1) is assumed. Further, assuming (E.1) implies, $\bar{K} = 1$.

Appendix F

Proof of Eq. (4.63)

The derivation for obtaining the closed-form solution of (4.62) is given as below:

Considering (4.60), we apply the change of variables as $cL_i = x$, $q = 2 + 2/\epsilon$.

Further, employing the PDFs of L_i and V_D into (4.62), we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_{\text{LOS}}^{\text{PL,av}} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{D_R^2(d)^{2/\epsilon}}{\xi^2(z_2 - z_1)} \times \\
 &\times \int_{p_1}^{p_2} V_D^2 \frac{\varrho}{p_2 - p_1} dv_d \int_{z_1}^{z_2} \frac{1}{(x/c)^q} e^{\left(-x \left(\frac{D_R c}{\xi x}\right)^{\epsilon/2}\right)} \frac{dx}{c} \\
 &= \frac{D_R^2(d)^{2/\epsilon} c^{q-1} \varrho}{\xi^2(p_2 - p_1)(z_2 - z_1)} \times \\
 &\times \int_{p_1=0\text{cm}}^{p_2=16\text{cm}} V_D^2 dV_D \int_{z_1}^{z_2} \frac{1}{x^q} e^{-\left(x^{1-\epsilon/2} \left(\frac{D_R c}{\xi}\right)^{\epsilon/2}\right)} dx. \tag{F.1}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, considering the inner integral of (F.1), a closed-form solution can be obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I &= \left(\frac{-\text{ExpIntegralE}\left[\frac{(\epsilon/2)-q}{(\epsilon/2)-1}, \left(\frac{D_R c}{\xi}\right)^{\epsilon/2} \times z_1^{1-\epsilon/2}\right] z_1^{1-q}}{(\epsilon/2) - 1} + \right. \\
 &\left. \frac{\text{ExpIntegralE}\left[\frac{(\epsilon/2)-q}{(\epsilon/2)-1}, \left(\frac{D_R c}{\xi}\right)^{\epsilon/2} \times z_2^{1-\epsilon/2}\right] z_2^{1-q}}{(\epsilon/2) - 1} \right). \tag{F.2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Further, the outer integral in (F.1) can be swiftly evaluated, and the complete closed-form expression is given in (4.63).

Appendix G

Proof of Eq. (4.66)

A closed-form solution corresponding to (4.65) can be obtained as follows: Employing (4.64) and the PDFs of X , Y , and V_D into (4.65), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_{\text{NLOS,IV}}^{\text{PL,av}} &= \frac{A_{IV}^2 I_{V_1-IV}^{2/\epsilon} D_R^2 I_{IV-V_2}^{2/\epsilon} \varrho}{\xi^4 \times (p_2 - p_1) \times (y_2 - y_1) \times (x_2 - x_1)} \times \\
 &\times \int_{p_1=0\text{cm}}^{p_2=16\text{cm}} \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \frac{V_D^2}{X^q Y^q} e^{\left(-c(X+Y)\left(\frac{D_R}{\xi(X+Y)}\right)^{\epsilon/2}\right)} \\
 &\times dx dy dV_D. \tag{G.1}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since the value of ϵ is small, therefore, we assume $\left(\frac{D_R}{\xi(X+Y)}\right)^{\epsilon/2} = \left(\frac{D_R}{\xi(X+Y)}\right)$. Now, we solve the integrals in (G.1) one-by-one. For example, solving the inner-most integral as:

$$I_1 = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \frac{1}{X^q} e^{\frac{-cD_R}{\xi}} dx = e^{\frac{-cD_R}{\xi}} \left(\frac{x_1^{1-q} - x_2^{1-q}}{q-1} \right). \tag{G.2}$$

Similarly the rest of the two integrals can be evaluated, and a closed-form solution is obtained as given in (4.66).

Appendix H

Proof of Eq. (4.69)

Note that, for path loss corresponding to NLOS-RS, we write $\cos \phi_i = \frac{I_{V_1-RS}}{L_i^{V_1-RS}}$ and $\cos \delta_{RS,i} = \frac{I_{RS-V_2}}{L_i^{RS-V_2}}$. Therefore, the NLOS path loss corresponding to the RS, i.e., $h_{\text{NLOS,RS}}^{\text{PL,av}}$, in (4.68) can be mathematically formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_{\text{NLOS,RS}}^{\text{PL,av}} &= z \times 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^2 \left(\frac{A_{RS} (\cos \phi_i)^{1/\epsilon}}{\xi(L_i^{V_1-RS})} \right)^2 \right. \\
 &\quad \times \left(\frac{D_R (\cos \delta_{RS,i})^{1/\epsilon}}{\xi(L_i^{RS-V_2})} \right)^2 \\
 &\quad \times \exp \left(-c(L_i^{V_1-RS} + L_i^{RS-V_2}) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. \times \left(\frac{D_R}{\xi(L_i^{V_1-RS} + L_i^{RS-V_2})} \right)^{\epsilon/2} \right) \right). \tag{H.1}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, employing (H.1), PDFs of R , S , Y , and V_D into (4.68), we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_{\text{NLOS,RS}}^{\text{PL,av}} &= z \times 10 \log_{10} \times \\
 &\quad \times \frac{A_{RS}^2 I_{V_1-RS}^2 D_R^2 \times \varrho \times 3}{\xi^4 \times (p_2 - p_1) \times (s_2 - s_1) \times (r_2 - r_1) \times k\pi} \times \\
 &\quad \times \int_{p_1=0\text{cm}}^{p_2=16\text{cm}} \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \int_{s_1}^{s_2} \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{V_D^2}{R^q S^2} e^{\left(-c(R+S) \left(\frac{D_R}{\xi(R+S)} \right)^{\epsilon/2} \right)} \times \\
 &\quad \times \frac{1}{y^{\frac{k-1}{k}} \sqrt{1-y^{2/k}}} dr ds dy dV_D. \tag{H.2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, we can solve the integrals in (H.2) one-by-one. Note that, a closed-form solution corresponding to the integral in (H.2) incorporating the limits of y can be determined using MATHEMATICA software.

Appendix I

Proof of Eq. (4.75)

To determine the closed-form expression corresponding to (4.74), we can express $C_{\text{DCMC}}(h_j) = I + R$ with the following considerations:

$$I = \int_0^\infty 0.5f(y|x=0, h_i) \times \log_2 \left[\frac{f(y|x=0, h_i)}{0.5f(y|x=0, h_i) + 0.5f(y|x=1, h_i)} \right] dy. \quad (\text{I.1})$$

$$R = \int_{c=\sum_i h_i}^\infty 0.5f(y|x=1, h_i) \times \log_2 \left[\frac{f(y|x=1, h_i)}{0.5f(y|x=0, h_i) + 0.5f(y|x=1, h_i)} \right] dy. \quad (\text{I.2})$$

Since $\log_2(\frac{a}{b}) = \log_2 a - \log_2 b$, therefore, we can express $I = I_1 - I_2$ as below:

$$I_1 = \int_0^\infty 0.5f(y|x=0, h_i) \log_2 [f(y|x=0, h_i)] dy. \quad (\text{I.3})$$

$$I_2 = \int_0^\infty 0.5f(y|x=0, h_i) \times \log_2 [0.5f(y|x=0, h_i) + 0.5f(y|x=1, h_i)] dy. \quad (\text{I.4})$$

Now, considering (4.71), and employing the change of variables method as $\frac{y^2}{2\sigma^2} = t$, a closed-form expression of (I.3) is obtained:

$$I_1 = -0.180337(2.83788 + \ln\sigma^2). \quad (\text{I.5})$$

Similarly, applying the change of variables to I_2 , we get a closed-form solution:

$$I_2 = \frac{K\sqrt{\pi/2}\sigma \ln(K)}{\ln 2} - \frac{K(c^2\sqrt{2\pi} - 4c\sigma + \sqrt{2\pi}\sigma^2)}{\sigma \ln(16)}. \quad (\text{I.6})$$

Therefore, a complete closed-form expression corresponding to I can be written using (I.5) and (I.6). Further, to determine the closed-form expression corresponding to (I.2), we can express (I.2) as $R = R_1 - R_2$ with the following considerations:

$$R_1 = \int_c^\infty 0.5f(y|x=1, h_i) \log_2 [f(y|x=1, h_i)] dy. \quad (\text{I.7})$$

$$R_2 = \int_c^\infty 0.5f(y|x=1, h_i) \times \log_2 [0.5f(y|x=0, h_i) + 0.5f(y|x=1, h_i)] dy. \quad (\text{I.8})$$

Now, applying the change of variables as $\frac{y^2}{2\sigma^2} = t$ and $\sqrt{2}\sigma\sqrt{t} - c = g$, we obtain the closed-form solution of R_1 :

$$R_1 = - \left(\frac{K\sqrt{\pi/2} \ln(2\pi\sigma^2)}{\sqrt{1/\sigma^2} \ln(4)} + \frac{K\sqrt{\pi/2}}{2\sqrt{1/\sigma^2} \ln(2)} \right). \quad (\text{I.9})$$

Similarly, we obtain the closed-form solution of R_2 as:

$$R_2 = \left(\frac{K\sqrt{\pi/2}\sigma \ln(K)}{\ln(2)} \right) - \left(\frac{K\sqrt{\pi/2}}{\frac{2}{\sigma} \ln(2)} \right). \quad (\text{I.10})$$

Therefore, a complete closed-form expression corresponding to R can be written using (I.9) and (I.10). Thus the ergodic DCMC capacity can be determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{DCMC}}^{\text{Ergodic}} &= \int_0^\infty C_{\text{DCMC}}(h_i) f_{h_i}(h_i) dh_i, \\ &= \int_0^\infty (I + R) f_{h_i}(h_i) dh_i. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{I.11})$$

Now, considering (4.11) and (4.12), $f_{h_i}(h_i)$ in (I.11) can be determined by applying the concept of transformation of RVs as:

$$f_{h_i}(h_i) = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\left(\ln\left(\frac{h_i}{h_{\text{PL,av}}}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2\right)^2}{8\sigma_x^2}\right)}{2h_i\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_x^2}, \quad h_i > 0. \quad (\text{I.12})$$

Further, to solve (I.11), we apply the change of variables method:

$$t_j = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{h_i}{h^{PL,av}}\right) + 2\sigma_x^2}{2\sigma_x}. \quad (\text{I.13})$$

Therefore, we get $f_{t_j}(t_j) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{t_j^2}{2}} dt_j = 1$. Thus the complete closed-form expression corresponding to (I.11) is given in (4.75).

Appendix J

Proof of Eq. (5.28)

Let us first consider the SVD of a matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_r \times N_t}$ with $N_r \leq N_t$ as:

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{Q}, \quad (\text{J.1})$$

where $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_r \times N_r}$ and $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_r \times N_t}$ are unitary matrices, $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is a diagonal matrix with $0 \leq \nu_1 \leq \nu_2 \leq \dots \leq \nu_q$ on the diagonal. This matrix factorization can be considered as an approach of change of variables. The Jacobian of standard matrix transformations from [120] are summarized here for the reader's convenience:

1. *Cholesky Decomposition:* $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{L}^T$, where $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times S}$ is symmetric positive definite matrix and $\mathbf{L} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times T}$ denotes lower triangular matrix with positive diagonal elements

$$d\mathbf{W} = 2^S \prod_{i=1}^S l_{ii}^{S+1-i} d\mathbf{L}. \quad (\text{J.2})$$

2. *LQ Decomposition:* $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{Q}$, where $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times T}$ is a real matrix for $S \leq T$ and $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times T}$ is a unitary matrix.

$$d\mathbf{C} = \prod_{i=1}^S l_{ii}^{T-i} d\mathbf{L}d\mathbf{Q}. \quad (\text{J.3})$$

3. *Eigenvalue Decomposition:* $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{U}^T$, where $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times S}$ represents a symmetric matrix, $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ is a diagonal matrix, $\text{diag}(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_S)$

$$d\mathbf{G} = \prod_{i < j} |\lambda_i - \lambda_j| d\mathbf{\Lambda}d\mathbf{U}. \quad (\text{J.4})$$

However, every real symmetric $S \times S$ matrix can be factored as $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{U}^T$ with the following properties:

- \mathbf{U} is orthogonal.
- $\mathbf{\Lambda} = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_S)$ is diagonal, with real diagonal elements.
- \mathbf{G} is diagonalizable by an orthogonal similarity transformation: $\mathbf{U}^T\mathbf{G}\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{\Lambda}$.
- The columns of \mathbf{U} are an orthonormal set of S eigenvectors: Thus we write $\mathbf{G}\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{G}[u_1 u_2 \cdots u_S] &= [u_1 u_2 \cdots u_S] \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & \lambda_S \end{bmatrix} \\ &= [\lambda_1 u_1 \quad \lambda_2 u_2 \quad \cdots \quad \lambda_S u_S]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{J.5})$$

Further, from the eigenvalue decomposition, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{G} &= \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{U}^T \\ &= [u_1 u_2 \cdots u_S] \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & \lambda_S \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1^T \\ u_2^T \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ u_S^T \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^S \lambda_i u_i u_i^T. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{J.6})$$

Therefore, we can express (J.4) as:

$$d\mathbf{G} = \prod_{i < j} \left| \sum_{i=1}^S \lambda_i u_i u_i^T - \sum_{j=1}^S \lambda_j u_j u_j^T \right| d\mathbf{\Lambda} d\mathbf{U}. \quad (\text{J.7})$$

The jacobian of (J.1) can easily be determined by expressing the SVD in terms of the following composition of transformations:

$$\mathbf{R} \Rightarrow (\mathbf{L}, \mathbf{Q}) \Rightarrow (\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{Q}) \Rightarrow (\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{\Lambda}, \mathbf{Q}). \quad (\text{J.8})$$

Therefore, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
d\mathbf{R} &= \prod_{i=1}^S l_{ii}^{T-1} d\mathbf{L} d\mathbf{Q} \text{ by (J.3)} \\
&= \frac{1}{2^S} \prod_{i=1}^S l_{ii}^{T-S-1} d\mathbf{W} d\mathbf{Q} \text{ by (J.2)} \\
&= \frac{1}{2^S} \prod_{i<j} \left| \sum_{i=1}^S \lambda_i u_i u_i^T - \sum_{j=1}^S \lambda_j u_j u_j^T \right| \times \\
&\quad \prod_{i=1}^S \lambda_i^{\frac{T-S-1}{2}} d\mathbf{\Lambda} d\mathbf{Q} d\mathbf{U} \text{ by (J.7)}. \tag{J.9}
\end{aligned}$$

Since $r \in (0, q)$, where q is the maximum multiplexing gain in the VLC channel, therefore, the jacobian of (J.1) with $S = q$ and $T = g$ can be obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned}
J_{g,q}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_q) &= \prod_{i<j} \left| \sum_{i=1}^q \lambda_i u_i u_i^T - \sum_{j=1}^q \lambda_j u_j u_j^T \right| \\
&\quad \times \prod_{i=1}^q \lambda_i^{\left(\frac{g-q-1}{2}\right)^+} d\mathbf{\Lambda} d\mathbf{Q} d\mathbf{U}. \tag{J.10}
\end{aligned}$$

Note that $\lambda_1 = \nu_1^2 \leq \lambda_2 = \nu_2^2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_q = \nu_q^2$, and considering the eigenvalue decomposition of $\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^T = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{U}^T$, we have:

$$d\mathbf{\Lambda} = 2^q \left(\prod_{i=1}^q \nu_i \right) (d\mathbf{\Sigma}). \tag{J.11}$$

Therefore, for a random matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_r \times N_t}$ with $N_r \leq N_t$, we can derive the pdf of $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ using (J.10) and (J.11) as:

$$\begin{aligned}
p_{(\mathbf{\Lambda})}(\mathbf{\Lambda}) &= \Omega_{N_t, N_r} \times \left(\prod_{i=1}^q \lambda_i^{\left(\frac{g-q-1}{2}\right)^+} \right) \\
&\quad \times \prod_{i<j} \left| \sum_{i=1}^q \lambda_i u_i u_i^T - \sum_{j=1}^q \lambda_j u_j u_j^T \right| \\
&\quad \times \left[\int_{\mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_r}} \int_{\mathbf{V}_{N_r, N_t}} p_{\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Lambda}^{\frac{1}{2}}\mathbf{Q})} d\mathbf{Q} d\mathbf{U} \right]. \tag{J.12}
\end{aligned}$$

Since $(\alpha_i)^+ = \frac{-\log \lambda_i}{\log \gamma}$, the joint PDF of α_i 's can be determined by applying the concept of transformation of random variables and is given in (5.28).

Publications Based on this Thesis

Published Journals:

- [J1] P. Sharda, A. Jaiswal, M. R. Bhatnagar, A. Garg, and L. Song, "Clustering based diversity improving transmit laser selection schemes using quantized feedback for FSO system," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 70, no. 7, pp. 6855-6868, July 2021.
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Technical Biography of Author

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